

EXPERIMENTAL SPEED DISTRIBUTION MEASUREMENTS
AND NHC SELF-ASSEMBLY ON Au(111)

by

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Dedicated to my grandfather,
Murray Heselton.

Abstract

Experimental speed distribution measurements

In [Part I](#), I present experimental measurements of the speed distribution in atomic beams produced by physical vapour deposition. These measurements are still needed in the literature, especially in collisionless beams produced by thermal evaporation. They also have a practical importance for the deposition of high-quality thin film materials, and may provide new strategies for advanced nanostructural control as well. Accordingly, we developed a unique experimental apparatus and procedure to measure this distribution. We used a rotating slotted cylinder velocity selector, or spindle, to mechanically generate velocity-selected atomic beams. Two detectors that operate on different physical principles, a hot-filament ionization gauge and a quartz crystal microbalance, were positioned directly above the spindle to detect transmitted atoms. The distribution of transmission measurements as a function of rotation speed is related to the speed distribution. This work reports on the theory-guided design and testing of the mechanical and control system equipment we built to perform these measurements. The experimental data obtained using an effusive oven, an open effusion cell, and an electron-beam evaporator highlight some interesting and important aspects of evaporation.

***N*-heterocyclic carbene self-assembly on Au(111)**

In [Part II](#), I present a detailed scanning tunnelling microscopy study of *N*-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) adsorption and self-assembly on Au(111). Surface modification and functionalization by the formation of a strongly bound self-assembled monolayer (SAM) of organic molecules has received considerable interest as a tool for the protection and stabilization of nanoparticles and the development of lab-on-chip sensors. Although SAMs are most commonly formed by the adsorption of alkanethiols, NHCs have recently attracted considerable interest. NHCs have important advantages compared to thiol-based systems, most notably their chemical tunability and ability to form strongly bound monolayers with improved stability. Given their novelty in the field of materials science, many fundamental properties of NHC-based SAMs are not well understood. This work provides much needed information on the NHC adsorption and self-assembly processes, including factors that control orientation, ordering, mobility, and adatom involvement. Efforts to understand these processes were crucial in advancing the chemistry and applications of thiol-based SAMs, and will similarly offer critical strategies for the design of NHC-based SAMs and their applications.

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I would also like to thank our outstanding collaborators. In physics, I would like to thank Felipe Crasto de Lima and Roberto Hiroki Miwa for providing an excellent collaboration between theory and experiment. In chemistry, I would like to thank Cathleen Crudden and members of her research group, especially Ishwar Singh and Alex Veinot for welcoming me into such an extraordinary research environment. It was truly wonderful and inspiring to work with such an incredible group of individuals.

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Statement of contributions

This thesis includes material that was a part of a collaborative study.

In [Part I](#) I present research that I conducted with Dr. Kevin Robbie. I carried out all experimental and theoretical efforts, including the design of mechanical, electrical, and software components, testing, modelling, and data acquisition and analysis. I am grateful for the contributions of former group members. The velocity selector design extended the work of Blair Lebert. I also acknowledge the thin film deposition software developed by Tim Brown.

In [Part II](#) I present research that I conducted with Dr. Alastair McLean. I acknowledge Alex Inayeh as being an equal contributor to the collection and interpretation of experimental STM data. The work described herein places an emphasis in areas where I made significant contributions to the understanding of NHC adsorption and self-assembly. This includes experimental and analysis efforts, which are a product of my own work.

The NHCs were synthesized by our collaborators in the Crudden group at Queen's University. First principles calculations were performed by our collaborators Felipe Crasto de Lima and Roberto Hiroki Miwa at the Federal University of Uberlândia. Both groups were also instrumental in developing our understanding of NHC binding and self-assembly.

Statement of originality

I hereby certify that the contents of this thesis are a product of my own work. All published or unpublished material from the works of others are fully acknowledged or referenced.

Ryan Groome

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Abbreviations

GLAD	Glancing angle deposition
PVD	Physical vapour deposition
QCM	Quartz crystal microbalance
MB	Maxwell-Boltzmann
MD	Molecular dynamics
TOF	Time-of-flight
PMF	Potential of mean force
HK	Hertz-Knudsen
MC	Monte-Carlo
HTEC	High temperature effusion cell
pBN	Pyrolytic boron nitride
UHV	Ultrahigh vacuum
rms	Root-mean-square
pdf	Probability density function
cdf	Cumulative distribution function
ESD	Electron stimulated desorption
RGA	Residual gas analyzer

ppm	Parts per million
HV	High vacuum
vdW	van der Waals
SAM	Self-assembled monolayer
SPR	Surface plasmon resonance
NHC	<i>N</i> -heterocyclic carbene
STM	Scanning tunnelling microscopy
LDOS	Local density of states
DFT	Density functional theory
NEXAFS	Near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure
HREELS	High-resolution electron energy loss spectroscopy
TPD	Temperature-programmed desorption
SPM	Scanning probe microscopy

Symbols

A partial list of commonly used symbols.

Velocity selection

$f(v), \tilde{f}(v)$ Speed and flux distributions

$\tau(v, \omega, \alpha)$ Admittance function

$T(\omega)$ Transmission function

v Particle speed

ω Spindle rotation speed

α Beam divergence angle

Velocity selector

N_c Number of helical channels

L Length

r_0 Mean distance from channel centre to rotation axis

ϕ Pitch angle

ψ Window aperture

τ_0 Fractional open area

Effusion

N Number of particles

P, V, T	Pressure, volume, and temperature
n, ρ	Density
m	Particle mass
Φ, Γ	Total flux and mass evaporation rate
A	Source area
$C_0(\phi, l/d)$	Clausing correction factor
Kn	Knudsen number
λ	Mean free path
d	Characteristic length of the flow domain

Detection

R	Deposition rate
i_c	Ion collector current
i_e	Electron emission current
s	Gauge sensitivity factor

Coordinates

ϕ	Polar or emission angle
β	Angle of incidence
θ	Azimuthal angle
r	Radial coordinate (e.g. source-to-detector distance)

Part I

Experimental speed distribution measurements in atomic beams generated by PVD

Chapter 1

Introduction

Current thin film fabrication technologies allow for precise nanostructural control. Virtually every property of a thin film, including the microstructure, surface morphology, and the mechanical, electrical, chemical, optical, and tribological properties, depends on the atomic growth process [1]. An advanced thin film fabrication technique is glancing angle deposition (GLAD), which combines physical vapour deposition (PVD) with controlled substrate motion to sculpt thin films with complex nanostructures [2]. Thin films fabricated by GLAD have a variety of optical applications (e.g. interference filters, selective polarization transmission filters) [3,4], and have also found applications in gas sensing [5,6], catalysis [7,8], and energy-related applications in energy storage [9,10] and solar energy conversion [11–13]. Several advanced methods for GLAD-based thin film engineering exist [14], including post-deposition treatments (e.g. annealing, etching) [15,16], substrate seeding [17], and tuning process parameters that influence growth, such as the substrate temperature [18]. Significant research efforts have been devoted to the development of advanced processes such as these, as they continue to offer improved control over the thin film nanostructure.

1.1 Motivation: Advanced nanostructural control

A thin film is a layer of material, ranging from a single atomic layer to several micrometres in thickness, that is deposited onto a substrate. Traditional PVD methods such as electron-beam evaporation and sputtering have been widely used in GLAD configurations to develop high-quality thin film materials [19]. The GLAD process manipulates the substrate tilt and rotation during deposition (see schematic in Figure 1.1a) to produce sculptured thin films with columnar nanostructures [14]. Columnar nanostructures, which form when the vapour flux arrives at oblique incidence angles due to atomic shadowing and limited adatom diffusion (Figure 1.1b), are sculpted by the substrate motion with controlled density and shape (e.g. tilted columns, zig-zag or helical structures, and so on) [19, 20]. Many factors influence the growth of these structures including shadowing between columns, the substrate material and temperature, the background gas pressure and composition, and the energy and angular distribution of the impinging vapour flux [21].

Figure 1.1: Schematics showing the GLAD geometry and columnar growth in a glancing configuration.

In many applications, the deposition rate and thin film thickness is determined *in situ* since (i) most thin film properties strongly depend on thickness and (ii) the deposition rate, determined by the energy and angular distribution of flux, is a significant factor that influences the thickness-uniformity and morphology of thin films [22–24]. A quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) placed in proximity to the film is a common growth characterization technique for thickness and deposition rate monitoring and control. A calibration factor based on *ex situ* accumulated thickness measurements generally relates the deposition rate at the sensor surface to that at the surface of the thin film [24]. This approach is limited, however, by its dependence on the impinging flux distribution. Even minor differences in a deposition process can result in film thickness errors and influence the properties of a film. To minimize thickness error, a related approach can be used that scans the QCM during deposition to characterize the angular distribution, and by integration the total flux, in real time [25, 26].

Thin film properties also depend on flux energetics. Film growth is strongly determined by the high impact energy of sputtered particles, for example [27–30]. Thermal evaporation produces vapour with low kinetic energies, on the order of 0.1 eV, and so the dependence can normally be neglected [31]. However, an effect called ‘steering’ [32–35] or sometimes the ‘surface trapping mechanism’ [36, 37] becomes important in glancing angle configurations. In contrast to ballistic deposition models for thin film growth, where particles travel along straight lines, interactions such as van der Waals interactions deflect the trajectory of a particle as it approaches the film surface (see Figure 1.1b). The deflection is most important when the velocity component perpendicular to the surface is small, for glancing angle impacts at low incident kinetic energies [32, 38]. Atomistic details provided by thin-film growth simulations

have shown that the steering effect modifies the shadowing process and affects the tilt angle of columnar nanostructures by the trapping of more particles on top of the growing columns [31,36,37]. Accordingly, it may be possible to develop thin films with further nanostructural control by tuning the impact velocity of thermally generated atomic vapour.

The present work aimed to examine the structure and physical properties of thin films condensed from velocity-selected atomic vapour, particularly in glancing angle configurations. Similar experiments have found differences in the annealing behaviour of films prepared with and without a velocity filter, studied by means of resistance measurements [39, 40]. Building on these works, we planned to investigate the effect of depositing velocity-selected vapour onto cryogenically cooled substrates by characterizing key properties dependent on thin film structure, including resistivity (upon annealing the films to high temperatures), surface roughness, optical reflectivity, and porosity. To vary the velocity of the impinging vapour flux, we designed a high-transmission helical velocity selector for use with common PVD techniques, such as electron-beam evaporation and resistive thermal evaporation. Critical to such experiments is an understanding of the flux energetics. Remarkably, however, very few experimental studies have reported on the velocity/energy distribution in atomic beams produced by thermal evaporation.

1.2 Thermal evaporation

The effusive oven, an isothermal enclosure equipped with a small hole (Figure 1.2a), is a simple and reliable source for thermal energy beams. Effusion provides a direct means to sample gas inside an oven and has been used by several investigators

to experimentally verify the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution [41–52]. The MB distribution, which is the basis for kinetic theory, describes the distribution of atomic/molecular velocities in a gas in thermal equilibrium [53]. Most experimental work has reported good agreement with theory for low-temperature gases that escape into vacuum, where the effects due to intrabeam and beam-gas scattering are small. A notable experiment was performed by Miller and Kusch in 1955 [48]. Using a helical velocity selector and surface ionization detector, they verified the MB distribution in potassium and thallium atomic beams to an accuracy of about 3%. By extension, it is generally assumed that the MB distribution also describes the velocity distribution of evaporated particles (Figure 1.2b), evaluated by assuming the vapour is an equilibrium gas at the temperature of the condensed (liquid or solid) phase [54–66].

Figure 1.2: (a) Effusion of a gas through a small hole or aperture. (b) Evaporation at the interface between a vapour and its condensed (liquid or solid) phase. A backwards vapour flux develops when interatomic collisions occur above the interface, leading to condensation and reflection processes.

Kinetic theory has provided the basis for understanding evaporation at the molecular level for more than one hundred years [67]. The widely used Hertz-Knudsen and Schrage relations for evaporation and condensation mass fluxes at the liquid-vapour interface are based on equilibrium analyses that rely on the MB distribution and neglect the effects due to collisions. The Boltzmann transport equation provides an

alternative approach for modelling transport phenomena (e.g. the evolution of the velocity distribution) when collisions are important [68–70]. Critical to these treatments are the assumed distribution functions for incident and outgoing particles at the interface [71]. In most cases, both the incoming and outgoing particle fluxes are modelled according to the MB distribution [72]. The boundary condition follows from the principle of detailed balance for a vapour in thermal equilibrium with its condensed phase, such that the fluxes balance with no net energy transfer [72]. Similar boundary conditions are constructed away from equilibrium on the basis that evaporated particles have a MB distribution governed entirely by the temperature of the condensed phase [55, 58, 73, 74]. While this may seem physically appropriate, a rigorous derivation for the expression is apparently lacking. This point has been addressed in many works [57, 62, 64, 75–77], leading to statements such as “no serious theoretical derivation of this boundary condition is known to us” [78].

Evaporation is a complex, dynamic process involving many interacting particles. To investigate evaporation phenomena at the atomic level, many works rely on computational approaches, including mean field kinetic theory [79, 80] and molecular dynamics (MD) [61, 62, 73, 78, 81–84]. These works have studied, for example, the evaporation mass flux, the evaporation/condensation coefficients, and the velocity distribution of the emitted particles. One of the more interesting results is that the velocity distribution function develops a temperature anisotropy and a drift velocity when collisions occur above the interface [61, 73, 80, 84]. Simulations have also been performed in the collisionless regime, to study the evaporation mechanism in isolation without condensation and reflection processes. In this regime, atoms kinetically depart from their condensed phase into vacuum without undergoing further collisions.

There are several known works in which the velocity distribution of evaporated particles is found to be approximately Maxwellian in the collisionless limit. Fischer *et al.* [82] and Fujikawa *et al.* [73] studied steady evaporation from planar liquid surfaces and found MB distributions for outgoing molecules at low temperature. Chandler *et al.* provided a detailed examination of the evaporation trajectories of water molecules escaping from the vapour-liquid interface [85]. In addition to the components of angular momentum, they found that the distribution of the velocity component normal to the surface was approximately Maxwellian. Based on their results, they suggested that a molecule near the surface only needs to spontaneously acquire sufficient energy to escape the vapour-liquid interface, consistent with the view that particles evaporate from the tail of the Maxwellian distribution from a deep, barrierless potential well.

Other studies have considered the need to include a binding energy for evaporating atoms [76, 78, 86], similar to why a binding energy term is included in the derivation of the energy distribution for sputtered atoms (generally approximated by the heat of sublimation or cohesive energy) [87, 88]. Gerasimov *et al.* assumed that for a particle to evaporate it must overcome a potential energy barrier, reducing its energy component normal to the surface [86]. Their description considered evaporation from a deep potential well, however many consider evaporation to be a stepwise process that leads to (nearly) free energetic barriers to evaporation. As described by Kacke and Stranski, the evaporation of an atom occurs through a series of thermally activated reconfigurations until it becomes loosely bound with a binding energy that is much lower than tightly bound bulk matter then, through stochastic interactions with adjacent atoms, it is ejected from the surface [54]. The stepwise mechanism is

unlike single-particle models, which assume evaporation occurs by the depletion of high-energy particles in the surface layer [78]. To provide atomic-scale insight into the evaporation mechanism, Anisimov *et al.* investigated non-equilibrium evaporation and condensation processes between two surfaces [76]. Using large-scale MD simulations, they demonstrated that interatomic collisions bring atoms right up to the edge of an interface, where they are released with a near-zero binding energy. In particular, the velocity distribution of evaporated atoms just beyond the interface was found to be nearly Maxwellian, with a small binding energy of about 0.3 meV.

Figure 1.3: Schematic of the liquid-vapour interface.

Weak long-range attractive interactions near the interface could offer a possible explanation for the occurrence of a small binding energy. Figure 1.3 shows an interface with loosely bound atoms, which may be ejected into the vapour phase via collisions with neighbouring atoms. As an atom escapes into the vapour phase, a mean force resulting from long-range interactions (e.g. van der Waals) attracts evaporated atoms back towards the condensed phase [89, 90]. The net force results from atom-surface interactions, which dominate due to the low number density in the vapour phase [78]. A distinction can also be drawn compared to a thermal gas that is sampled from an oven, where the net force would be closer to zero due to the large average separation

distance between particles.

The main limitation encountered in these simulations is the realistic treatment of the vapour-liquid interface, owing in part to the small system size (e.g. thousands of particles) and the critical dependence on the intermolecular interaction potential. Many studies use a truncated Lennard-Jones potential, which neglects many-body interactions and truncates long-range dispersion interactions using a cutoff function. It is well-known, however, that long-range many-body dispersion interactions play a crucial role in determining structure and bonding in molecular and condensed matter systems [91]. Including long-range dispersion contributions also has a major impact on the properties of interfaces, including surface tension and the interfacial width due to the increased cohesive force [92]. Several groups have emphasized that the detailed physical structure of the interface should affect the kinetic behaviour of evaporating particles, thereby affecting the velocity distribution of evaporated particles as well [57, 78, 79]. Although it remains unclear if or how such interactions affect the velocity distribution, there is some experimental evidence supporting the need for an energy barrier.

The mechanisms involved in the desorption of adsorbates have been extensively studied using laser-induced thermal desorption. Fukutani *et al.* studied Xe desorption from Au(001) for a wide range of initial surface coverages [93]. Using time-of-flight (TOF) techniques, they found that post-desorption collisions modify the velocity distribution except when the coverage is low, towards the collisionless limit where the data appear to be consistent with the MB distribution. On the other hand, non-Maxwellian distributions that contain a sharp onset (i.e. displaced towards lower energies) have been observed in many systems, even in the absence of collision effects.

Examples include the dissociative desorption of CH_3 radicals from CH_3I [94] and the non-reactive desorption of NO monomers from a cryogenically cooled ClNO film [95]. Using spectroscopic and TOF methods, Pfab *et al.* showed that NO monomers desorb with reduced kinetic energy and without a loss of rotational or electronic energy [95]. The reason for a non-Maxwellian distribution of translational kinetic energies was explained in terms of a small desorption barrier. By displacing the MB distribution, they determined the desorption barrier to be 27 ± 5 meV, which has the order of a van der Waals type bond. The need to consider an energy barrier was evident due to the use of low temperature, since the desorption energies of the NO monomers were comparable to the small, 27 meV displacement. These data provide important details on the mechanism of the desorption process that may translate to evaporation processes as well.

Several studies on the evaporation from liquid surfaces have reported departures from Maxwellian behaviour. Kisters *et al.* provided among the first experimental evidence for non-Maxwellian evaporation in their study of carboxylic acid dimers [96]. In a series of recent experiments, Nathanson *et al.* studied the evaporation of common gases dissolved in a variety of liquids, including hydrocarbons (e.g. dodecane), alcohols, and pure and salty water [97–99]. The liquid temperature for each experiment was chosen to maintain collision-free flow conditions. Using TOF methods, they found that He atoms evaporate with a super-Maxwellian velocity distribution, exceeding the expected flux-weighted average energy by as much as 70%. Similar behaviour was observed with Ne atoms, which also evaporated with super-Maxwellian kinetic energies [100]. In contrast, the evaporation of H_2 molecules showed sub-Maxwellian behaviour while the velocity distributions for heavier and more polarizable gases such

as Ar, N₂, O₂, CO₂, and H₂O were in good agreement with the expected MB distribution [98–100].

MD simulations of helium evaporation have successfully reproduced the super-Maxwellian behaviour [65, 66, 101]. The most comprehensive study was carried out by Kann and Skinner, who considered the evaporation of simple gases from water [65]. They found that the potential of mean force (PMF) in the interface region plays a key role in determining the velocity distribution of evaporated particles. It describes the force acting on a solute particle as it escapes from the interface, averaged over all possible solvent configurations. Provided equilibrium was maintained within the interfacial region, through frequent collisions and fast solvent reorganization, the speed distribution was approximately Maxwellian. However, due to the finite timescale for evaporation and the effectiveness and frequency of collisions, which are key factors in the equilibration process, the evaporation behaviour was generally non-Maxwellian. By varying the mass of the evaporating particle and the strength of the gas-surface interaction potential, they captured instances of both sub- and super-Maxwellian evaporation behaviour. In particular, super-Maxwellian behaviour was observed for heavy particles that weakly interact with the solvent whereas sub-Maxwellian behaviour was observed for light particles adsorbed in a deep potential well. In general, however, it remains unclear if or how the evaporation dynamics or the presence of an adsorption well affects the speed distribution in thermal atomic beams generated by PVD.

Traditional PVD methods offer an excellent platform for studying evaporation phenomena. Methods for thermal evaporation range from simple resistively heated elements, such as boats made of refractory metals that contain the evaporant, to

electron-beam heaters to laser ablation systems [102]. In principle, these methods can be used to study how fast atoms fly away from their condensed phase. An important technique for steady-state evaporation from liquid or solid surfaces is electron-beam heating, owing to its extensive use in thin film deposition. Numerous experimental studies have shown that the mean atomic velocity exceeds the value predicted by kinetic theory, which is considered to occur at high evaporation rates due to the presence of a collisional region just above the vapour source [103–106]. Depending on the evaporation conditions, a number of collisional processes may be important, including vapour-phase collisions and the excitation/ionization of evaporated atoms by electron impact [106]. The emission from laser-irradiated surfaces exhibits similar hyperthermal behaviour, which has been extensively modelled within the framework of Knudsen layer formation theory to capture the effect of vapour-phase collisions [63, 107–110]. Remarkably, thermal evaporation from liquid or solid surfaces by PVD has not been studied in detail in the collisionless limit, which is required to obtain information on the velocity distribution at the surface, as it relates to the evaporation mechanism. Not only are these measurements important for the technological development and theoretical modelling of thin films, they are also essential towards the basic understanding of evaporation.

1.3 Aim and scope

The primary aim of this thesis was to develop an experimental apparatus and procedure to accurately and precisely measure the speed distribution in atomic beams generated by an electron-beam-heated surface. We chose to focus on electron-beam

evaporation due to its widespread use in thin film deposition and because measurements of the complete speed distribution are mostly unavailable in literature [111].

Our secondary objectives were to:

1. measure the speed distribution of atoms emitted from an effusive oven,
2. compare measurements with those obtained using an open effusion cell or a resistive boat, and
3. investigate the structure and physical properties of thin film coatings condensed from velocity-selected vapours in glancing angle configurations.

We constructed and rigorously tested an apparatus to perform speed distribution measurements in PVD-generated atomic beams under high vacuum conditions. The apparatus relied on a mechanical velocity selector coupled with flux- and density-sensitive detectors. A mechanical velocity selector was chosen over spectroscopic techniques in order to be able to condense thin films from velocity-selected atomic vapour. That is, a mechanical velocity selection has the feature that it physically separates atoms or molecules based on speed. Speed distribution measurements were carried out by aligning the velocity selector between the source and detector. In this way information on the velocity distribution at the surface, as it relates to the evaporation mechanism, can be obtained provided the flow is collisionless. The chamber pressure, source-to-detector distance, velocity selector design, and detection methods were all major design considerations for achieving a suitable signal-to-noise ratio at low source temperatures, towards the collisionless limit when the vapour flux is low.

In this thesis I present details on the engineering design, construction, and testing of our speed distribution measurement apparatus. Underpinning these discussions

are basic principles and the theoretical framework needed to analyze and interpret experimental data for various sources and detection methods. We placed an initial emphasis on the effusion cell, which was used as a benchmark to verify our detection and analysis methods. Speed distribution measurements were also obtained using an open effusion cell and an electron-beam evaporator. In early 2018, however, after years of design and testing and just a few months of data collection, my workspace was converted into a nanophotonics lab, which put an abrupt end to my research. This impeded my plans to conduct (i) low-temperature experiments, (ii) experiments with new sources, such as a resistive thermal boat, and (iii) velocity-dependent deposition experiments. Without the ability to conduct experiments, I transferred fields to pursue another research interest, which I include in a stand-alone part.

1.4 Organization

This thesis is organized as follows. The next three chapters discuss the main processes involved in the determination of the speed distribution: (i) atomic beam formation, (ii) velocity selection, and (iii) detection. In [chapter 2](#) I establish the theoretical framework and the experimental methods, including instrumentation and design details, for the atomic beam sources used in this work. The focus of [chapter 3](#) is velocity selection, which addresses aspects of the engineering design and the framework used for theoretical and computational modelling. Detection methods are presented in [chapter 4](#), where I establish basic operating principles and highlight important design aspects and performance testing. The results and analysis of the speed distribution experiments are presented in [chapter 5](#) and [chapter 6](#) concludes and outlines future work.

Chapter 2

Deposition methods

This chapter provides the relevant background/technical information necessary for understanding experimental results presented in subsequent chapters. The experiments were carried out using either an effusive oven or an electron-beam evaporator. First, I consider the celebrated Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution within the framework of equilibrium statistical physics, before continuing with a general overview of these deposition techniques. Throughout, I also discuss the equipment and the methods that we used to carry out this research.

2.1 The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution

Consider a gas of N identical atoms of mass m that are contained in an isothermal enclosure of volume V at a sufficiently low density and high temperature. When the number density is sufficiently low, the de Broglie wavelength of an atom is much smaller than the average interatomic separation distance between nearest neighbour atoms. It follows, when the excluded volume is negligible in comparison to the size

of the container, that atoms may be treated classically as point particles with a well-defined position and momentum. At the same time, when the temperature, T , is sufficiently high, the mean free path λ that an atom travels between collisions is much smaller than the internal dimension of the container. With this condition, collisions occur mainly with other atoms in the gas phase rather than with the container walls [112].

Now suppose the system is initially prepared in a non-equilibrium state that is appreciably different from the MB distribution. The basic premise that atoms collide with one another in the gas phase, giving rise to energy partitioning and redistribution, is the (minimum) requirement needed for the system to evolve towards equilibrium – a unique stationary state that is unaffected by initial conditions [113, 114]. The smallest timescale over which equilibration can occur has the order of the collision time, defined as the average time a particle spends in free flight between collisions [114–116]. At equilibrium, it is overwhelmingly probable that any microstate chosen at random from the ensemble of possible microstates that satisfy the given macroscopic conditions will have a MB distribution [114]. The canonical ensemble can be applied to an ideal gas in thermal equilibrium with a heat bath to derive this distribution. It is a time- and position-independent probability density function that can be expressed in terms of particle speed v by integrating out the angular dependence,

$$f(v)dv = \frac{4v^2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{m}{2k_B T} \right)^{3/2} \exp\left(\frac{-mv^2}{2k_B T} \right) dv, \quad (2.1)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant [53]. This result is independent of the exact form of the interatomic interaction potential (assuming it depends only on the spatial positions of the atoms), provided collisions exist, and is valid at any location inside

the bulk of a gas, far from the walls of the enclosure [117].

The MB distribution forms the basis of the kinetic theory of gases and it is usually applied to the evaporation problem as well [54–60, 62–66]. In what follows, I review several interesting and important aspects of the different methods for thermal evaporation used in this work.

2.2 Physical vapour deposition: An introduction

Physical vapour deposition (PVD) describes a variety of techniques that deposit material in vacuum environments, either by evaporation, sputtering, or other non-chemical methods [118]. All PVD methods rely on kinetic energy transfer to atoms (or molecules) in their condensed, liquid or solid, state in order to bring about phase transitions to the vapour phase [102].

At low evaporation rates and typical chamber pressures (about 10^{-4} Pa or 10^{-6} Torr), evaporated atoms travel ballistically through the vacuum environment, with little to no interactions with other particles, until eventually they condense on a surface [2]. Keeping the evaporation rate low, as it relates to the number density of particles above the evaporating surface, reduces the possibility that atoms will collide with one another as they leave the surface. Similarly, maintaining a sufficiently low pressure ensures that the motion of each atom remains unchanged as it traverses the chamber, unimpeded by collisions with residual gases.

Evaporation is the simplest way to produce vapour [102]. In evaporation deposition, thermal energy is used to heat a material until vapour is released at an intended rate. Evaporation sources range from simple resistively heated elements (e.g. filaments or boats) made of refractory metals that contain the evaporant, to

sophisticated ovens and even electron-beam heaters and laser ablation systems. Conventionally, all of these sources are considered to be methods for thermal evaporation because the mechanism for evaporation can still be thermally driven even when energy is supplied to the evaporant from electrons or photons [102]. Heating the material until its vapour pressure exceeds about 10^{-1} Pa (or 10^{-3} Torr) can yield a reasonable deposition rate on a target surface depending on its position and orientation with respect to the source [2]. Although many materials reach their melting point and become liquid before producing vapour at an appreciable rate, some materials sublimate, meaning atoms transition to the vapour phase directly from the solid phase. We do not distinguish between the evaporation and sublimation of an evaporant since its vapour pressure, when plotted as a function of temperature, is a smooth and continuous curve.

Among the many methods used for depositing material in vacuum, this work relied on effusion and electron-beam evaporation to deposit high purity Ag into vacuum. The remainder of this chapter provides a detailed description of these deposition sources, including important theory and relevant operating principles.

2.3 Effusion

Effusion is a steady-state, rather than an equilibrium, process in which particles (atoms or molecules) escape from an enclosure through a small opening into an evacuated space. An effusion cell, or Knudsen cell, consists of an enclosure equipped with a small aperture/orifice that holds the condensed phase of a material. The material is heated to produce a suitable vapour pressure within the oven and “evaporation” occurs as effusion from the opening, which appears as the vapour source. The system

of particles inside the enclosure is maintained out of equilibrium, possibly in a steady state, since there is a net transport of macroscopic quantities such as mass, momentum, and energy into vacuum. Standard effusion models assume these particles follow an MB distribution when the source is operated under near-equilibrium conditions, even though it only strictly applies at equilibrium when there is no net evaporation flux [64]. Near-equilibrium conditions between the condensed phase and its saturated vapour can be achieved only through careful control of the experimental conditions. To provide a random sample of the gas inside the oven, an ideal effusion experiment relies on molecular flow conditions and the use of an ideal orifice. Given the practical importance of Knudsen cells in the formation of epitaxial films and nanostructures, a large number of both experimental and theoretical studies have investigated this process. In this section, I will describe the process of effusion and then focus on equipment details that are relevant for understanding subsequent chapters.

2.3.1 Molecular flow condition

Models governing effusion transport phenomena are only considered reliable in the molecular flow regime when gas particles rarely collide with one another as they exit the orifice. Historically, the type of flow regime is determined by the Knudsen number, Kn , which is a dimensionless number that quantifies the degree of gas rarefaction [112]. Interpreted physically as the ratio of particle-wall to particle-particle collisions in the orifice, it is defined by the ratio

$$\text{Kn} = \frac{\lambda}{d}, \quad (2.2)$$

where d is the characteristic length of the flow domain, in this case the orifice diameter, and λ is the mean free path, or the average distance a particle travels between

collisions inside the oven [119]. For atoms in a Maxwellian gas, λ is

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}n\sigma}, \quad (2.3)$$

where σ is the effective collision cross section and n is the gas density, which can be expressed in terms of pressure and temperature using the ideal gas law [120]. While there is no abrupt boundary marking the transition between different types of flow, three idealized flow regimes are summarized in Table 2.1. These are the regimes of molecular, transition, and continuum flow, which are quantitatively distinguished depending on the value of Kn [121].

Molecular flow	$\text{Kn} > 1$
Transition flow	$1 > \text{Kn} > 0.01$
Continuum flow	$\text{Kn} < 0.01$

Table 2.1: Flow regimes classified by Knudsen number.

Several investigators have measured the speed distribution in atomic/molecular beams effusing from Knudsen cells in order to experimentally demonstrate that a gas in thermal equilibrium inside an isothermal enclosure obeys Maxwellian statistics. While gas-phase collisions in the vicinity of the orifice can cause departures from the MB distribution [46], studies performed using a ‘near-ideal’ orifice have reported results in excellent agreement with theory when $\lambda > d$ [48–51]. Here, the temperature range explored for Ag spanned about 1450 K to 1725 K, constrained either by a detection limit or the temperature limit of the source. We note that the condition $\lambda = d$ occurs within this range at ~ 1500 K. To evaluate λ , we assumed the effective particle diameter of Ag was 2.85 Å and estimated its saturation vapour pressure

from equilibrium pressure data reported in the CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics [122].

2.3.2 Ideal effusion cells

The classic model for effusion assumes particles of an equilibrium gas pass through an ‘ideal orifice’ from an inert, isothermal enclosure [123, 124]. The ideal orifice is a hypothetical hole that is infinitesimally thin, having an area that is very small in comparison to the extent of the evaporating surface. For such a geometry, the loss of effusing particles is not expected to appreciably disturb the equilibrium between the condensed phase and its saturated vapour within the cell [125]. Tantamount to a hole that is closed, the vapour is regarded as an equilibrium gas at the temperature of the condensed phase [125]. A corollary, as discussed in [section 2.1](#), is that the velocity distribution for particles in the bulk of the gas, away from the walls of the enclosure, follows the three-dimensional isotropic MB distribution [126]. The differential particle flux arriving at the orifice, defined to be the number of particles striking a surface element of unit area per unit time with velocities in the interval \mathbf{v} and $\mathbf{v} + d^3\mathbf{v}$, is evaluated from this distribution according to

$$d\Phi(\mathbf{v}) = \frac{n}{4\pi} v f(v) dv \cos(\phi) \sin(\phi) d\theta d\phi, \quad (2.4)$$

where $f(v)$ is given by [Equation 2.1](#), a function of the speed $v = |\mathbf{v}|$, and $n = N/V$ is the number density of the gas [125, 127]. This expression is conveniently expressed using the spherical coordinates (v, θ, ϕ) , where θ is the azimuthal angle that varies from 0 to 2π and ϕ is the polar angle that ranges from 0 to $\pi/2$, since the velocity distribution function is independent of the direction of \mathbf{v} for an isotropic system.

Collisions with the walls of an ideal orifice may be ignored due to its infinitesimal length. On the other hand, gas-phase collisions among particles in the vicinity of the orifice are only rare if the transport mechanism is governed by Knudsen flow. When such collisions are neglected, the differential particle flux emerging from the cell into vacuum is given by Equation 2.4, evident since particles which arrive at the hole pass it freely, without undergoing any collisional events [120]. A notable result, obtained by integrating this expression over the limiting range of particle speeds, is that the angular distribution for particles leaving the cell is governed by the cosine distribution [123, 128]. For such an angular dependence, the ratio of the flux leaving the orifice at an angle ϕ , measured from the surface normal, to the centreline intensity is directly proportional $\cos(\phi)$. If, instead, the angular dependence is integrated out over the half-space outside the cell, Equation 2.4 becomes

$$d\Phi(\mathbf{v}) = \frac{n}{4} v f(v) dv, \quad (2.5)$$

which describes the rate per unit area that particles with speeds between v and $v + dv$ effuse through the hole. Further integration yields the total flux of effusing particles,

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{A} \frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{1}{4} n \langle v \rangle = \frac{P}{\sqrt{2\pi m k_B T}}, \quad (2.6)$$

which is expressed in a familiar form by relating the gas density n inside the container to the pressure P using the ideal gas law and by evaluating the mean speed $\langle v \rangle$ from the first moment of the MB distribution [128]. This is the well-known Hertz-Knudsen

(HK) relation, which is related to the mass evaporation rate according to

$$\Gamma = mA\Phi = P\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi k_B T}}A, \quad (2.7)$$

where the area A is determined by the dimension of the orifice.

A detector located outside the enclosure can be used to sample the gas that effuses into vacuum. To measure the speed distribution given by [Equation 2.1](#) under steady state conditions, particles must be detected within a fixed spatial interval at a fixed measurement time [\[129\]](#). In contrast to density-sensitive detection, it is readily seen from [Equation 2.5](#) or [Equation 2.6](#) that flux measurements contain information on both number density and particle speed. In Otto Stern's early work, he forgot the extra factor of v arising from the transformation of a speed distribution to a flux distribution [\[41\]](#) – a mistake that was identified in a letter he received from Albert Einstein [\[130, 131\]](#). The speed distribution for particle flux has a probability density function of the form

$$\tilde{f}(v)dv = 2v^3 \left(\frac{m}{2k_B T}\right)^2 \exp\left(\frac{-mv^2}{2k_B T}\right) dv, \quad (2.8)$$

which is obtained by normalizing [Equation 2.5](#). This function determines the fraction of particles, with speeds within the infinitesimal interval v and $v + dv$, that emerge from the orifice per unit time. Since normalization eliminates the dependence on gas density, it also applies to particles crossing an arbitrary plane once steady state has been reached, making it the distribution of interest for experiments that rely on rate-sensitive detection [\[56\]](#).

From a statistical perspective, the intensity of the atomic/molecular beam emerging from the source may be chosen to yield a large signal-to-noise ratio. Increasing the beam intensity can be achieved simply, either by raising the oven temperature or by expanding the size of the orifice. At the same time, the intensity is limited by the required flow regime since it too is governed by these parameters.

2.3.3 Clausing's model and Monte-Carlo methods

In practice, the orifice of a real effusion cell has a finite length and correction factors can be introduced to account for departures from the ideal model [123, 128]. Clausing was the first investigator to adequately model highly rarefied gas flows in cylindrical channels [132]. He considered the limiting case of a free molecular flow, where interparticle collisions are absent. In this extreme, the flux that emerges from a finite orifice consists of (i) particles from the oven that pass directly through the orifice without collision and (ii) particles that undergo one or more wall collisions while passing through the orifice.

A difficulty associated with the study of effusion transport phenomena arises from the need to model gas-surface interactions. Clausing's treatment not only assumes that the flux at entrance of the channel has a cosine angular distribution, but that the walls of the channel re-emit incident particles according to a cosine angular distribution as well [132]. The cosine emission model, analogous to Lambert's emission law in optics, was first introduced to kinetic theory by Knudsen, who considered it as the most reasonable assumption for characterizing the spatial distribution of emission from molecularly rough surfaces under conditions of extreme rarefaction [133]. As emphasized by Gaede, Clausing, and later by Comsa, cosine-distributed (i.e. diffuse)

emission from surfaces inside an enclosure is consistent with an ensemble of particles that have an isotropic angular distribution in the volume at equilibrium [134]. In the absence of equilibrium, Knudsen's empirical 'law' has been applied to atoms and molecules that either desorb, evaporate, or scatter from surfaces [135]. The basic implementation of the boundary condition considers a non-absorbing and non-reacting surface that thermally accommodates incident particles, which are re-emitted diffusely with Maxwellian-distributed speeds defined by the wall temperature [136]. When a particle is re-emitted by such a surface, it travels in a direction that is independent of its angle of incidence, with the same chance of moving forwards or backwards through the channel.

Assuming diffuse re-emission from the wall surfaces, Clausing showed that the number of particles transmitted through a cylindrical aperture of length l and diameter d per unit time per unit area at an angle ϕ , measured from the surface normal direction, into the solid angle $\sin(\phi)d\theta d\phi$ is

$$\frac{1}{A} \frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{n\langle v \rangle}{4\pi} C_0(\phi, l/d) \cos(\phi) \sin(\phi) d\theta d\phi, \quad (2.9)$$

where $A = \pi d^2/4$ [132]. Except for the correction factor $C_0(\phi, l/d)$, this expression is equivalent to Equation 2.4 once the dependence on particle speed is integrated out. It depends only on the emission angle ϕ and the ratio l/d and is defined in terms of

$$\alpha = \frac{\sqrt{l^2 + d^2} - l}{d + d^2/\sqrt{l^2 + d^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad p = \frac{l}{d} \tan(\phi) \quad (2.10)$$

to be (e.g. see [123, 132])

$$C_0(\phi, l/d) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{2}{\pi}(1 - \alpha) (\arcsin(p) + p(1 - p^2)^{1/2}) \\ \quad + \frac{4}{3\pi p}(1 - 2\alpha) (1 - (1 - p^2)^{3/2}) & \text{if } p < 1, \\ \alpha + \frac{4(1 - 2\alpha)}{3\pi p} & \text{if } p \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

In connection with subsequent chapters, we first make use of this result to derive the rate at which particles arrive onto a differential area element dA_s . If the receiving surface is oriented such that the incident flux arrives at an angle β , the solid angle subtended by dA_s is $d\Omega = \cos(\beta)dA_s/r^2$, where \mathbf{r} defines the vector joining the source to the element, $r \equiv |\mathbf{r}|$, and β is the incidence/deposition angle defined by the angle between \mathbf{r} and the surface normal of dA_s . From Equation 2.9, the local incident flux of particles per unit area of the receiving surface, $dA_s = r^2 \sin(\phi)d\theta d\phi / \cos(\beta)$, is

$$\frac{1}{A} \frac{dN}{dt dA_s} = \frac{n\langle v \rangle \cos(\phi) \cos(\beta)}{4\pi r^2} C_0(\phi, l/d), \quad (2.12)$$

which can be multiplied through by mA/ρ to obtain the deposition rate,

$$R = \frac{\Gamma \cos(\phi) \cos(\beta)}{\pi r^2 \rho} C_0(\phi, l/d), \quad (2.13)$$

where ρ is the density of the deposited film and ϕ and β correspond to the emission angle and the angle of incidence, respectively.

We also modelled Knudsen effusion through a cylindrical channel using Monte-Carlo (MC) methods to correctly identify the thermodynamic system measured by

a detector outside the enclosure (i.e. surface emissions versus particles from the gas-phase inside the oven). In simulating free molecular flow, we assumed that the particles move in straight lines and only change directions by colliding with an interior wall. A simulation initialized a single particle at a time, an approach amenable to parallel processing, since the trajectories of individual particles are independent from each other. In the initialization process, a particle was assigned a random position at the entrance of the channel and then propagated along a direction sampled from the cosine distribution (see [section 3.4](#) for more details). Without considering sorption or surface diffusion, every particle that collided with a wall was re-emitted in a direction sampled according to the cosine law, which peaks along the surface normal and is independent of the particle's angle of incidence. With this procedure, a simulation counted the number of particles exiting the channel and grouped them based on the occurrence of wall collisions. A potential advantage of using the MC method, in comparison to the analytic solutions derived by Clausing, is the flexible approach it offers to study the effects of different gas-surface interaction models.

Simulated transmission probabilities are plotted as a function of l/d and compared with the Clausing model in [Figure 2.1a](#). In keeping with [Equation 2.6](#), the total flux per unit area emerging from a non-ideal orifice is $\Phi = Wn\langle v \rangle / 4$, where W is the so-called Clausing transmission factor that is retrieved from [Equation 2.9](#) by integrating out the angular dependence,

$$W = 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} C_0(\phi, l/d) \cos(\phi) \sin(\phi) d\phi. \quad (2.14)$$

This factor is evaluated numerically and shown to agree well with the transmission factor obtained by simulation for all l/d (plotted in black and green, respectively).

Figure 2.1: (a) The fraction of particles transmitted through a cylindrical channel as a function of l/d . For each channel geometry, a simulation was run until 10^5 particles escaped. (b) The angular distribution of the flux emitted from a cylindrical channel with $l/d = 0.67$ is compared to the cosine law for an ideal orifice. Simulations for each angular distribution were run until 10^7 particles escaped.

The MC method also allows us to separate contributions to the transmission factor arising from particles that pass through the channel with and without wall collisions (plotted in orange and blue, respectively). While particles that pass freely through the orifice, without undergoing any wall collisions, dominate at small l/d , the number of escapes becomes dominated by particles that have undergone wall collisions at large l/d . Incidentally, the l/d ratio for the orifice used in this work corresponds to the point when the probability of escape with or without wall collisions is nearly equal. We estimate about 47% of particles escape into vacuum without undergoing a collision with a wall when $l/d = 0.67$. We recorded the number of wall collisions per escape for this geometry and found this number is close to unity, which agrees with the approximate analytical treatment [137]. Similar results have also been reported in recent work by Copland and others [138].

Figure 2.1b compares the angular distribution of flux for $l/d = 0.67$ with the cosine emission law, as it applies for infinitesimally thin channels (solid red and green curves,

respectively). Simulated results are determined by sorting the polar angle of each escape into equally spaced 1° bins weighted per unit solid angle and then normalizing to the highest bin count (marked with circles every 6°). Excellent agreement between theory and simulation is obtained for both cases, highlighting the expected beam-collimating effect for non-ideal orifices.

Finally, we consider the flux arriving at a detector. Our work decouples contributions to the overall angular distribution by separately recording the polar angle of particles that escape with or without wall collisions. With reference to the simulation results shown in [Figure 2.1b](#) for $l/d = 0.67$, we demonstrate that the form of the distribution is notably different for particles that arrive directly from the gas phase inside the oven versus those that arrive from a surface inside the channel (plotted in blue and orange, respectively). Upon initialization, particles enter the channel with directions distributed according to the cosine law and those that satisfy the geometrical constraint imposed by the shape of the channel escape without any wall collisions. By comparison, the angular distribution is broader for particles that undergo wall collisions due to diffuse re-emission downstream from the channel entrance. The angular distribution also exhibits a preference towards forward peaking as l/d increases (trend not shown), though it necessarily tends to zero along the beam centreline since no particles are emitted in the surface plane when directions are sampled according to the cosine law. To calculate a transmission probability for each distribution, we separately integrate them according to [Equation 2.14](#) within a given interval. As an example, we estimate approximately 98% of all particles emitted with polar angles within 5° have not undergone a collision with a wall. This result leads to an interesting conclusion in the case that gas-phase collisions occur inside the oven (e.g.

when the oven is sufficiently large). Even though over half of all escapes undergo at least one wall collision, a detector placed far away from the orifice along its centreline primarily samples particles emitted directly from the gas phase inside the oven.

2.3.4 Extensions to Clausing's orifice treatment

A focus of Knudsen effusion studies has been to determine the angular number distribution of flux that emerges from non-ideal orifices in order to test the validity of the Clausing model. Most experiments have identified departures from the Clausing distribution, even under conditions when it is expected to apply [139–144]. At best, the model offers a semi-quantitative description of experimental data in the molecular flow regime when gas-phase collisions in the channel are considered negligible [145]. To address its shortcoming, many studies have considered the possibility of more complex gas-surface interaction phenomena.

A surface-diffusion contribution to the flux emitted from the effusion cell has been considered to explain departures from the Clausing model. Instead of immediate re-emission, the surface diffusion theory developed by Winterbottom and Hirth assumes atomic or molecular adsorbates migrate along the surface before being re-emitted [146, 147]. With this kind of vapour-surface interaction, they showed that a net surface-diffusion flux resulting from a concentration gradient in the population of particles adsorbed on the heated walls of the orifice can contribute to the total flow from the cell. The geometry-dependent surface-transport effects are closely related to an adsorbate population that develops on the outer surface of the effusion cell lid where evaporation occurs from a free surface. Particularly for short and near-ideal orifices, their treatment predicts enhanced emission and an altered angular distribution that is

less directed than the Clausing distribution, tending towards the cosine distribution.

A departure from the diffuse reflection gas-surface interaction model has also been considered to explain the observed angular distribution data. Conditions such as high incident energies, low (glancing) incidence angles, shallow potential wells, and high surface temperatures can promote scattering towards the specular direction [148]. Traditional gas-surface interaction models take into account the incomplete accommodation, instead of fully diffuse interactions with complete thermal accommodation. For example, the Maxwell model is the simplest boundary condition, constructed assuming complementary fractions of diffuse re-emission and specular reflection from the surface [149].

The specular reflection of molecules from the heated walls of an effusion orifice has been extensively studied in connection with angular and speed distribution measurements. During their effusion experiments, Wang and Wahlbeck measured non-Clausing angular distributions that were larger than prediction in the near-forward direction, both for short and for long cylindrical orifices [143]. They explained the data qualitatively by assuming that low-angle specular (or lobular) reflection occurred during the gas-surface interactions. To explore this effect, they also measured the velocity distribution under similar conditions [50]. Whereas near-ideal orifice data demonstrated good agreement with theory, they found that the non-ideal orifice data showed effusion-angle-dependent deviations from the theoretical Maxwellian distribution that were most notable near the centre line. Having identified gas-phase collisions and surface diffusion as unlikely causes for the observed angular and velocity distributions, they attributed the departures to specular reflection. By including this interaction process, they justified that an excess of high-speed molecules in the

near-forward direction can occur if the reflection occurs more readily at high incident energies and glancing incidence angles.

Departures from predicted behaviour have also been reported for a near-ideal orifice under conditions of extreme rarefaction. Particles emerging from the orifice come directly from the sample surface or from a wall inside the cell when the mean free path is large in comparison to the interior dimensions of the enclosure. Ward *et al.* performed experiments in this regime and found angular distributions that disagreed with the expected cosine law of effusion [144]. They likened their measurements to the image from a pinhole camera, with the beam mirroring information on the interior of the effusion cell. The results of a subsequent Monte-Carlo analysis reproduced the experimental data by assuming loss (e.g. due to adsorption or surface reactions) occurred on the different surfaces inside the cell [150]. This comparison highlights that without the randomization effect of gas-phase collisions, diffuse surface emissions are not sufficiently random to establish the predicted cosine-law angular distribution if surface losses occur inside the oven.

2.3.5 High temperature effusion cell

We conducted benchmark experiments necessary for model validation using a high temperature effusion cell (HTEC) that was purchased from SVT Associates. The cell consisted of a 10 cm³ tapered pyrolytic boron nitride (pBN) crucible with a 10.0° opening angle. Evaporant material was loaded in the crucible, referred to as the ‘charge’, and a 1.02 ± 0.05 mm thick cap with a 1.52 ± 0.05 mm diameter orifice was positioned above the charge and secured using a spring-tension ring. The use of a conical crucible with a pointed bottom directed and aligned the melt pool along

the centreline [144]. With regard to the crucible material, we used pBN because it has a high temperature rating and because its chemical inertness and non-wetting characteristics help prevent surface losses and liquid from creeping up the cell walls, respectively [123, 151].

The crucible is secured to a heater assembly that is surrounded by a set of coaxially separated refractory metal heat shields. The electric resistance heater uses two filaments connected in parallel to heat both the crucible and a type C thermocouple positioned at the base of the crucible. Power to the heater is supplied using a 55 V, 13 A power supply and the temperature of the cell is regulated using a PID controller that uses the temperature reading from a thermocouple mounted near the base of the crucible as the process value. It is experimentally difficult to measure the source temperature directly, however SVT reports that the temperature inside the cell is approximately uniform along its axis until the top ~ 19 mm of the cell. The aperture is positioned below this point and the thermocouple is located near the base of the crucible to provide an accurate estimate of the source temperature. The assembly also has (i) a pneumatic shutter positioned above the crucible to interrupt the flow of atoms into the chamber and (ii) a water-cooling shroud to reduce outgassing during operation. Finally, we note that detectors sample the beam within the elongated walls of the crucible (i.e. within 5°) during experimentation.

2.4 Electron-beam evaporation

In addition to effusion experiments, we also measured the speed distribution in Ag atomic beams produced by electron-beam heating, a widely-used PVD method for growing thin film materials. This section provides a description of the equipment

and methods we used in this work. Other considerations, such as the effect of near-surface collisions, are also discussed as they relate to experimental data presented in subsequent chapters.

2.4.1 Bent-beam electron gun

We used a commercially available 3kW rod-fed bent-beam electron gun from Thermionics. With reference to [Figure 2.2a](#), electrons that are thermionically emitted from a heated tungsten filament are accelerated in 10kV potential. The electron beam is then bent by about 270 degrees using a permanent magnet that directs it onto the evaporant surface. Energy transfer due to collisional and, to a lesser extent, radiative losses locally heats the rod-shaped evaporant, which protrudes a small distance through a water-cooled crucible, or hearth. The accelerating voltage is controlled using a high voltage power supply that outputs 0 to -10 kV DC (regulated to $\pm 0.5\%$) to a filament transformer, which has two high-voltage outputs that are electrically connected to the filament in vacuum. The emission current is set using a source controller and kept constant using a closed loop feedback system that varies the potential difference between the high-voltage inputs to the filament. While evaporating material, a stepper motor advances the source and a pneumatic shutter can be positioned above the source material to interrupt vapour flow.

2.4.2 Temperature estimation

Deposition rate measurements can provide useful information on the temperature of a heated surface. Drawing on the work presented in [subsection 2.3.3](#), the angular distribution of particles ejected from a ‘real’ small surface may be influenced by

Figure 2.2: (a) Electron-beam evaporation system. (b) Vapour-emitting surface at low and high rates of evaporation.

collisions or by a convex emitting surface due to the surface tension of the evaporant. This is normally taken into account by replacing Knudsen’s cosine law with a higher-order cosine function [122, 152]. Following this approach, the deposition rate, R , on a substrate separated by a distance r can be expressed in terms of an empirically determined rate-dependent beaming exponent, n . When R is calculated as a deposited film thickness per unit time, it is related to the mass evaporation rate, Γ , according to

$$R = \frac{(n + 1) \cos^n(\phi) \cos(\beta)}{2\pi r^2 \rho} \Gamma, \tag{2.15}$$

where n determines the anisotropy of the evaporant flux, ρ is the density of the deposited film, and ϕ and β correspond to the emission angle and the angle of incidence, respectively [128, 153]. The temperature dependence is recovered from the kinetic treatment for Γ (Equation 2.7). Shibata *et al.* showed that this method yields accurate temperature estimates at low to moderate rates of evaporation based on

mutual agreement with spectral radiance profile measurements [153].

2.4.3 Near-surface effects

While the details of high-rate electron-beam evaporation are complicated, the general physical principles are well known. Near-surface collisions (see Figure 2.2b) and other flow phenomena, such as acceleration due to vapour excitation/ionization processes, can obscure the initial velocity distribution of an evaporating surface [59, 63, 93, 104, 106, 108, 154–158]. Knudsen layer formation theory offers a kinetic approach to study the evaporation problem. A Knudsen layer can form for as few as three collisions per particle and extend a few mean free paths from the surface [59, 93, 156]. In the layer, a half-range Maxwellian distribution at the surface evolves to a full-range Maxwellian distribution with a center-of-mass (flow) velocity u_k [93, 156]. The flux distribution at the layer boundary goes as

$$f(v)dv \propto v^3 \exp\left(\frac{-m(v - u_k)^2}{2k_B T_k}\right) dv \quad (2.16)$$

for the emission from a steady thermal source, where T_k is the (translational) temperature of the flow [59].

The translational temperature and the flow velocity arise as a consequence of near-surface collisions, which convert thermal energy to translational kinetic energy along the surface normal direction [103–105, 108, 159]. For an ideal monoatomic gas, the ratio of T_k to the surface temperature T_s , determined at the boundary by Knudsen-layer formation theory, is $T_k/T_s = 0.65$ [59]. Various treatments of the Knudsen-layer

problem have also shown that the Mach number,

$$M = u_k \sqrt{\frac{m}{\gamma k_B T_k}}, \quad (2.17)$$

is close to unity at the boundary, where m is the particle mass, γ is the heat capacity ratio (5/3 for an ideal monoatomic gas), and k_B is Boltzmann's constant [59, 93]. This relation provides a useful check on the reliability of the values for u_k and T_k determined in subsequent analysis.

The flow beyond the boundary undergoes adiabatic expansion if still further collisions occur, which leads to a similar distribution function but with different values for u_k and T_k [59]. At lower number densities, the collision frequency may be sufficiently high to affect the particle distribution, such that collision-free flow conditions do not apply, but still too low for the flow to equilibrate in a Knudsen layer. Sibold and Urbassek have shown that the flux distribution is significantly modified if escaping particles undergo as few as one collision on average [157]. Although an analytical solution is not available, the flow, which is neither molecular nor in thermodynamic equilibrium, is commonly approximated with a shifted Maxwellian given by [Equation 2.16](#).

The velocity distribution of atoms that emerge from the collisional regime can also be modified due to the complicated exchange between internal (electronic) and translational degrees of freedom [160]. The atomic vapour usually contains a small fraction of atoms in electronically excited states that can decay by both radiative and non-radiative processes. In thermal equilibrium, excited state populations determined by the Boltzmann distribution are often negligible except at very high temperature, such is the case for Ag owing to the 3.7 eV excitation energy to the first excited state [161].

However, the excitation of atoms is not purely thermal, but rather driven by electron impact excitation due to inelastic collisions with electrons¹. Compared to primary or thermal electrons, ‘hot’ electrons ($>5\text{ eV}$) generally have a higher collision rate with neutral vapour, as determined by the cross sections for electron impact excitation or ionization [162]. When the number density of atoms above the evaporating surface is high, excited atoms can relax due to a collision with another particle before spontaneous emission and convert the excitation energy into kinetic energy. The effect of excitation and ionization has been considered by several research groups to explain why the mean speed of atomic beams during high-rate electron-beam evaporation is larger than the predicted value [103–106].

2.4.4 Ion extraction

We made an attempt to extract the weakly ionized plasma (generally less than 1% ionization [162, 163]) from the beam of neutral atoms using a custom ion trap that is shown in Figure 2.3a. We designed this instrument because charged particles produced during the electron-beam heating process obscure ionization gauge measurements. In particular, we noticed that opening and closing the source shutter changed the collector current by an amount that varied with deposition rate, even when the gauge was turned off. Our goal was to recover the intact signal by applying a bias to

¹There are several different groups of electrons that belong to different energy ranges. These are primary beam and backscattered electrons, thermal electrons generated by thermionic emission from the heated surface and thermal ionization, and hot electrons, which include secondary electrons and electrons generated by impact ionization events involving primary and secondary electrons [162, 163]. True secondary electrons decelerate in the material due to multiple inelastic scattering interactions with bound electrons before re-emerging from the surface. Secondary electrons also include electrons emitted due to electron avalanche, Auger electrons, and photoelectrons emitted due to the adsorption of Bremsstrahlung [163].

the plasma removal electrode. The core component of the design consisted of a negatively charged cylindrical electrode located just above the evaporant that attracted and captured positively charged ions and repelled negative charges. The electrode had a primary hollow cylinder that was axially aligned along the beam path. It was also equipped with a second tube that was tilted at a 7.5° angle. This geometry was used because our measurement convention relied on an off-axis detector placed within line-of-sight of the source.

(a) Ion extractor

(b) Ion extraction experiment

Figure 2.3: (a) Photograph of the ion extractor assembly. (b) Extraction current plotted as a function of electrode potential during electron-beam evaporation (7.5 kV accelerating voltage, 273 mA emission current). These results are not corrected for differences in deposition rate, which was measured by a quartz crystal monitor close to the surface to decrease throughout the experiment.

We measured the extraction current as a function of the removal electrode potential (0 to -100 V) while evaporating silver in vacuum. The experimental results shown in [Figure 2.3b](#) rise steeply and plateau at high voltage, which suggests that ions, produced by electron-impact and thermal ionization processes, are extracted from the plasma onto the negatively charged electrode. These results are representative of several trials and are consistent with those obtained by other research groups [[164](#), [165](#)]. Considering the transmission probability is not necessarily zero for energetic ions passing through the velocity selector depending on its design, the ion

extraction system presented offers the ability to obtain the speed distribution of only neutral vapour.

Nevertheless, even when operated at a positive bias or when used in combination with heavy shielding around the detector, the design was not able to eliminate the effect that charged particles have on ionization gauge measurements. This finding holds for both on-axis and off-axis detector positions. Considering about 40% of 10 keV electrons normally incident on Ag scatter into the backward hemisphere [166], the gauge is most likely affected by high-energy electrons. We introduced shielding to prevent electrons from scattering from the vacuum chamber walls into the detection region, but it is possible they still arrived along the beam axis. Without a much more controlled experimental investigation, we decided to acquire transmission spectra using only quartz crystal monitors for electron-beam evaporation experiments.

Chapter 3

Velocity selection

Several different techniques have been used to measure the energy/velocity distribution of neutral particles in atomic and molecular beam experiments, such as (i) fluorescence techniques, (ii) time-of-flight measurements, and (iii) via mechanical velocity selection [129, 167]. Laser-induced fluorescence relies on the resonant absorption of laser light to produce electronically excited states that subsequently decay to lower levels by spontaneous emission. Since the excitation wavelength is Doppler-shifted for particles that have a non-zero velocity component in the direction of the laser beam, the fluorescence signal can be related to the velocity distribution when the laser is tuned over a suitable range [111, 168]. In contrast, time-of-flight methods chop the beam into single bunches of particles that spread out in transit to a detector. Provided successive bunches do not appreciably overlap before detection, the distribution of arrival times is related to the velocity distribution [129]. Unlike both of these techniques, mechanical velocity selectors physically separate neutral particles with a chosen velocity from a beam that may have a broad velocity spectrum, such as a Maxwellian distribution. This feature is essential for the growth of thin films

condensed from velocity-selected atomic vapour.

3.1 Introduction

Among the first to test the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution was Stern in 1920 [41, 131], then Eldridge in 1927 [42], and then Zartman in 1931 [43]. These early experiments relied on slotted disks mounted on a rotating shaft to selectively transmit atoms within a narrow range of speeds. The prototypes for slotted disk velocity selectors have since been improved upon, now achieving a high degree of accuracy and precision. Today, the slotted disk velocity selector and the slotted cylinder velocity selector are two common designs capable of selectively filtering the speeds of atomic/molecular and even neutron beams.

Slotted disk velocity selectors are made up of two or more thin slotted disks that are axially aligned about their rotation axis. The teeth between the slots of the disks define a helical path, parametrized by the orientation and separation distance of the disks. By varying the rotation speed, only particles traveling within a targeted range of speeds can be transmitted (e.g. see the work of [169–173]). These velocity selectors are lightweight and have a low moment of inertia in comparison to slotted cylinder velocity selectors, which facilitates their acceleration to high rotation speeds. The disks are also easy to machine, with the added benefit that particles are deposited on the face of the disk rather than the walls of the grooves, thereby preventing the accumulation of unwanted material.

The slotted cylinder velocity selector, first implemented by Levinstein and Crane in 1946 [174], has a large number of helical grooves along the outer surface of a metal cylinder. This type of instrument, shown schematically in [Figure 3.1](#), has been widely

implemented to selectively transmit atoms and molecules [48, 174, 175] as well as neutrons [176–179] within a narrow range of speeds. Although these devices require considerable effort to construct, they are often favourable to slotted disk velocity selectors because they consist of a single part. This feature, for example, bypasses alignment challenges and yields transmission spectra that are free from ‘sidebands’. Velocity sidebands is a common problem for slotted disk type velocity selectors [169], referring to particles that are transmitted through a series of slots other than the helical paths defined by the teeth of the rotating disks [180, 181].

Figure 3.1: Slotted cylinder velocity selector containing a single helical channel.

For atomic beam experiments, the slotted cylinder velocity selector is only suitable for use with condensable vapours. It is characterized using a transmission function,

$T(\omega)$, that evaluates the fraction of atoms transmitted at a particular rotation speed, ω . In principle, only atoms within a fixed range of speeds can enter a channel, travel along its path, and escape without undergoing a collision with the sidewall of a groove. It is usually assumed that any atom that strikes a wall condenses and, as a result, is removed from the beam. This assumption is motivated by several experimental and theoretical studies that have shown the sticking probability for metal atoms impinging on a metal surface is unity for thermal energies, regardless of impact angle, and that the likelihood for reflection only becomes significant for hyperthermal (>10 eV) impacts at glancing angles [182–184]. On the other hand, we note that the sticking probability is affected by many other factors, such as surface contamination from adsorbed gases [185] and surface temperature and morphology [183, 186]. Within the context of velocity selection experiments, Miller and Kusch aligned a straight channel with an atomic beam and monitored the flux of transmitted atoms to experimentally constrain the sticking probability [48]. They did not observe evidence of specular scattering and state diffuse reflection from the interior walls of the velocity selector contributed to (at most) a 0.1 % increase in beam intensity. Accordingly, appreciable effects due to scattering are probably unlikely in our apparatus as well.

The remainder of this chapter summarizes the engineering design and theoretical and computational modelling of a slotted cylinder velocity selector. First, in [section 3.2](#), I report on the construction of the velocity selector that was used to carry out this work. Following the work of Miller and Kusch [48] and Dash and Sommers [179], I then derive several expressions for $T(\omega)$ in [section 3.3](#) that apply under different approximations. In [section 3.4](#), I present Monte-Carlo (MC) simulation software that we developed to test these models and continue to derive a

new model to interpret simulated data for three-dimensional (3D) systems.

3.2 Engineering design

Constraints in the design of the velocity selector and its housing apparatus include transmission and rotation limits, and the geometry of the vacuum chamber. The velocity selector was designed for UHV application on a CF flange mounted above the source by a fixed distance of 86.4 cm. To obtain an appreciable signal-to-noise ratio, it was suspended from the flange by approximately 36.2 cm (center-of-mass) to increase the vapour flux passing through its helical channels. In practice, suspending it from such a large distance produced resonance phenomena, which I address in later sections.

Characteristics of the velocity selector transmission function were also important design considerations. The geometry of the velocity selector was chosen to yield a peak transmission of 40 to 50% and a signal accessible without having to use high rotation speeds, in excess of 8000 rpm. As I will show in later sections, these design considerations should be balanced with resolution requirements. In particular, low resolution combined with even low-divergence beams act to prevent low-speed filtering.

3.2.1 Velocity selector apparatus

This experiment uses a high-transmission slotted cylinder velocity selector, or spindle, that was constructed out of PH1 stainless steel using direct metal laser sintering and has dimensions that are accurate to $\pm 0.2\%$ (see [Figure 3.2a](#)). The 200.0 mm long cylinder has 90 helical channels that are equally spaced along the circumference at a

mean distance of 41.9 mm from the cylinder axis. Each channel is rotated by a 3.00° pitch angle and has a 2.90° window aperture.

Figure 3.2: Photographs of the velocity selector and its assembly.

The basic design principles for the integrated assembly (see [Figure 3.2b](#)), including the principles involved for its rotation in vacuum, are as follows. A servo motor, which is electrically isolated from the chamber, is connected to a ferromagnetic fluid sealed rotary feedthrough that is mounted on a 70 mm Conflat flange. The feedthrough is fixed to a zero-length reducer flange and attaches to a shaft in vacuum using a flexible helical shaft-coupler. The spindle rotates with the shaft and the radial loads are supported by three water-cooled bearing mounts that house shielded high-precision radial ball bearings lubed with Braycote 601EF vacuum grease. The bearing mounts are secured using a rigid support structure that is welded to the mounting flange and an aluminum oxide ceramic heat shield blocks the channels from incident vapour except a few along the beam axis.

We iterated the apparatus several times using both a guided and trial-and-error approach. For the most part, we focused on strategies to improve its mechanical

stability at high rotation speeds. Modal analysis software was used to identify the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the design under vibrational excitation and we designed additional support structures to suppress unwanted resonances below 250 Hz, which is ~ 80 Hz higher than the rated limit for the rotary components in the design.

3.2.2 Resonance problem

Mechanical resonance is a persistent problem in our system that has limited high-speed transmission measurements. Harmonic vibrations at the rotation frequency of the spindle are created when it rotates due to many factors, such as a rotating unbalance (i.e. an eccentric, or unbalanced, mass) or a shaft misalignment. These vibrations excite the base of its structure, acting as an external (harmonic) force that drives the assembly to oscillate. Resonance occurs when the driving frequency is equal to one of the natural frequencies of the system, resulting in large amplitudes of vibration that can be hazardous. We also note that resonance phenomena can cause the velocity selector to vibrate at noticeable amplitudes over a large range of frequencies (near a natural frequency), which is undesirable since this also affects transmission measurements.

Modal analysis is a method used to study the dynamic response of a structure under vibrational excitation. For complex vibration problems, it is common to approximate continuous, or distributed systems that have an infinite number of degrees of freedom as discrete multi-degree-of-freedom systems [187]. The governing equations of motion for a vibrating system that has n -degree-of-freedom are a set of n coupled

second order ordinary differential equations that can be derived from Newton's second law of motion. The resulting equations can be expressed in matrix form as an eigenvalue equation and the natural frequencies (eigenvalues) and the normal modes (eigenvectors) of vibration are determined by evaluating the 'free-vibration' response of the system. The free-vibration response is obtained when a system oscillates due to an initial disturbance (e.g. discrete elements are given an initial displacement) in the absence of external forces [187]. The normal modes, or modal vectors, are linearly independent and form a basis in the n -dimensional space. The response is therefore a linear superposition of the normal modes of vibration.

We experimentally observed resonance at 2850 ± 150 rpm, or 47.5 ± 2.5 Hz. Guided by modal analysis, we designed a support structure to increase the rigidity of the velocity selector apparatus and suppress unwanted resonances below 170 Hz, which is necessary in order to mechanically select high-speed atoms. In particular, we used modal analysis simulation software from Autodesk Inventor Professional, which uses the finite element method to determine the modal (natural) frequencies and mode shapes of a structure for a given a set of boundary conditions (structural constraints) and external forces (loads).

3.2.3 Reinforced assembly

An early prototype velocity selector is shown in [Figure 3.3a](#). Guided by simulation, we designed rigid support bars to reinforce the assembly and suppress resonance phenomena. The support bars were attached at one end to the bottom of the bearing support bars and connected at the other end to different available Conflat flanges mounted on the chamber, as shown in [Figure 3.3b](#). To achieve the necessary part

accuracy, each component was manufactured using computer numeric control machining and mechanically altered as needed to achieve a tight tolerance fit. As well, we also designed and constructed a new spindle. Its mounting position in the second generation designs is shown in [Figure 3.3c](#) and [Figure 3.3d](#).

Figure 3.3: Generations of the velocity selector assembly.

The first four mode shapes of the first generation velocity selector assembly are shown in [Figure 3.4](#). The first vibration mode is a longitudinal bending mode (along the x -axis) that has a natural frequency of 46.7 Hz, which is consistent with experimental observations between 45 and 50 Hz. The second vibration mode is a lateral bending mode along the y -axis at 89.5 Hz. The next two modes correspond to a torsional vibration mode (twisting along the rotation axis) at 291 Hz, followed by a higher order bending mode at 312 Hz.

With reinforcements, the fundamental frequency increased from 46.7 Hz to 220 Hz (see [Figure 3.5a](#) for the corresponding mode shape). This value is about 50 Hz higher than the rated operating speed of the rotary components used in the design. The design worked reasonably well and while we did not observe resonance in the new

Figure 3.4: The first four mode shapes of the first generation velocity selector apparatus. All simulations assume the flange mating surface is fixed and mesh the spindle using shell elements. We also note that the reported deformation values are not physical; mode shapes are assigned arbitrary amplitudes and should only be used for understanding how the part vibrates. In other words, the colour bar shows relative displacement values.

system, we designed a new spindle and its geometry required a new assembly. The fundamental mode shape and frequency of both the free and supported assembly are detailed in [Figure 3.5b](#) and [Figure 3.5c](#), respectively. In practice, we only tested the reinforced assembly and did not observe resonance phenomena.

Figure 3.5: Fundamental mode shapes and frequencies of velocity selector iterations.

3.2.4 Discussion

A variety of factors can affect the accuracy of a simulation. For instance, because the system is approximated using a finite element mesh, the mode shapes are better modelled by the element structures for low vibration modes. Also, due to the manufacturing process several differences exist between a simulated assembly and the physical apparatus, such as imperfect boundary conditions, imperfect contacts, and variations in the size and physical properties of the components. Approximations such as the omission of damping and modelling the bearings as solid components also affect the response of the system. We therefore relied on modal analysis as a guide to suppress unwanted resonances during the design process. In practice, we did not observe resonance phenomena while testing either of the reinforced assemblies and consider the support structure to be an effective design solution.

3.3 Theoretical modelling

The spindle is described by an admittance function, $\tau(v, \omega)$, that models the helical geometry of the channels to determine the fraction of atoms traveling at a speed v that are transmitted at the rotation speed ω . The integral transmission function, $T(\omega)$, is

$$T(\omega) = \int_0^{\infty} f(v)\tau(v, \omega)dv, \quad (3.1)$$

where $f(v)$ is assumed to be a normalized Maxwellian distribution and $f(v)\tau(v, \omega)$ is speed distribution of transmitted atoms. Transmission measurements depend on the quantity that is measured by the detector. For a number density detector that detects particles within a fixed spatial interval at a fixed time, $f(v)$ is given by [Equation 2.1](#).

For a particle flux detector that is sensitive to the rate at which particles cross a unit surface, $f(v)$ is given by [Equation 2.8](#).

3.3.1 Collimated beams

Assume a collimated beam, parallel to the velocity selector axis, is aligned with the center of a helical channel at a distance $r = r_0$ from the axis of rotation. Atoms with the speed

$$v_0 = \frac{\omega L}{\phi} \quad (3.2)$$

maintain a constant distance from the walls of the channel and travel a distance L during the time it takes the spindle to rotate by an angle ϕ . Similarly, atoms with a speed

$$v = \frac{\omega L}{\phi + \Delta\psi} = \frac{v_0}{1 + \Delta\psi/\phi} \quad (3.3)$$

move a transverse distance $r_0\Delta\psi$ relative to the side of the channel during transit. The minimum and maximum speeds that are transmitted are therefore

$$v_{\mp} = \frac{v_0}{1 \pm \gamma}, \quad (3.4)$$

where $\gamma \equiv \psi/\phi$. For example, an atom that enters a channel moving at the speed v_- will travel the distance L during the time it takes the spindle to rotate by $\phi + \psi$. Likewise, an atom with the speed v_+ will travel the same distance during the time it takes the spindle to rotate by an angle $\phi - \psi$.

The fraction of atoms that enter the helical channels, or the fractional open area

of a spindle with N_c channels, is

$$\tau_0 = \frac{N_c r_0 \psi}{2\pi r_0} = \frac{N_c \psi}{2\pi}. \quad (3.5)$$

For an atom to traverse a helical channel and avoid capture, it must enter a channel through a reduced, or effective aperture of width $r_0\psi - r_0|\Delta\psi|$, where $|\Delta\psi|$ ranges from 0 to ψ . The admittance function is defined over this range to be

$$\tau(v, v_0) = \frac{N_c(r_0\psi - r_0|\Delta\psi|)}{2\pi r_0} = \tau_0 \left(1 - \frac{|\Delta\psi|}{\psi}\right), \quad (3.6)$$

and is zero for $|\Delta\psi| > \psi$. Solving Equation 3.3 for $\Delta\psi$ and substituting the result into Equation 3.6, $\tau(v, v_0)$ becomes

$$\tau(v, v_0) = \tau_0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma} \left| \frac{v_0}{v} - 1 \right| \right), \quad (3.7)$$

which is valid over the range $v_- \leq v \leq v_+$, and 0 otherwise.

The transmission function,

$$T(v_0) = \int_{v_-}^{v_+} f(v) \tau(v, v_0) dv, \quad (3.8)$$

is evaluated using the substitution $x_0 = v_0/v_p$, where $v_p \equiv (2k_B T/m)^{1/2}$. When $f(v)$ is given by the MB speed distribution,

$$T(x_0) = \frac{\tau_0}{\gamma} [2 \operatorname{erf}(x_0) - (1 + \gamma) \operatorname{erf}(x_-) - (1 - \gamma) \operatorname{erf}(x_+)], \quad (3.9)$$

where $x_{\mp} = x_0/(1 \pm \gamma)$ and the error function is defined as

$$\operatorname{erf}(z) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^z e^{-t^2} dt. \quad (3.10)$$

A similar result is obtained when $f(v)$ is given by the flux distribution [48]:

$$T(x_0) = \frac{\tau_0}{\gamma} \left[(1 + \gamma)e^{-x_-^2} + (1 - \gamma)e^{-x_+^2} - 2e^{-x_0^2} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}x_0}{2} \left(\operatorname{erf}(x_-) + \operatorname{erf}(x_+) - 2\operatorname{erf}(x_0) \right) \right]. \quad (3.11)$$

3.3.2 Divergent beams

Consider a beam with a small angular spread $2\alpha_0$ emitted from a point source that is aligned with the center of one of the helical channels. The angle α_0 is determined either by the dimensions of the collimating system (e.g. the helical channels) or from the source-detector geometry, whichever is most restrictive. Beam divergence in the radial direction roughly modifies the effective length of the spindle by the factor $\sec(\alpha_0)$, which is negligible for this experiment. A marked departure from the collimated beam model can occur when the beam diverges in the tangential direction.

Consider an atom moving with a speed v , as defined by [Equation 3.3](#), that also has a tangential deflection α such that $-\alpha_0 \leq \alpha \leq \alpha_0$. In what follows, we assume positive angles point along the tangential velocity component of the channel, opposite to its twist (e.g. see [Figure 3.1](#)). In addition to moving a transverse distance $r_0\Delta\psi$ relative to the side of the channel during transit, it will be displaced by the amount

$L\alpha$. The admittance function, written as a function of α , is

$$\tau(v, v_0, \alpha) = \frac{N_c(r_0\psi - |r_0\Delta\psi - L\alpha|)}{2\pi r_0}, \quad (3.12)$$

which is valid for $|r_0\Delta\psi - L\alpha| \leq r_0\psi$ (since transmitted atoms cannot move a transverse distance that exceeds the dimension of the channel) and is zero otherwise. This expression can be written in the form

$$\tau(v, v_0, \alpha) = \tau_0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\gamma} \left| \frac{v_0}{v} - 1 - \frac{L\alpha}{r_0\phi} \right| \right) \quad (3.13)$$

when substituting $\Delta\psi$ in terms of v .

The admittance function, $\tau(v, v_0)$, is obtained by averaging [Equation 3.13](#) over α ,

$$\tau(v, v_0) = \frac{1}{2\alpha_0} \int_{-\alpha_0}^{\alpha_0} \tau(v, v_0, \alpha) d\alpha, \quad (3.14)$$

which was solved analytically by Dash and Sommers [179]. They provided an equivalent treatment except the negative sign in front of the $L\alpha$ terms, which does not affect $\tau(v, v_0)$ provided the distribution of polar angles is symmetric.

3.3.3 Root-mean-square transmitted speed

The root-mean-square (rms) speed of transmitted atoms is related to the second moment of the speed distribution of atoms that emerge from the velocity selector according to

$$v_{\text{rms}} = \langle v^2 \rangle^{1/2} = \left(\frac{1}{C} \int_0^\infty v^2 f(v) \tau(v, v_0) dv \right)^{1/2}, \quad (3.15)$$

where C is a normalization constant given by

$$C = \int_0^\infty f(v)\tau(v, v_0)dv. \quad (3.16)$$

For collimated beams, $v_{\text{rms}}(\omega) \approx v_0$ provided $\gamma \ll 1$. This is shown in Figure 3.6a, which plots $v_{\text{rms}}(\omega)$ and $T(\omega)$ for the spindle geometry described by Miller and Kusch (red) and the spindle used for this experiment (blue) [48]. The main difference is resolution; the admittance function relevant to this experiment overlaps substantially with $f(v)$ at low ω . Interestingly, v_{rms} does not increase monotonically with ω when accounting for beam divergence, nor does the transmission function vanish for $\omega \leq 0$ (Figure 3.6b). The transmission function is also found to be most sensitive to α_0 at negative rotation speeds. These results show that low-resolution combined with even a small beam divergence angle can prevent the selective transmission of low speeds.

Figure 3.6: Relationship between v_{rms} and ω for (a) collimated beams and (b) divergent beams given a MB flux distribution at 1500 K.

3.3.4 Beam axis misalignment

The transmission function is modified if the velocity selector is tilted with respect to the beam axis, as shown in Figure 3.7a and Figure 3.7b. Equivalently, it is also modified if the beam axis is misaligned with the axis of rotation due to an off-axis detector, as shown in Figure 3.7c.

Figure 3.7: (a) Beam axis and velocity selector axis are parallel. (b) Velocity selector is tilted. (c) Tangential displacement between the source and the detector.

For a tilt angle β , the pitch angle ϕ of the velocity selector can be replaced with an effective value

$$\phi_e \approx \phi + \frac{\beta L}{r_0}, \quad (3.17)$$

where L is the length of the spindle and r_0 is the radius to the center of the channels [179]. This relation is only approximate since the assumption that atoms travel a mean radial distance r_0 from the cylinder axis for arbitrary configurations is not generally valid (e.g. see section 3.4.7). We have tested this relation both experimentally and by simulation by varying the detector position along the tangential direction. For

example, consider a detector that is mounted on a linear translator that displaces it at an angle θ with respect to the tangential direction. If its projected displacement along the tangential direction is $y = d \cos(\theta)$, where d is measured from the translator, then the angle between the two axes is $\beta = \arctan(y/h)$, where h is the source to detector distance.

3.3.5 Scattering from residual gases

The transmission function is modified when beam atoms undergo velocity-dependent scattering with residual gases in transit to the detector. The mean free path of an atom or molecule moving with a definite speed v through a Maxwellian gas at temperature T that is composed of a single species of particles of mass m is

$$\lambda_v = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}x}{n\sigma} \left(e^{-x^2} + \left(2x + \frac{1}{x} \right) \int_0^x e^{-y^2} dy \right)^{-1}, \quad (3.18)$$

where $x = v/v_p$, $v_p = (2k_B T/m)^{1/2}$, n is the number density of the gas, and σ is the mutual collision cross section [120]. The cross-sectional scattering area is usually assumed constant and evaluated assuming the colliding particles are hard spheres, such that $\sigma = \pi \langle d \rangle^2$, where $\langle d \rangle$ is the average of the kinetic diameters of both species available from viscosity measurements. When v much exceeds the speeds of the gas particles or when the temperature of the gas tends to absolute zero, Equation 3.18 reduces to the more familiar form $\lambda = (n\sigma)^{-1}$, which specifies the mean free path of an atom or molecule moving with constant speed among a collection of randomly-distributed stationary particles. The survival probability,

$$P_v(z) = e^{-z/\lambda_v}, \quad (3.19)$$

evaluates the probability that an atom will travel a distance z without undergoing a collision [188]. Assuming any atom that scatters is removed from the beam, the transmission function can be weighted by $P_v(z)$ to obtain the fraction of atoms that reach the detector,

$$T(\omega) = \int_0^\infty P_v(h) f(v) \tau(v, \omega) dv, \quad (3.20)$$

where h is the source to detector distance, which is assumed to be constant.

Figure 3.8: (a) $P_v(z)$ is plotted as a function of v for $z = 53.9$ cm. (b) Effect of the velocity-dependent scattering on $T(\omega)$ given a MB flux distribution at 1500 K.

The residual gas in a vacuum chamber generally consists of air and all sorts of condensable vapours, such as water that desorbs from the internal surfaces of the chamber. An accurate determination of λ_v is very difficult since (i) the temperature of the gases and vapours may not be strictly defined, (ii) the vacuum tends to deteriorate as the rotation speed of the velocity selector increases, and (iii) the change in pressure is accompanied by a change in composition, as shown in [subsection 4.3.2](#). To simplify the analysis, we assume the residual gas consists of air at room temperature. If the effective particle diameters of air and Ag are 3.72 \AA and

2.85 Å, respectively [122], their mutual cross section is $3.4 \times 10^{-15} \text{ cm}^2$. The dependence of $P_v(z)$ on v is such that low-speed atoms preferentially scatter, as plotted in [Figure 3.8a](#) for different chamber pressures up to 10^{-6} Torr. The effect of the beam hardening on the transmission function, $T(\omega)$, is shown in [Figure 3.8b](#). To account for the measured pressure dependence on rotation speed, plotted in the bottom panel, we let $n \rightarrow n(\omega)$ in the analysis. Around 2.3×10^{-7} Torr, there is essentially no difference between spectra calculated with and without scattering corrections. There is also very little difference between spectra, magnified in the inset, assuming an order of magnitude increase in pressure.

3.4 Computational modelling

We developed MC simulation software to test theoretical models of the transmission function, as they apply for either collimated or divergent beams in one or two dimensions. We also simulate 3D systems and investigate the effect of off-axis deflection. To improve the agreement between theory and simulation, we also develop a new approach to evaluate the transmission function.

3.4.1 Overview

The integral transmission function evaluates the fraction of atoms transmitted through the velocity selector. If a detector is positioned above the helical channels, this function is equal to the ratio of the quantity (i.e. number density or flux) of detected atoms to the quantity that would be detected without a velocity selector.

With reference to [Figure 3.9](#), an atom is created at a random position on a planar, circular, cosine-emitting surface with a pseudo-random speed sampled from the

Figure 3.9: (a) Schematic of a slotted cylinder velocity selector containing a single helical channel and (b) source-detector geometry. The angles α_0 and α_+ are defined assuming there is no additional collimation from the velocity selector.

Maxwellian distribution. Trajectories that intercept a finite-sized detector are advanced by a distance d along the z -axis to the bottom of the velocity selector. To ensure each atom enters a random channel at an arbitrary initial distance from its walls, we rotate the velocity selector by a random azimuthal angle, θ_i , that ranges from 0 to 2π upon initialization. An atom is then propagated with a constant velocity and an algorithm that characterizes the geometry of the velocity selector determines whether or not it evades capture. The transmission function is calculated from the ratio of the number of atoms that emerge from the velocity selector to the total number of simulated atoms.

3.4.2 Initializing atoms

Atomic positions

We rely on disk point picking to initialize atoms at random positions on a 2D disk. Let the polar coordinates r and θ define the position of an atom. If u and v are uniformly distributed random variables on the interval $[0, 1]$, then the azimuthal coordinate, θ , and radial coordinate, r , are calculated according to

$$\theta = 2\pi u, \quad \text{and} \quad r = \sqrt{v}r_0, \quad (3.21)$$

which span the intervals $[0, 2\pi]$ and $[0, r_0]$, respectively [189].

Particle speeds

We use the inverse transform sampling method to sample speeds from the Maxwellian distribution. This method relies on the inverse cumulative distribution function to generate random samples from a specified probability density function (pdf) [190]. If $f(x)$ is the pdf of a continuous random variable, x , then the related cumulative distribution function (cdf) of a real-valued random variable X , denoted as $F_X(x)$, evaluates the probability of obtaining $X \leq x$, and is given as

$$F_X(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x f(t)dt, \quad (3.22)$$

where t is an integration variable. The domain of the cdf maps $F_X(x)$ into the interval $[0, 1]$. If a uniform random variable on the interval $[0, 1]$, U , is input to the inverse of cdf, then $x = F_X^{-1}(U)$ is distributed according to the cdf. Accordingly, x has the

probability density $f(x)$.

Since the MB speed distribution is, by definition, zero for speeds less than zero, its cdf is given as

$$\begin{aligned} F_V(v) &= \int_0^v \frac{4\mu^3 u^2}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-(\mu u)^2} du, \\ &= \operatorname{erf}(\mu v) - \frac{2\mu v}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-(\mu v)^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

where u is an integration variable and $\mu = (2k_B T/m)^{-1/2}$. Similarly, the cdf for the flux distribution is

$$\begin{aligned} F_V(v) &= \int_0^v 2\mu^4 u^3 e^{-(\mu u)^2} du, \\ &= 1 - ((\mu v)^2 + 1) e^{-(\mu v)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

The inverse of both functions are evaluated numerically and used to generate N pseudo-random particle speeds.

Velocity unit vectors

To generate initial velocity vectors, we assume that the ideal cosine law of emission applies at each infinitesimal element of area on a planar emitting surface [152, 191]. The velocity unit vector is defined in spherical coordinates to be

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\mathbf{r}} = \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \hat{\mathbf{i}} + \sin(\theta) \sin(\phi) \hat{\mathbf{j}} + \cos(\phi) \hat{\mathbf{k}}, \quad (3.25)$$

where the polar angle, ϕ , ranges from 0 to $\pi/2$ and the azimuthal coordinate, θ , ranges from 0 to 2π . To improve computational efficiency, we use the following relations to

randomly generate vectors, distributed according to the cosine emission law, within the restricted polar angles $\phi \in [0, \phi_r]$:

$$\theta = 2\pi u, \quad \text{and} \quad \phi = \arcsin\left(\sqrt{v \sin^2(\phi_r)}\right), \quad (3.26)$$

where u and v are uniformly distributed random variables on the interval $[0, 1]$. If the polar angle is not restricted, ϕ reduces to the known expression $\phi = \arcsin(\sqrt{v})$ [192].

The expression for ϕ is derived as follows. From kinetic theory, the integral form of the angular probability distribution for cosine emission is

$$A \equiv \int_{\theta=0}^{2\pi} \int_{\phi=0}^{\phi_r} \frac{1}{\pi} \cos(\phi) \sin(\phi) d\theta d\phi = \sin^2(\phi_r), \quad (3.27)$$

which is unity when $\phi_r = \pi/2$. The pdf must be weighted by the area, A ,

$$f(\theta, \phi) d\theta d\phi = \frac{\cos(\phi) \sin(\phi)}{\pi \sin^2(\phi_r)} d\theta d\phi, \quad (3.28)$$

in order to satisfy the normalization condition

$$1 = \int_{\theta=0}^{2\pi} \int_{\phi=0}^{\phi_r} f(\theta, \phi) d\theta d\phi. \quad (3.29)$$

Since θ and ϕ are independent variables, $f(\theta, \phi)$ can be separated into the product of two independent pdfs, $f(\theta)$ and $f(\phi)$. The marginal density function, $f(\theta)$, can be evaluated by integrating out the angular dependency of the polar coordinate,

$$f(\theta) = \int_0^{\phi_r} f(\theta, \phi) d\phi = \frac{1}{\pi \sin^2(\phi_r)} \int_0^{\phi_r} \cos(\phi) \sin(\phi) d\phi = \frac{1}{2\pi}. \quad (3.30)$$

Similarly, the pdf for ϕ is

$$f(\phi) = \int_0^{2\pi} f(\theta, \phi) d\theta = \frac{\cos(\phi) \sin(\phi)}{\pi \sin^2(\phi_r)} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta = \frac{\sin(2\phi)}{\sin^2(\phi_r)}, \quad (3.31)$$

and $f(\theta, \phi) d\theta d\phi = f(\theta) f(\phi) d\theta d\phi$, as required. The distribution $f(\phi) d\phi$ evaluates the probability that an atom will have a velocity vector with a polar angle within the interval ϕ and $\phi + d\phi$.

Random samples from $f(\phi)$ are generated using its inverse cumulative distribution function. Making use of the introduction to inverse transform sampling in [section 3.4.2](#), the cdf for $f(\phi)$, written as $F(\beta)$ where β is an integration variable, is

$$F(\phi) = \int_0^\phi f(\beta) d\beta = \frac{1}{\sin^2(\phi_r)} \int_0^\phi \sin(2\beta) d\beta = \frac{\sin^2(\phi)}{\sin^2(\phi_r)}. \quad (3.32)$$

Setting $v = F(\phi)$ and solving for ϕ , where v is a uniform random variable on the interval $[0,1]$, yields the expression for ϕ in [Equation 3.26](#). This procedure is easily repeated for the azimuthal coordinate, θ , and can also be applied to uniform point picking from a disk.

3.4.3 Polar angle distribution

The distribution of polar angles for an extended source and an infinite plane detector has a characteristic $\sin(2\phi)$ shape. When the detector has a finite size, the polar coordinate is restricted to its largest possible angle, α_+ . As shown in [Figure 3.10a](#), the distribution obtained when considering all initialized atoms (red) agrees with [Equation 3.31](#). However, the choice $\phi_r = \alpha_+$ does not guarantee that an initialized vector will intercept the detector. Each trajectory is therefore initialized iteratively

until a valid vector is found. The resulting distribution is plotted in blue. As shown, the probability density drops rapidly as $\phi \rightarrow \alpha_+$ since only a small fraction of atoms with large ϕ are initialized near the perimeter of the source with valid trajectories.

Figure 3.10: (a) Normalized distribution of polar angles for 10^5 randomly sampled velocity vectors. (b) Distribution of polar angles projected in the yz -plane.

We improved the agreement between simulation and theory for 3D systems by accounting for the non-uniform polar angle distribution. In keeping with the 2D description for divergent beams, the admittance function can be weighted by the polar angle pdf, projected along the tangential direction of the velocity selector, $f_p(\phi)$, before averaging it over the limiting range of beam divergence angles:

$$\tau(v, v_0) = \frac{\int_{-\alpha_+}^{\alpha_+} f_p(\phi) \tau(v, v_0, \phi) d\phi}{\int_{-\alpha_+}^{\alpha_+} f_p(\phi) d\phi}. \quad (3.33)$$

In the spherical coordinate system, an atom's polar angle projected into the yz -plane is $\phi_p = \arctan(\hat{\mathbf{e}}_r \cdot \hat{\mathbf{j}} / \hat{\mathbf{e}}_r \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}})$, which belongs the domain $[-\alpha_+, \alpha_+]$. A normalized histogram containing the set of projected polar angles, $\{\phi_p\}$, is plotted in [Figure 3.10b](#).

3.4.4 Velocity selector algorithm

Velocity selection is the central aspect of this simulation. The `ATOMALIVE` function¹ determines if the atom is alive, propagating inside a channel, or dead (i.e. if it has struck one of the inner walls). This function inputs the cylindrical coordinates of an atom, r , θ , and z , in the coordinate frame of the velocity selector defined in [Figure 3.9a](#). It also inputs the rotation speed of the velocity selector, ω , the time that has elapsed since the start of the simulation, t , and the initial azimuthal rotation of the velocity selector, θ_i , and it outputs either `True` (atom is alive) or `False` (atom is dead). The algorithm is shown in [Figure 3.11](#); 10^6 atoms were initialized at random positions ($r \in [0, r_+]$, $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$, and $z \in [0, L]$) and then plotted if they were found inside a channel.

Figure 3.11: A plot of the velocity selector algorithm.

Pseudocode for the `ATOMALIVE` function is included in [Algorithm 1](#). First, the function determines if the atom's z position is outside the range $[0, L]$. If it is, the atom is alive since it can possibly be inside a wall. If the atom's z position is inside

¹A great thank you to Connor Stone for helping me write this cornerstone algorithm!

the cylinder, the function then determines if the atom is outside the channels in the radial direction. If neither condition is met, the function then determines if the atom is inside a window or if it has exceeded the window aperture, in which case the atom is inside a wall and the function returns FALSE (see next paragraph). If none of these conditions are met then the atom must be alive and the function returns TRUE.

Algorithm 1 Determine if the atom is alive or dead.

```

1: function ATOMALIVE( $r, \theta, z, \omega, t, \theta_i$ )
2:   if  $z < 0$  or  $z > L$  then
3:     return True
4:   if  $r < r_-$  or  $r > r_+$  then
5:     return False
6:    $\theta_e = (\theta - (\omega t + \theta_i) + \phi z / L) \% 2\pi$ 
7:   if  $\theta_e \% 2\pi / N_c > \psi$  then
8:     return False
9:   else
10:    return True

```

The velocity selector rotates by an angle $\omega t + \theta_i$ in the time interval t , during which the trailing wall moves closer to the atom. The atom, instead of the velocity selector, is rotated by this angle in the opposite direction. In addition, because the atom's distance from the trailing wall increases as it advances in the z direction, the walls of a particular channel are offset by the amount $\phi z / L$, owing to the fact that the velocity selector has helical channels and not straight channels. The equivalent azimuthal coordinate, θ_e , of the atom is

$$\theta_e = \left(\theta - (\omega t + \theta_i) + \frac{\phi z}{L} \right) \% 2\pi, \quad (3.34)$$

where the modulo operator, $\%$, evaluates the remainder of the division of a by b ,

defined as

$$a \% b = a - b \left\lfloor \frac{a}{b} \right\rfloor, \quad (3.35)$$

where $\lfloor x \rfloor \equiv \text{floor}(x)$. This operation restricts θ_e to the interval $[0, 2\pi]$, even for negative dividends. If ψ and ψ^* define the window and wall angular apertures, respectively, then $N_c(\psi + \psi^*) = 2\pi$ for a velocity selector that has N_c channels. All channels can be made identical to the first one through the operation

$$\theta_r = \theta_e \% \frac{2\pi}{N_c}, \quad (3.36)$$

where θ_r is defined to be the reduced azimuthal coordinate of the atom. In the collapsed system, the atom is inside a wall if the reduced azimuthal coordinate exceeds ψ . This method is reviewed in [Figure 3.12](#); θ_r is indicated for an atom that is propagating inside a window ([Figure 3.12a](#)), and for an atom that has condensed on the leading edge ([Figure 3.12b](#)) and trailing edge ([Figure 3.12c](#)) of a channel.

Figure 3.12: Cross-section of the velocity selector; coloured elements represent channels (i.e. windows) and white regions represent walls. (a) An atom with the equivalent azimuthal angle θ_e that is inside the window of the fifth channel. (b, c) An atom that has condensed on the leading/trailing edge of the same channel. In the collapsed systems, the reduced azimuthal coordinates correspond to (a) an atom that is propagating in the first channel, (b) an atom that has condensed on the leading edge of the first channel, and (c) an atom that has condensed on the trailing edge of the first channel.

A variety of auxiliary statistics can be queried from this software, including the channel number, n_c , in which an atom is propagating and its condensation location. While an atom is still alive, the channel number in which it is propagating is calculated according to

$$n_c = \left\lceil \frac{\theta_e}{\psi + \psi^*} \right\rceil, \quad (3.37)$$

where $\lceil x \rceil \equiv \text{ceiling}(x)$ and $n_c \in [1, N_c]$. Atoms that are found inside a wall at $z \approx 0$ condensed on the face of the velocity selector. Depending on the source and detector geometry, it is also possible for the radial coordinate of an atom to exceed $[r_-, r_+]$. Atoms with $z > 0$ and $r_- < r < r_+$ that condense on the leading or trailing wall of a channel satisfy

$$\frac{\theta_r}{\psi} \approx 1, \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\theta_r}{\psi + \psi^*} \approx 1, \quad (3.38)$$

respectively. These relations are only approximate since atoms may be found slightly inside a wall due to the finite time step used to propagate them.

3.4.5 Uncertainty

While, for a single simulation, there is no uncertainty in the number of transmitted atoms, the randomness associated with the MC experiment will cause this number to vary between simulations. For example, a simulated distribution, generated using inverse transform sampling, is in a quasi-equilibrium state (i.e. only close to equilibrium) due to the finite number of initialized particles. The deviation from thermodynamic equilibrium can be characterized in terms of energy fluctuations in the canonical ensemble for a finite system of N particles at constant temperature T in thermal contact with a heat bath. While the internal energy of the system fluctuates randomly about its mean value $\langle E \rangle$, the rms fluctuation is non-vanishing [113, 115],

calculated according to

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{\langle E \rangle} = \frac{\langle (E - \langle E \rangle)^2 \rangle^{1/2}}{\langle E \rangle}. \quad (3.39)$$

This expression evaluates to

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{\langle E \rangle} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3N}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\sigma_E}{\langle E \rangle} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2N}}, \quad (3.40)$$

for fluctuations about the average energy $3k_B T N/2$ and $2k_B T N$, respectively.

Figure 3.13: Relative rms energy fluctuation as a function of the number of initialized Ag atoms at various temperatures. The ensemble average is approximated by initializing 1000 microstates and averaging the results.

We generated states with a varying number of particles to show rms energy fluctuations follow these scaling relations. Figure 3.13a and Figure 3.13b plot results for particle speeds initialized with a MB speed and flux distribution, respectively. The data was fit to the model $cN^{-1/2}$ and the corresponding fit constants were evaluated to be 0.82 and 0.70. These values are in good agreement with the predicted values $\sqrt{2/3}$ and $\sqrt{1/2}$.

Other parameters contribute to the uncertainty that are more difficult to model, such as the emission angle. For simplicity, we assume that the number of transmitted

atoms is a binomial random variable [193]. Every atom that is propagated through the velocity selector represents an independent trial (since they are individually propagated) that has one of two possible outcomes: the atom can either condense or it can be transmitted. Let p denote the probability that an atom will be transmitted in a single trial and assume ν atoms are transmitted in a single experiment consisting of n independent trials. If the entire experiment is repeated several times and ν is binomial-distributed, the average number of transmitted atoms is $\langle \nu \rangle = np$ and

$$\sigma = \sqrt{np(1-p)} \quad (3.41)$$

is the standard deviation of the number of atoms that make it through the velocity selector.

3.4.6 Admittance function simulations

The admittance function describes the fraction of atoms traveling at speed v that are transmitted through a velocity selector rotating at the speed ω . Even when the beam divergence angle is small, the admittance function may be substantially modified relative to the collimated beam case.

These simulations considered a 2D system of particles, emitted from a point source, with uniformly distributed random speeds and uniformly distributed random polar angles on the interval $[-\alpha_0, \alpha_0]$. To compute the admittance function, we recorded the speed v_i of every atom and whether or not it was transmitted. We then applied the same binning to both the set $\{v_i\}_1^N$ and the speeds of transmitted atoms and calculated the ratio.

Figure 3.14: The simulated admittance function for divergent beams emitted from a point source is shown in red with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars and compared with various models.

The data plotted in [Figure 3.14a](#) and [Figure 3.14b](#) agree with the theory for divergent beams developed by Dash and Sommers without the need for any fit parameters [179]. In contrast, there is a clear difference between simulation and the model for slotted-disk type velocity selectors developed by Frankl (evaluated assuming the ratio of the disk thickness to the length of the rotor is zero) [194].

3.4.7 Transmission function simulations

We have found that collimated beams and beams that diverge along the tangential direction of the velocity selector are well described by the formalism developed by Dash and Sommers [179]. For 3D systems, however, atoms are no longer confined to either 1D or 2D motion, nor are they emitted from a hypothetical point source. In this section, I compare simulated data with two models of varying complexity. The first model fits the theory for divergent beams to the data using an effective beam divergence angle, $\alpha_0 \rightarrow \alpha_{fit}$. The second model accounts for distribution of polar

angles, as discussed in [subsection 3.4.3](#).

Divergent atomic beams

The divergent beam model fits the data reasonably well for small sources, as shown in [Figure 3.15a](#). Departures from the model become appreciable for larger sources, as evidenced by residuals that systematically depart from zero at negative rotation speeds. As shown in [Figure 3.15b](#), the model underestimates the transmission probability for negative rotation speeds and overestimates it for rotation speeds approaching the peak.

Figure 3.15: The simulated transmission function is plotted in red with $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars in (a) for the MB speed distribution and (b) for the MB flux distribution. Models for collimated and divergent beams are plotted and green and blue, respectively.

The second model uses a weighted average to calculate the admittance function over the limiting range of divergence angles. In both cases, the simulated results are in good agreement with this model without the need for any fit parameters. The goodness-of-fit is also indicated by the residual plots; most residuals intercept the x -axis within $\pm 1\sigma$.

Figure 3.16: Location where atoms condense as a function of rotation speed. No atoms exceeded the radial dimensions of a channel for either simulation.

Figure 3.16a and Figure 3.16b plot the condensation statistics for the same two simulations. The fraction of atoms that condense on the bottom face of the velocity selector, labeled ‘dead on arrival’, is ~ 0.275 . This value is related to its fractional open area, $\tau_0 = N_c \psi / (2\pi) = 0.725$. The remaining atoms either escape or condense on the leading or trailing wall of a channel. At slow rotation speeds, most of the incident vapour condenses on the leading wall. As the rotation speed increases this fraction decreases while the fraction that condense on the trailing wall increases by a commensurate amount. The peak transmission occurs when these values are nearly equal.

Misaligned detector

With reference to Figure 3.17a, this section considers the effect of off-axis detection. The effect of tangential displacement on the transmission probability was modelled in subsection 3.3.4 by replacing the pitch angle of the helical channels with an effective

value, ϕ_e . In addition to tangential displacement, we also consider the less restrictive, and probably more applicable, case when the detector is placed in a general location.

Figure 3.17: (a) Source-detector geometry. (b, c) A comparison between theory and simulation for different detector positions (MB flux distribution, HTEC-QCM geometry).

As shown in [Figure 3.17b](#), displacing the detector along the y direction by a small amount yields a considerably different transmission spectrum. We calculated ϕ_e for the two configurations and found that the divergent beam model, as it applies a for point source, fits the simulated data reasonably well for $\alpha_{fit} = 0.40^\circ$. This value is consistent with previous results for on-axis detection (e.g. see [Figure 3.15a](#)). Since the detector position is known exactly for simulated systems, we also simulated the

relevant polar angle distributions and show the weighted divergent beam model agrees with the data for both configurations without the need for an effective pitch angle or fit parameter.

We introduce an effective radius, r_{fit} , to [Equation 3.17](#),

$$\phi_e = \phi + \frac{\arctan(y/h)L}{r_{fit}}, \quad (3.42)$$

when the detector position is off-centred. This treatment is needed for both models since the approximation that atoms travel inside the helical channels at a mean radial distance r_0 from the cylinder axis breaks down. As shown in [Figure 3.17c](#), agreement exists when the detector is displaced in both x and y provided $r_0 \rightarrow r_{fit}$ is treated as a fitting parameter. We note that r_{fit} is greater than the radial distance to either the source or detector when $y = -4$ mm and $x = r_0 + 2.5$ mm, while the opposite is true when $y = -4$ mm and $x = r_0 - 2.5$ mm.

The weighted divergent beam model, as it compensates for non-uniform polar angle distributions, has so far successfully approximated simulations that use a large, extended source geometry. However, it is especially challenging to implement this model under experimental conditions since the detector position along the x and y directions, r_{fit} , and possibly the source radius are not known. Even if r_{fit} and the source radius are known, we have not been able to determine x and y from curve fitting. Out of necessity, we developed the following recipe. As a first step, we note that r_{fit} is linearly correlated with the radial coordinate of the detector, $(x^2 + y^2)^{1/2}$, as measured from the velocity selector axis. This is shown in [Figure 3.18a](#), which plots a collection of r_{fit} retrieved from curve fitting for different detector positions and source radii (see inset). Having performed linear regression to determine the

relation, we assembled a library of expected spectra within the deemed parameter space. The parameter space spans a range of source radii and detector positions and collectively the expected signals are referred to as the template bank. We can then compare spectra in the template bank to simulated or experimental data in search for the best match based on a χ^2 minimization approach.

Figure 3.18: (a) Relationship between $(x^2 + y^2)^{1/2}$ and r_{fit} for different detector positions and source radii (MB flux distribution at 1498 K). (b) A simulation is compared with the template bank to estimate the detector displacement. (c, d) The simulation from (b) is repeated ~ 1000 times and the x and y displacement estimates are binned and fitted to a Gaussian distribution.

Consider a data set that consists of N independent observations O_i that each have normally distributed error σ_i . When fitting a model to a set of data points, the chi-squared test for goodness of fit minimizes

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (3.43)$$

where E_i is the expected value. For single-model assessment and to compare similar models, it is convenient to use the reduced chi-squared statistic as a convergence diagnostic, defined as $\chi_r^2 = \chi^2/K$, where K denotes the (generalized) number of degrees of freedom. In what follows, we assumed $K = N - P$, where P is the number of fit parameters [195].

Having built a template bank, we simulated data for a 0.762 mm source at 1498 K. The χ_r^2 contour plot is shown in Figure 3.18b. For ~ 1000 simulations, $\langle \chi_r^2 \rangle = 1.009$. The histogram plot of x displacement estimates shown in Figure 3.18c is well approximated by a normal distribution with a mean and standard deviation of -1.1 ± 0.4 mm. Similarly, the displacement along the y direction is -3.71 ± 0.08 mm (see Figure 3.18d). Both estimates are in close agreement with the actual values of -1.24 mm and -3.70 mm, respectively. The y position estimate is, however, more precise (by a factor of 5) due to pitch angle sensitivity.

The weighted divergent beam model, calculated using either the true detector coordinates or those estimated using this analysis method, are in close agreement with simulation, as shown in Figure 3.19a. The goodness of fit is also indicated by the residual plot; Figure 3.19b shows the distribution of normalized residuals agrees well with a Gaussian with mean and variance of $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 1$, respectively [195].

Figure 3.19: (a) Simulated transmission spectrum from Figure 3.18b and (b) the corresponding residual plot. The histogram showing the distribution of normalized residuals in the inset is compared with a normalized Gaussian centred at 0 with a variance $\sigma^2 = 1$.

3.4.8 Energy fluctuations (some derivations)

Following the work in subsection 3.4.5, a simple derivation of σ_E can be obtained by making use of the following relation:

$$\langle (E - \langle E \rangle)^2 \rangle = \langle E^2 \rangle - 2 \langle E \langle E \rangle \rangle + \langle E \rangle^2 = \langle E^2 \rangle - \langle E \rangle^2, \quad (3.44)$$

where the last step follows from the fact that $\langle E \rangle$ is constant and can therefore be pulled out of the ensemble average. The MB energy distribution,

$$f_\epsilon d\epsilon = f_v \left(\frac{dv}{d\epsilon} \right) d\epsilon = 2 \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\pi}} \left(\frac{1}{k_B T} \right)^{3/2} e^{-\epsilon/(k_B T)} d\epsilon, \quad (3.45)$$

has first- and second-order moments given by

$$\langle \epsilon \rangle = \int_0^\infty \epsilon f_\epsilon d\epsilon = \frac{3k_B T}{2}, \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \epsilon^2 \rangle = \int_0^\infty \epsilon^2 f_\epsilon d\epsilon = \frac{15k_B^2 T^2}{4}, \quad (3.46)$$

where $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon^2 \rangle$ denote the mean and mean-square energy per atom. These quantities are related to $\langle E \rangle$ and $\langle E^2 \rangle$ by a multiple of N . From these results, $\sigma_E = \sqrt{3Nk_B^2 T^2/2}$.

The MB flux distribution is also of interest since, under steady-state conditions, it is experimentally measured in this study using a rate-sensitive detector. The corresponding energy distribution is derived to be

$$f_\epsilon d\epsilon = f_v \left(\frac{dv}{d\epsilon} \right) d\epsilon = \frac{\epsilon}{(k_B T)^2} e^{-\epsilon/(k_B T)} d\epsilon, \quad (3.47)$$

which is a pdf that describes the rate at which particles cross a unit surface with energies between ϵ and $\epsilon + d\epsilon$. Using the same formalism, it is straightforward to derive an expression for σ_E that corresponds to the rms fluctuations in the energy of the system crossing a unit surface at constant temperature (i.e. in contrast to the previous result, which corresponds to energy fluctuations in the volume of a system). The relevant moments of the energy distribution are

$$\langle \epsilon \rangle = \int_0^\infty \epsilon f_\epsilon d\epsilon = 2k_B T, \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \epsilon^2 \rangle = \int_0^\infty \epsilon^2 f_\epsilon d\epsilon = 6k_B^2 T^2, \quad (3.48)$$

where $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon^2 \rangle$ represent the average energy and mean-square energy per atom crossing a unit surface per second, respectively. The rms fluctuation is then $\sigma_E = \sqrt{2Nk_B^2 T^2}$, yielding

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{\langle E \rangle} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2N}}. \quad (3.49)$$

Chapter 4

Detection methods

There are many methods that can be used to detect neutral atoms from thermal energy atomic beams. Organized by their measurement principle, the most commonly used detectors include, (i) accumulation detectors such as the quartz monitoring sensor, (ii) ionization detectors such as the Bayard-Alpert ionization gauge, (iii) surface ionization detectors such as the Langmuir-Taylor detector, (iv) thermal detectors such as cryogenic bolometers, and (v) spectroscopic detectors that rely on, for example, photoionization or laser-induced fluorescence [196]. State-of-the-art mass-selective and state-selective detectors also exist that are able to distinguish beam particles from residual gas atoms and molecules. We designed brand-new experiments to measure the transmission function, $T(\omega)$, using the first two detectors listed.

The quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) and the hot-filament ionization gauge are two standard instruments that operate on different physical principles. QCMs are the most widely used sensor for *in situ* thickness and deposition rate monitoring during thin film deposition, capable of measuring mass changes on the order of nanograms per square centimetre in relatively short measurement times [23]. In contrast, hot-filament

ionization gauges, sometimes called hot-cathode ionization gauges or Bayard-Alpert ionization gauges, are the most commonly used instrument for pressure measurements in high vacuum and ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) environments ranging from 10^{-3} Torr to 10^{-11} Torr [197, 198]. This chapter will review operating principles and experimental details for both detectors.

4.1 Quartz crystal microbalance

The use of a quartz crystal resonator as a mass-sensing device was first investigated by Sauerbrey in the late 1950s. Today QCMs have become the most commonly used instrument for *in situ* thickness and deposition rate sensing for PVD processes [23]. QCMs can be operated anywhere from vacuum to high pressure environments and have a lifetime that is usually determined by the type and amount of material that is deposited on its surface. If the accumulated mass is too large, the crystal will fail to oscillate [23].

4.1.1 Theory

A typical quartz crystal monitor, shown in Figure 4.1, consists of metal electrodes that are deposited on either side of a thin piezoelectric quartz crystal. The crystal will undergo shear deformation when a voltage is applied across the two electrodes due to the piezoelectric effect. When an alternating potential electrically excites the crystal at one of its resonant frequencies, a standing shear wave is established across the thickness of the crystal with displacement maxima at the surfaces [199]. During use *in vacuo*, an oscillator circuit is used to vibrate the crystal at the frequency of its fundamental mode and, as material condenses on its surface, its oscillation frequency

decreases by an amount that is related to the mass of the adsorbed layer.

Figure 4.1: Illustration of the front and back sides of a standard quartz monitor crystal. The hatched area in each figure represents the electrode coating. (a) ‘Double anchor’ electrode pattern. (b) ‘Full-pad’, or fully-coated electrode that faces the deposition source. The shaded region represents a film that has been deposited on the electrode.

Sauerbrey method

The resonant condition for a thickness-shear mode resonator at its fundamental frequency, f_0 , is

$$f_0 = \frac{v_s}{2t_q}, \quad (4.1)$$

where t_q is the crystal thickness and v_s is the shear wave phase velocity [199]. When this condition is satisfied, the acoustic wavelength is equal to one half of the thickness of the crystal and a standing wave is established with displacement maxima at the surfaces, such that the top and bottom crystal faces move in opposite directions.

For a uniformly deposited layer of material that rigidly couples to the quartz crystal (such that it moves synchronously with the oscillating quartz crystal), the change in mass, Δm , is related to the measured frequency shift, Δf , according to the Sauerbrey equation,

$$\Delta f = -\frac{2f_0^2}{A\sqrt{\rho_q\mu_q}}\Delta m, \quad (4.2)$$

where f_0 is the fundamental frequency, A is the active area of the crystal, ρ_q is the density of quartz (2.648 g cm^{-3}), and μ_q is the shear modulus of quartz

$(2.947 \times 10^{11} \text{ g cm}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2})$ [200]. Reasonably accurate mass and thickness measurements using the Sauerbrey equation are limited to the case when the frequency shift from f_0 is less than $\sim 2\%$, such that the deposited film does not experience appreciable shear deformation [200].

Z-match method

Modern QCM monitors and controllers rely on the so-called ‘Z-match’ method, an improvement to Sauerbrey’s linear equation that models the quartz crystal and the deposited film as a composite acoustic resonator [200, 201]. Provided the acoustic losses in the quartz crystal and the deposited film are small, the change in mass per unit area is

$$\frac{\Delta m}{A} = \frac{N_q \rho_q}{\pi Z f} \arctan \left(Z \tan \left(\frac{\pi(f_0 - f)}{f_0} \right) \right), \quad (4.3)$$

where f_0 is the resonant frequency of the unloaded crystal (prior to deposition), f is the resonant frequency of the loaded crystal, ρ_q is the density of quartz, and N_q is the frequency constant of the quartz crystal ($1.668 \times 10^5 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$) [200]. The so-called Z-Factor, Z , is the ratio of the shear-mode acoustic impedance of the quartz crystal to that of the deposited film, given as

$$Z = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_q \mu_q}{\rho_f \mu_f}}, \quad (4.4)$$

where μ_q is the shear modulus of quartz and ρ_f and μ_f are the density and shear modulus of the deposited film, both of which are generally close to their accepted bulk values. In this work, we took the Z-Factor and the density of silver to be 0.529 and 10.50 g cm^{-3} , respectively [202]. This method provides reasonably accurate mass

and thickness estimates for frequency shifts up to $\sim 40\%$, beyond which acoustic losses become significant.

4.1.2 Monitor and control system

With reference to [Figure 4.2](#), this experiment used 14 mm diameter gold-coated AT-cut quartz crystals mounted in commercially available water-cooled sensor heads. The crystals had a fully-coated electrode pattern on the surface facing the deposition source and a double-anchor electrode pattern on the other side, as shown in [Figure 4.1](#). This pattern is known to provide a stable electrical connection and suppress unwanted modes of oscillation [\[203\]](#). The SQM-242 controller card from Inficon monitored the thickness and deposition rate of four QCMs that were independently driven by external oscillators [\[202\]](#). This controller relies on an active oscillator circuit to drive each crystal at its fundamental frequency. It also performs the frequency to accumulated thickness conversion using the Z -match method. Assuming a measurement period of 0.50 s, its frequency resolution is 0.055 Hz at 6 MHz, the unloaded resonance frequency of the crystals [\[202\]](#). For a uniformly deposited silver film, this corresponds to a thickness and deposition rate sensitivity of 0.0064 \AA and 0.013 \AA s^{-1} , respectively. For comparison, a deposition rate of 0.01 \AA s^{-1} corresponds to a pressure between 10^{-8} and 10^{-7} Torr, assuming [Equation 2.6](#) for a Maxwellian distribution of velocities at 1235 K, which is orders of magnitude above the detection limit of ionization gauge detectors. In principle, however, arbitrarily low rates can be measured with the QCM since the resonant frequency of the quartz crystal continuously changes as mass accumulates on its surface. In what follows, the deposition rate is evaluated either from the average and standard deviation of the estimates output from the controller card

or by linear regression of the accumulated thickness with time.

Figure 4.2: Photograph of a quartz crystal monitor assembly. Insets: example of a double anchor (left) and a full-pad (right) electrode pattern.

4.1.3 Energy dependence

The use of a quartz crystal resonator as a particle flux monitor, as it requires the additional process of condensation, requires knowledge of the sticking probability. The sticking probability describes the fraction of atoms or molecules arriving on a surface that remain bound. Generally, this quantity depends on several surface state properties, such as the substrate material, temperature, and topology, and it also depends on the chamber pressure and varies with the energy and impact angle of condensing vapour atoms [24]. For simplicity, we assume the sticking probability is unity for the deposition of metal atoms at normal incidence onto the surface of a quartz crystal resonator by PVD in vacuum. This is motivated by several studies that have shown the likelihood for reflection only becomes significant for hyperthermal (>10 eV) impacts at glancing angles [182–184].

4.1.4 Temperature dependence

The most significant nongravimetric effect that limits high accuracy QCM measurements during the vacuum deposition of non-high-stress metals, such as Ag, is temperature [204]. The resonance frequency of an oscillating crystal has an intrinsic dependence on temperature that can introduce positive or negative error in thickness and deposition rate measurements [204–206]. A deposition cycle will normally underestimate these quantities upon heating and overestimate them upon cooling due to frequency shifts induced by changes in the sensor temperature [206,207]. To minimize temperature-dependent effects, microbalance applications often use a combination of water-cooling (to prevent large temperature changes) and low temperature coefficient AT-type resonators. These crystals, cut at a nominal angle of $35^{\circ}15'$ to the optical axis in quartz, have been widely adopted because they exhibit a relatively small frequency-temperature dependence over a wide temperature range centred around 25°C [205].

Radiative heat transfer from the source and energy transferred from adsorbed atoms can cause temperature-induced apparent mass changes during thermal evaporation processes. The main contribution comes from the resistively, or electron-beam, heated vapour source, which radiates heat energy (peak emission in the infrared) that is absorbed by the vacuum chamber walls and equipment in chamber, including the quartz crystals [207]. Unlike radiation heating, energy is also transferred to the substrate as atoms condense at its surface. An atom's kinetic energy, including the heat released upon adsorption, contributes to substrate heating [38]. For thin films of metal grown under UHV conditions by thermal evaporation, the heat released upon the adsorption of an atom is generally much larger than its incident kinetic energy

due to the atom-surface interaction potential that accelerates it towards the surface. For metals that grow in a continuous film (e.g. layer-by-layer growth), the heat released upon adsorption is usually taken to be the heat (enthalpy) of sublimation of the bulk phase of the deposit, ΔH_s , which serves as an estimate for the generalized surface binding energy of substrate atoms [208]. If energy loss is dissipated only by the excitation of lattice vibrations (an adiabatic process) [209], the average power per unit area transferred to the substrate for a given particle flux j is

$$J = (2k_B T + \Delta H_s) j, \quad (4.5)$$

which assumes the sticking coefficient is unity and takes $2k_B T$ to be the average energy per atom crossing a unit surface per second, as derived in [subsection 3.4.8](#) using Maxwellian statistics.

We circumvent time-dependent temperature changes as much as possible to mitigate errors in deposition rate data. During electron-beam evaporation, we noticed the source shutter glows red-hot and subsequently cools when opened. Since opening a previously closed shutter may cause the crystal temperature to slightly decrease, we run experiments after a cool-down period (given the absolute error in accumulated mass approaches a constant value as the crystal temperature settles) or work without shuttering action. We monitored the deposition rate to explore this effect but a much more controlled experimental investigation is needed due to instabilities in the melt pool.

In principle, changing the particle flux and/or kinetic energy of atoms that impinge on the crystal surface (e.g. via mechanical velocity selection) can also give rise to small temperature changes and produce errors in deposition rate data. To investigate

Figure 4.3: Top panel: rotation speed of the velocity selector. Middle panel: thickness and first time derivative of the thickness measured by a QCM placed in the velocity-selected beam path. Bottom panel: deposition rate measured by a second QCM placed in line-of-sight of the effusion orifice.

transient QCM behaviour, we passed a high-intensity beam of silver atoms, produced by heating the effusion cell to 1673 K, through the velocity selector. The response curve in Figure 4.3 shows how the thickness and deposition rate, detected by a QCM in the velocity-selected beam path, change with time as the rotor accelerates to a higher speed. In the acceleration interval, the deposition rate falls off sharply as transmission through the velocity selector, and therefore Ag flux reaching the crystal surface, decreases. The effect of temperature, though, is probably not appreciable since steady state is observed just after the acceleration interval, at constant flux.

4.2 Hot-filament ionization gauge

A hot-filament ionization gauge uses energetic electrons to impact-ionize atoms which are then collected at an electrode; the resulting ion current is proportional to the number density of atoms/molecules in the gauge volume. The basic principles of

operation are as follows. Electrons are thermionically emitted from a heated filament (cathode) held at a raised ground potential and then accelerated towards a cylindrical grid (anode) that is typically held at ~ 180 V. The positive filament bias establishes an electric field that impedes electron collisions with a thin collector wire, axially aligned with the grid axis, held at ground potential so that most electron paths end due to a collision with the grid. Some electrons impact-ionize atoms inside the gauge volume and the positive ions that are not captured by the collector wire on their first pass will continue to orbit in the surrounding space charge cloud of orbiting ions until they are adsorbed (or escape through the open ends of the helical grid). Assuming the electron emission current is constant and residual current due to pressure-independent processes can be ignored, the measured collector current is directly proportional to the number density of atoms in the ionizing volume.

4.2.1 Theory

The usual model that relates the measured collector current, i_c , to the number density of atoms inside the anode grid region, n , is derived as follows; see [198] for a recent review. Since multiply charged ions can contribute to the ion current, let $\sigma_k(E_e)$ be the electron-impact cross section as a function of electron energy, E_e , for the $k = \{1, 2, \dots\}$ times ionization of a particular species (e.g. beam atoms or nitrogen). Let N be the number of electrons entering the anode grid region per unit time and, for simplicity, let L and A be the length of the interaction region and the cross-sectional area of the electron ‘beam’, respectively. Target atoms are essentially motionless in the limit of a high-energy incident electron and, in terms of these basic quantities, the total number of atoms inside the ionizing volume is nLA . For a single charge state,

the number of ionizing collisions per unit time is equal to the relevant cross section multiplied by (i) the flux of electrons per unit area (N/A) and (ii) the number of scattering centers, which reduces to $NnL\sigma$. If all ions are collected and the number of secondary electrons produced by ionizing collisions is small, then the ion current resulting from gas-phase ionization processes is

$$\frac{i_+}{i_e} = nL \sum_k k\sigma_k(E_e) = nL\sigma_T(E_e), \quad (4.6)$$

where $i_e = eN$ is the electron emission current and e is the elementary charge. The total cross section, $\sigma_T(E_e)$, is recovered when the summation is performed over all charge states [210]. Since there are usually all sorts of chemical species ν that contribute to i_+ , a more general form of this equation can sum the product of n_ν and the corresponding cross section over the index ν to obtain the total ion current.

The ideal gas law is usually applied to relate this to pressure, yielding

$$\frac{i_+}{i_e} = \frac{\sigma_T(E_e)L}{k_B T} P \equiv SP, \quad (4.7)$$

where S is defined as the gauge sensitivity factor. This quantity is sensitive to any changes to the electron or ion space charge since it is related to the integral of the ionization probability over the path of an electron and varies according to the electrode potentials, chemical species, gauge geometry, and absolute temperature [211].

Three main contributors to the collector current, i_c , are shown schematically in Figure 4.4. The low pressure measuring limit of the gauge is determined by a residual current term, i_r , that arises from several pressure (or number density) independent

processes that contribute to the measured collector current, including an x-ray induced photoemission current, i_x , and current resulting from electron stimulated desorption (ESD), i_{ESD} . If the measured collector current is $i_c = i_+ + i_r$, Equation 4.7 can be written in the form

$$P = \frac{1}{S i_e} (i_c - i_r), \quad (4.8)$$

where $i_r = i_x + i_{ESD}$ is the residual current term.

Figure 4.4: (a) Multiple-pass electron trajectory that results in the ionization of an atom inside the gauge region. The secondary electron produced by the ionizing collision is omitted for clarity. (b) and (c) show two main processes that contribute to residual current.

Bremsstrahlung production can occur when energetic electrons impact with the grid or its support structure. Some of resulting x-rays may strike the collector wire and cause photoelectrons to be ejected; the resulting current, i_x , is electrically indistinguishable from the pressure-dependent ion current [212]. The desorption of neutral atoms or molecules in their ground state or an excited state, or ions that are either positively or negatively charged, can also occur when electrons electrically excite adsorbed gas on the grid surface (e.g. see [213] and [214] for reviews). Even though desorbed ions are not efficiently captured by the thin collector wire due to their high kinetic energies (i.e. several eV) and generally constitute only a small percentage of the total flux of desorbed species, positive ion emission by ESD contributes to the

collector current, which raises the low pressure limit of the gauge.

4.2.2 Detector biases

Both the efficiency of ionizing neutral atoms and the efficiency of collecting ionized atoms exhibit a velocity/energy dependence that may introduce artifacts into the measured transmission spectra. For instance, it is well-known that the ion production rate depends on the relative velocity of the colliding particles, but it is simple to show the dependence on the atomic beam velocity is negligible for thermally evaporated material since electron speeds are larger by about three to four orders of magnitude. Consider the reaction rate

$$R = n_e n_a v_r \sigma(E) \quad (4.9)$$

that describes the number of ions that form per unit second per unit volume due to ionizing collisions, where n_i is either the atom or electron number density, $v_r = |\mathbf{v}_e - \mathbf{v}_a|$ is their relative speed, and E is the collision energy, defined as the relative energy between the target atoms and the electrons [215] (see [216] for more details and relativistic corrections). If the electron flux is given by $n_e v_e A$ and $v_e \gg v_a$, this general expression reduces to Equation 4.6. This rate equation applies to fast atomic/molecular beam experiments and is often used in the study of chemical kinetics [217]. Related expressions have also been developed for electron-impact ionization cross section measurements in crossed beam experiments [210]. For such an arrangement, $E \approx m_e v_r^2 / 2 = E_e + (m_e / m_a) E_a$ in the center-of-mass system. Since the electron to atom mass ratio is $m_e / m_a \approx 200\,000^{-1}$ for Ag, it is clear the atomic beam velocity has a negligible effect on the ion production rate for the current work.

The number of ions that are captured by the thin collector also varies as a function

of energy. A simple model developed by Comsa showed the ion collection efficiency of common ionization gauges can be non-unity even for energies near 0.1 eV [218]. However, in addition to its initial kinetic energy, propagation direction, and the location where it is created, the probability that an ion will be captured once it has been created depends on many other factors that are difficult to model, such as the precise geometry of the gauge and the electric potential, which is influenced by local space charge phenomena. It is necessary to account for space charge effects since the presence of charged particles modifies the potential field, which in turn modifies charged particle trajectories [219]. A recent study by Richard *et al.* accounted for these effects in simulations that showed the collection efficiency decreases with decreasing emission current [219]. Although simulations are still needed to model the energy dependence, the ion collection efficiency is presumably close to unity for this work since thermal energies are small in comparison to an ion's gain in kinetic energy as it travels towards the collector wire (several tens of eV depending on the position where it is created and the accelerating potential).

4.2.3 Engineering design

We removed a miniature dual filament ionization gauge from its housing and positioned it above the velocity selector using a custom design (see Figure 4.5). Kapton-insulated silver-plated copper wires were crimped at one end to the electrical outputs of a power feedthrough and to the gauge at the other end. The assembly was in turn mounted on a linear translator to position the gauge above the spindle. The gauge had a conventional style, equipped with a yttria-coated iridium filament, a tantalum grid, and a tungsten ion collector. The choice of cathode material, as it relates to

outgassing, was an important consideration. In this work, iridium filaments are the best choice because they are low-temperature electron emitters and therefore operate at lower temperatures compared to uncoated tungsten filaments [220].

Under normal operating conditions (see subsection 4.2.6), the filament to ground voltage was set to 32 V and ~ 2 V was applied across the filament, resulting in ~ 2 A of current flow. The grid voltage was kept constant at a 180 V potential and the electron emission current and the collector current were measured using a multimeter and a picoammeter, respectively.

We also designed a grounded metal envelope to surround the entire electrode assembly. The envelope was equipped with two clearance holes, covered by a conductive mesh (0.46 fractional open area), that were axially aligned with the beam axis to allow atoms to enter and exit. Heavy shielding was required to maintain a stable electrical environment for electron and ion trajectories; it served to block particulates and shield the gauge from electromagnetic interference and charged particles in the vacuum chamber.

Figure 4.5: (a) Photograph and (b) drawing of the ionization gauge assembly.

4.2.4 Operation and testing

Ionization efficiency curves are obtained by plotting i_c/i_e as a function of electron energy, which is roughly determined by the anode-to-cathode voltage. With reference to the schematic shown in [Figure 4.6](#), we developed a procedure to measure this dependency at a different chamber pressures and operating potentials in order to determine the optimal operating conditions of our detector. We used a variable leak valve to vary the chamber pressure and monitored the composition of residual gases using mass spectrometry.

Figure 4.6: Electrical circuit of a hot-filament ionization gauge.

The ionization efficiency curve shown in [Figure 4.7a](#) was acquired at a high partial pressure of N_2 and a moderate to low emission current (about 0.1 mA for grid potentials in the range of 180 V). The filament to ground voltage was set to 32.000 V and a 1.960 V potential was applied across the filament, which resulted in 2.092 A of current flow at an average chamber pressure of 8.1×10^{-7} Torr. The grid voltage was varied from 50 V to 210 V in 2 V increments and the electron emission current and

collector current were measured using a multimeter and a picoammeter, respectively. The current ratio was estimated from the time average $\langle i_c/i_e \rangle$ over a 10 s measurement period, after which the voltage was incremented. A time delay was needed between measurement periods to achieve a steady state.

Figure 4.7: (a) Ionization efficiency as a function of electron energy at a raised chamber pressure consisting mostly of N_2 . The average and standard deviation of three experiments is shown in blue. (b) RGA spectrum acquired just before the measurements reported in (a).

The experimental results agree well with the binary-encounter-Bethe theory for the total ionization cross section of a target by electron impact [221]. Using the molecular orbital constants from NIST [222], the total cross section was evaluated as a weighted sum of the cross section of each chemical species in the chamber. The weights were taken from composition estimates, as determined from the residual gas analyzer (RGA) spectrum shown in Figure 4.7b.

4.2.5 Ionization efficiency of Ag

The single-ionization cross section of Ag was measured by Freund *et al.* using the crossed-beams technique [223]. The spectrum peaks around 45 eV and then slowly decreases for increasing electron energy. At high kinetic energies, double and triple

ionization also contribute to the total ionization yield and, therefore, the collector current. For example, at 100 eV, near the peak of the double ionization cross section, the double-to-single ratio is about 0.1 [223]. However, a later study published by Bartlett *et al.* argued that their results were likely affected by a large population of metastable states [224]. Our attempts to measure the ionization efficiency of Ag were unsuccessful due to a dominating background signal from residual gas ionization. In principle though, once this distribution is established for a particular detector, the accelerating potential can be optimized to maximize ionization yield and possibly discriminate against residual gases.

4.2.6 Phase sensitive detection

The ionization gauge has the advantage that it can be applied in a phase-sensitive detection scheme to extract a modulated signal, such as the ion current resulting from a chopped atomic/molecular beam, from the DC noise produced by residual gas ionization [225]. In this work, the transmitted beam intensity should change with time in a well-defined way since the beam is periodically interrupted as the velocity selector rotates due to the finite width of the helical channels. As a corollary, it follows that the collector current should be modulated as well.

As a starting point, we made an attempt to resolve the frequency spectrum of the collector current, which should have a fundamental at $f_0 = N_c f$, where N_c is the number of helical channels and f is the rotation frequency. The collector current was passed through a transimpedance amplifier (gain of 10^7 V A^{-1} , $\pm 1\%$ accuracy, bandwidth from DC to 120 kHz) and the output voltage was recorded at a 250 kS s^{-1} sampling rate. We did not observe an appreciable peak at f_0 or any of its harmonics.

To support this observation, we note that the beam intensity is only weakly modulated for large detectors due to transmission contributions through multiple channels. In principle, phase-sensitive detection can still be achieved with the existing setup if the entrance to the ionizing volume on the electrode shield is replaced with a hole that is smaller than the size of a helical channel.

In preparation for these measurements, we designed and tested an optical encoder, mounted outside vacuum to a viewport, to measure the rotation frequency of the helical channels. The source was a collimated 1 mW, 635 nm laser diode module mounted on an adjustable stage. We adjusted its intensity using a mounted absorptive neutral density filter and used a ring-actuated iris diaphragm to manipulate the aperture size of the beam. A quadrant photodiode array measured the intensity of light reflected from the groove of a helical channel. The reflected laser light was first focused using an achromatic doublet (75 mm focal length) and then isolated from ambient light using a premium bandpass filter with a centre wavelength of 633 nm and a full-width at half-maximum of 5 nm. The lens and the filter were mounted to a threaded kinematic cage mount using a slotted lens tube and custom components were used to secure the silicon photodiode amplifier module to the cage mount. We also designed additional circuitry so that a transistor-transistor logic voltage output could serve as the reference signal to a lock-in amplifier.

4.3 Experimental determination of $T(\omega)$

A schematic of the experimental setup is shown in [Figure 4.8](#). The core components of the apparatus are the vapour source, the detectors, and the rotating slotted cylinder velocity selector used to selectively separate and transmit atoms with a chosen

velocity. In keeping with [section 3.3](#), the velocity selector transmission function is given by

$$T(\omega) = \begin{cases} \int_0^\infty f(v)\tau(v,\omega)dv & \text{for a density-sensitive detector,} \\ \int_0^\infty \tilde{f}(v)\tau(v,\omega)dv & \text{for a flux-sensitive detector,} \end{cases} \quad (4.10)$$

where $f(v)$ and $\tilde{f}(v)$ are the normalized speed and flux distributions of the incident beam and $\tau(v,\omega)$ is the probability of transmission through a selector rotating at ω . This section relates the detector output signals to $T(\omega)$ assuming the beam is collisionless and that the measurement time scale is large compared to the modulation time scale resulting from the rotation of the velocity selector.

Figure 4.8: Experimental setup for electron-beam evaporation experiments.

4.3.1 QCM measurements

The deposition process is not entirely stable; small variations in the temperature of the melt cause deposition rate fluctuations that vary both in magnitude and frequency. For example, the process control loop used to supply power to the heater of the effusion cell exhibits oscillations that affect the deposition rate. During electron-beam heating, the top of the rod forms a molten metal pool that steadily recedes into the crucible as material evaporates. To reduce the influence on deposition rate, we advance the rod in discrete increments at regular time intervals using a stepper motor. Small deposition rate variations do not appreciably affect transmission measurements when the time-scale of the fluctuations is much shorter than the measurement time. We introduce a method to compensate slow (i.e. long time scale) fluctuations.

Consider an on-axis QCM, aligned with the source axis, with a surface normal parallel to the incoming vapour direction. If the vapour is filtered by a velocity selector, the differential flux that arrives at the sensor will be weighted by the fraction $\tau(v, \omega)$ of particles that escape the selector. By modifying [Equation 2.13](#), for example, the model to predict the deposition rate, R , becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 R &= \frac{mnA}{4\pi r^2 \rho} \int_0^\infty v f(v) \tau(v, \omega) dv, \\
 &= \frac{mnA \langle v \rangle}{4\pi r^2 \rho} \int_0^\infty \tilde{f}(v) \tau(v, \omega) dv, \\
 &= R_0 T(\omega),
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

where $\langle v \rangle$ is the first moment of $f(v)$ and m , n , A , r , and ρ are defined previously. We identify R_0 as the hypothetical rate that would be measured without velocity selection. This rate can be estimated experimentally using a second oscillator that has

an unobstructed view of the source since its measurement, R_d , is directly proportional to R_0 . If $R_0 \equiv \epsilon R_d$, the velocity-selected deposition rate is

$$R \approx \epsilon R_d T(\omega), \quad (4.12)$$

which is approximately true for small variations in the temperature/deposition rate.

In principle, ϵ can be estimated during either (i) low-rate electron-beam evaporation or (ii) low-temperature effusion from a non-ideal orifice assuming the angular distribution is cosine or corrected according to the Clausing model [104, 123, 226]. For example, consider the rate at which particles impinge on a substrate that is separated from an effusion orifice by a distance r (see chapter 2). If ϕ and β are defined to be the emission angle and the incidence angle, respectively, then the deposition rate ratio, R_i/R_j , of two detectors that are each within a direct line-of-sight of the orifice is

$$\epsilon = \frac{R_i}{R_j} = \frac{\cos(\phi_i) \cos(\beta_i)}{\cos(\phi_j) \cos(\beta_j)} \cdot \frac{C_0(\phi_i, l/d)}{C_0(\phi_j, l/d)} \cdot \left(\frac{r_j}{r_i}\right)^2, \quad (4.13)$$

where l and d are the length and the diameter of the aperture and $C_0(\phi, l/d)$ is Clausing's correction factor, which simplifies to unity for an infinitesimally thin orifice.

Since the angular distribution, and therefore ϵ , is not well-known for the present experiments (see subsection 5.1.1), we make a proportional comparison $T(\omega) \propto R/R_d$ between theory and experiment.

4.3.2 Ionization gauge measurements

In addition to deposition rate variations, transmission measurements using an ionization gauge can be distorted due to changes in the chamber pressure. The residual

gas in vacuum systems generally consists of air and condensable vapours, such as water that desorbs from the internal surfaces. Heating from the source stimulates outgassing, which tends to cause systematic pressure variations throughout an experiment. We also note that the chamber pressure deteriorates when the velocity selector rotates. This was investigated using a RGA that acquired mass spectra for the spindle in its idle position and when rotating at 200 rad s^{-1} . The spectrum shown in [Figure 4.9a](#) contains a peak at 19 u, which likely corresponds to fluorine and may be evidence of outgassing from the bearings since the grease is a perfluorinated polyether compound. It is also known that outgassing due to the mechanical motion of rotary components in UHV, stimulated by the friction between stainless steel surfaces, can eject carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen into vacuum, which can then combine to form CO, CO₂, CH₄, and heavier hydrocarbons [[227](#), [228](#)]. This effect has been observed for the rotary systems implemented by other research groups [[227](#)] and is consistent with the presence of new peaks at 30 u and 44 u.

The particle number density, n , in the gauge volume of an on-axis detector has contributions from both velocity-selected beam atoms and residual gases. Following the work presented in [subsection 4.2.1](#), if the residual current term due to pressure-independent processes is negligible, the measured collector current is

$$\frac{i_c}{i_e} = L \left(\sigma_b(E_e)n_0T(\omega) + \sum_{\nu} \sigma_{\nu}(E_e)n_{\nu} \right), \quad (4.14)$$

where n_0 is the unfiltered number density of beam atoms in the gauge volume and the sum over the partial number densities n_{ν} determines the background due to residual gas ionization. As before, L is defined to be the length of the ionizing volume and $\sigma_i(E_e)$ is the total electron-impact ionization cross section of either the beam atoms

($i = b$) or the residual gas species indexed by ν .

Figure 4.9: (a) Composition of residual gas in the vacuum chamber for different rotor speeds. (b) i_c/i_e and P_r are linearly dependent as a function of ω .

We isolated the signal from the atomic beam by subtracting the background due to residual gas ionization. This contribution was estimated using a second ionization gauge that was shrouded from deposition source. This method can be applied because a linear transformation relates the outputs of both gauges, independent of source temperature and rotor speed. To show this, we heated the effusion cell but kept the source shutter closed. We determined that i_c/i_e and the nitrogen-equivalent pressure output, P_r , from the shrouded gauge are related according to $i_c/i_e = s(P_r - P_0)$, where s is a sensitivity factor and P_0 is a pressure offset term. This dependence is shown in Figure 4.9b as a function of rotation speed. While variations in n_0 can be compensated for using a third gauge, at present we compare theory with experiment according to $T(\omega) \propto (i_c/i_e - sP_r)$, which assumes the vapour flow occurs under steady-state conditions.

Chapter 5

Experimental speed distribution measurements

We relied on effusion and electron-beam physical vapour deposition processes to deposit high purity Ag into vacuum. The experimental apparatus and control system that we developed measured the speed distribution of the atomic vapour by means of mechanical velocity selection and density- and flux-based detection techniques. The theoretical and experimental methods used in this study are described in previous chapters. In this chapter, I present a number of speed distribution measurements obtained under a variety of experimental conditions.

5.1 Effusion experiments

We used a high temperature effusion cell (HTEC) equipped with a conical pBN crucible to conduct benchmark experiments. The crucible was covered with a removable

1.02 ± 0.05 mm thick lid that had a single right-circular cylindrical channel measuring 1.52 ± 0.05 mm in diameter. The source material loaded into the crucible were $>99.99\%$ pure 3 mm Ag shot pellets from Cerac. Parts per million (ppm) impurity levels were specified to be 71 for Cu, 12 for Sb, 5 for Pb, and 3 for Ni, measured using spectrographic analysis by the manufacturer. All other impurities had levels ≤ 2 ppm. To reduce beam contamination, the cell was degassed at a temperature between 1200 K and 1600 K under high vacuum (HV) prior to deposition.

5.1.1 Mass evaporation rate

As a first step towards full-scale experiments, we varied the effusion-cell temperature to compare temperature-dependent deposition rate measurements with theory. The experimental data shown in [Figure 5.1a](#) was measured using an off-axis quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) placed in direct line-of-sight of the source. The results for increasing temperature agree with the Clausing-corrected Hertz-Knudsen (HK) relation (see [Equation 2.13](#)) within about $\pm 1\sigma$ without the use of any fit parameters. The deposition rate was also measured simultaneously by a second QCM positioned above the velocity selector (see [Figure 5.1b](#)). Rotating the velocity selector at 4.86 rad s^{-1} maximized the rate and by extension its transmission function, $T(\omega)$.

To simplify the analysis (see [section 4.3](#)), we assume transmission near its peak maximum is temperature-independent (see inset). The best-fit value $T(\omega = 4.86 \text{ rad s}^{-1}) = 0.35 \pm 0.01$ yields excellent agreement between theory and velocity-selected deposition rate data. Within the framework of temperature-independent transmission, we also show that the ratio of the two rates follows the theoretical prediction of [Equation 4.12](#) (bottom panel in [Figure 5.1b](#)).

Figure 5.1: Temperature-dependent deposition rate measurements are compared with theory. The film thickness was monitored for 200 s, with the rate calculated from the slope of the best-fit line, at 25 K intervals. Measurements with (a) an off-axis QCM placed in direct line-of-sight of the orifice ($r_d = 45.2 \pm 1.0$ cm, $\phi_d = \beta_d = 5 \pm 2^\circ$), and (b) an on-axis QCM placed above the velocity selector ($r = 53.9 \pm 1.0$ cm, $\phi = \beta = 0 \pm 2^\circ$).

Although intense atomic/molecular beams are preferred based on signal-to-noise ratio considerations, it is well-known that high oven temperatures can bring about departures from known effusive flow behaviour. In the present experiment, the Knudsen number (Kn) varied from 41 to 0.18 in the temperature range of our measurements, reaching one around 1500 K. The agreement between theory and experiment over such a wide range is therefore surprising, but perhaps fortuitous. While it is difficult to decide on the exact effusive behaviour in this situation, it is very unlikely that transport occurs under conditions in which gas-phase collisions can be considered negligible. As shown in Figure 5.1a, the deposition rate exhibited hysteresis upon thermal cycling. The hysteresis presumably arises because the analysis considers an isothermal enclosure at steady state, while the use of a rapid warm-up and cool-down procedure caused the oven assembly to lag the indicated temperature. An examination of the data shows measurements on the descending branch – and more importantly the deposition rate averaged over 3.5 h between heating and cooling cycles – exceed the

predictions of the isothermal effusion formula. These departures are consistent with known transition-region behaviour. Many studies have shown that the probability of effusion in the near-forward direction increases with decreasing Kn (with long channels exhibiting minima) [141–143, 229, 230]. Although the exact flow behaviour here is obscured by the hysteresis, the important flow phenomena are (i) attenuation and (ii) drift. Along the centreline, the beam intensity is both attenuated by collisions in the gas flow along the length of the channel and enhanced by development of a drift velocity (e.g. see previous discussions on preferential scattering).

Figure 5.2: Photographs of the effusion cell under different experimental conditions. (a) Droplets are not observed at low temperature. (b) Small metal droplets are observed on the outer surface of the lid and on the cell walls near the exit after the heating cycle.

Another phenomenon linked to the effusion process is spitting, or the ejection of metal droplets from the melt inside the oven. Possible causes for spitting include (i) convection flows in the melt, (ii) the liberation of trapped gases, and (iii) droplets forming on the inner surfaces of the cell that drop/roll back into the melt [231]. In our case, spitting from the orifice was visible by eye at an onset temperature of about 1550 K. The two images in Figure 5.2 show a large number of droplets just outside the oven after the heating cycle. At present, how these droplets contribute to the deposition rate, if at all, is unknown.

Other considerations include phenomena like surface diffusion and bulk surface flow (creeping) along either the orifice or cell walls. Although these effects (introduced in [chapter 2](#)) are also known to enhance the emission rate, we expect they have a limited contribution to the total emission for the chosen orifice geometry and cell material. From the analysis of Winterbottom and Hirth, the use of a relatively large effusion orifice (i.e. 1.5 mm diameter, 1.0 mm length) reduces the relative surface-diffusion contribution [[146](#)]. Other researchers have also shown that the poor wettability of pBN crucibles by most liquid metals prevents creeping [[151, 232](#)].

5.1.2 Detector alignment

We have run a number of speed distribution experiments with the non-ideal orifice, mostly under high-temperature conditions to reduce data acquisition time. Even though the effect of gas-phase collisions becomes relevant at high temperature, these experiments offered a quick means to investigate how the detector position affects the transmission spectrum. I described a simple method to model this effect in [subsection 3.3.4](#) that replaces the pitch angle of the helical channels with an effective value, ϕ_e . To examine this effect, we measured a collection of transmission spectra at different detector positions and temperatures.

Transmission spectra for two different detector positions are plotted in [Figure 5.3a](#). The detector started above the edge of the velocity selector (red curve), nearly in direct line-of-sight of the source, and was then moved towards the cylinder axis by about 10 mm on a 45° to 60° angle to the tangential axis (blue curve) using a linear translation stage. The peak in transmission at a negative rotation speed suggests the handedness of the velocity selector inverts along this path. To take into

account $\phi_e \rightarrow -|\phi_e|$, the transmission function is reflected about the y -axis. We observed a negligible change in ϕ_e when fitting the data to the divergent beam model with/without a constant offset term. The observed agreement between theory and experiment indicates that the handedness inversion of the helical velocity selector is possible and reversible by detector displacement.

Figure 5.3: (a) QCM transmission spectra measured for different detector positions at 1623 K. The chamber pressure was below $\sim 10^{-6}$ Torr. The divergent beam model is fit to the data with a scaling amplitude and effective pitch angle (dashed) and a constant offset (solid). (b) A collection of ϕ_e are plotted as a function of QCM displacement for experiments at different temperatures.

Figure 5.3b fits the model introduced in subsection 3.3.4 to the collection of ϕ_e obtained from the transmission spectra for different detector positions and temperatures. The best-fit values are consistent with our understanding of the experiment geometry. We also note that the beam axis is aligned with the velocity selector axis when $\phi_e = \phi = 3^\circ$, which occurs when the detector is in view of the source (shown by extrapolation). We shifted the sensor to optimize its alignment, but a slight bend in its tubing introduced a nonlinearity (data not shown) due to the breakdown of the assumption $y = d \cos(\theta)$. Ultimately, we reverted to a less-bent arrangement to minimize this nonlinearity, thereby avoiding the increased sensitivity to displacement.

5.1.3 QCM measurements

This section reports speed distribution measurements for Ag effusing from a non-ideal orifice. The detection method, described in previous chapters, involved three main components:

- (i) a mechanical velocity selector,
- (ii) an on-axis QCM mounted 53.9 ± 1.0 cm above the source, and
- (iii) an off-axis QCM placed at a $5 \pm 2^\circ$ angle of emission and incidence, 45.2 ± 1.0 cm from the orifice.

The deposition rate at each rotation speed was calculated by linear regression of the accumulated thickness over a 135 s interval. To compensate for oscillations in thickness occurring on the measurement timescale, we repeated each experiment five times and report the average. Collectively, the experiments covered a wide range of temperatures and were performed one after another to ensure similar conditions. Similar to previous studies, we find the best agreement with theory when the oven temperature was kept as low as practically possible and observe what might be an excess of high-speed atoms at high temperatures.

The results were analyzed using two models discussed previously: (i) the transmission model for divergent beams, as derived for a point source, and (ii) the weighted divergent beam model for extended sources. We compared both models with experimental data using amplitude scaling determined from curve fitting. Amplitude correction is useful since a number of factors probably influence the relationship between on- and off-axis deposition rates comprised in [Equation 4.12](#). The divergent beam curve fit model also estimated effective values for the angular spread, α_e , and

the pitch angle, ϕ_e . The second model simulated weighting factors assuming the cosine emission law applied at each infinitesimal element of area on a planar emitting surface. Due to computational complexity, the analysis in this case relied on template-matching in the deemed parameter space.

Low temperature

We measured the speed distribution in a low-intensity beam of silver atoms, produced by an oven at 1448 K. Our first consideration is the QCM mounted in line-of-sight to the effusion orifice. Averaging the off-axis deposition rate measurements over the series of experiments yields $\langle R_d \rangle = 0.046 \pm 0.011 \text{ \AA s}^{-1}$. This result is in excellent agreement with the predicted flux, $0.050 \pm 0.004 \text{ \AA s}^{-1}$, without the use of adjustable parameters. The prediction follows from [Equation 2.13](#), with the error calculated by propagating uncertainty in the dimensions of the orifice and the position of the detector relative to the source. The small difference between theory and experiment indicates that factors such as spitting (which was not observable by eye) and surface diffusion did not appreciably contribute to the effusive flow.

[Figure 5.4a](#) compares velocity selector transmission measurements, R/R_d , with theory. The experimental results and the divergent beam model are in excellent agreement for the best-fit parameters $\phi_e = 0.43 \pm 0.05^\circ$ and $\alpha_e = 0.35 \pm 0.02^\circ$. The effective pitch angle is expected from the high-temperature alignment experiment presented earlier, based on positioning information from the translation stage. The effective angular spread is also consistent with simulated results presented in [section 3.4](#). The weighted divergent beam model also relied on two free parameters, in this case the relative Δx and Δy positions of the detector. Effective values for ϕ_e and

(b) Detector position

(c) rms speeds

Figure 5.4: (a) Low-temperature QCM transmission spectrum. Experiment is compared with the divergent beam model for point sources and the weighted divergent beam model for extended sources. (b) Experimental data is compared with the template bank to estimate the detector position. (c) R/R_d is plotted as a function of the rms speed of the transmitted atoms.

α_e were not needed since Δx and Δy determine ϕ_e and the dependence on α_e is lifted by the weighting factors described earlier. A contour map of the reduced χ^2 statistic is shown in Figure 5.4b that compares a library of expected spectra, generated by systematically varying the position parameters, with the observed data. Using the χ^2 minimization approach outlined in section 3.4.7, we estimate the QCM position was just off-centre, displaced by $\Delta x = 3.0 \pm 0.4$ mm and $\Delta y = -5.65 \pm 0.10$ mm. The

corresponding transmission function is in excellent agreement with the experimental results, showing no appreciable difference from the best-fitting curve obtained for the divergent beam model. In fact, the effective pitch angle estimated from Equation 3.42 for the off-centre detector position is $0.43 \pm 0.05^\circ$, which is equal to the value obtained with the first model. The similarity of the models is not surprising since the small source, placed far away from the detector, is well approximated by a point.

Figure 5.4c plots R/R_d as a function of rms speed, $\langle v^2 \rangle^{1/2}$, calculated using the best-fit position parameters. The agreement between the experimental results and the theoretical predictions is excellent. The shape of the distribution follows from the analysis presented in subsection 3.3.3, which shows $\langle v^2 \rangle^{1/2}$ is not monotonic with ω when beam divergence is taken into account. As a result, the spindle design is ideally-suited for high-speed filtering at $\pm|\omega|$, with low-speed filtering limited by its low resolution.

High temperature

We also carried out speed distribution experiments at high-temperature, beyond the expected limit for molecular flow. The data was compared with theory using the effective pitch angle and detector position determined at low temperature. It was convenient to use these parameters since no changes were made to the alignment, either by moving the source or detector relative to the velocity selector, between experiments. This choice helped reduce the number of free parameters, but was not essential for the subsequent analysis¹.

Figure 5.5a compares experimental measurements of the transmission distribution,

¹Without this constraint, we found best-fit values for ϕ_e in $\pm 1\sigma$ agreement with $0.43 \pm 0.05^\circ$ for the three experiments reported here, with no significant change in the overall fit quality (or best-fit amplitude or effective angular spread).

acquired at 1498 K, with theory. The divergent beam model provides a good fit to the data for $\alpha_e = 0.47 \pm 0.01^\circ$, which exceeds its predicted value. The analysis also considers the weighted divergent beam model. Since α_e correlates with the size of the source, we treated its radius as a free parameter. A contour map of the reduced χ^2 statistic, shown in Figure 5.5b, compares a library of spectra with the data. By minimizing the statistic, we obtained a transmission distribution that also shows good agreement with experiment. The estimated apparent source radius is 4.72 ± 0.04 mm, which exceeds the orifice radius by more than a factor of 6. The next section discusses possible reasons for the increase.

Figure 5.5: (a) QCM transmission spectrum at 1498 K. Experimental measurements are compared to divergent beam and weighted divergent beam models. (b) Contour map of the reduced χ^2 statistic, plotted as a function of amplitude and source radius.

Results for speed distribution experiments at 1573 and 1673 K are shown in Figure 5.6. The agreement between theory and experiment is similar to that found at 1498 K. As discussed previously, the models rely on amplitude scaling and we either find (i) a best-fit value for α_e equal to $0.50 \pm 0.01^\circ$ or $0.48 \pm 0.01^\circ$, or (ii) an apparent source radius that exceeds the orifice radius by a factor of 6 or 7. These values are similar to those obtained at 1498 K.

Figure 5.6: Experimental measurements of the transmission distribution at (a) 1573 K and (b) 1673 K are compared with theory.

The bottom panels of the transmission spectra plot the residuals. In each case, the residuals systematically depart from zero, displaying similar oscillatory behaviour. Although this trend likely indicates a departure from the model, there is no statistically significant difference between the expected and observed results at 1498, 1573, or 1673 K.

Discussion

Effusion studies have experimentally demonstrated that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution describes the velocities of a gas in thermal equilibrium [48, 51, 233].

The present study measured the speed distribution in a silver atomic beam produced by an effusing orifice using a mechanical velocity selector coupled with quartz crystal resonators. The speed distribution data at $\text{Kn} = 2.2$ shows excellent agreement with theoretical predictions, in accordance with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Analysis of secondary QCM data shows the average deposition rate agrees with theory, corrected for orifice length on the basis of free molecular flow and diffuse

boundary conditions, without the use of adjustable parameters. These findings offer key insights into the effusion process. Several effects that can perturb the velocity distribution, such as (i) surface diffusion and orifice creep, (ii) gas-phase collisions occurring in the effusing gas, and (iii) specular reflection occurring on the orifice walls, appear to be insignificant based on the observed agreement.

Monte-Carlo calculations in the limiting case of a free molecular flow with the diffuse reflection boundary condition showed surface emissions make up roughly half of the total flux leaving the orifice. Despite the high contribution, flux direct from the gas phase inside the oven dominates the surface emission component at small angles of emission. Since the primary detector is placed along the central beam axis, the only significant contribution to experimental speed distribution measurements is gas emerging directly from the oven.

Small departures from known molecular effusion behaviour occurred at 1498 K (corresponding to $\text{Kn} = 1.1$) that became more pronounced at higher oven temperatures. Although the low resolution velocity selector makes it difficult to decide on specific aspects of the departures, a principle feature that we observe is an apparent excess in the transmission spectra at high rotation speeds. Similar departures have been reported by Miller and Kusch, who observed a deficiency of slow atoms and an excess of fast atoms [48]. Non-Maxwellian velocity distributions are well documented and usually caused by intrabeam or beam-gas scattering [46, 48, 50]. We have previously shown that the effects from beam-gas scattering may be neglected in the reported range of chamber pressures. The most important process should be the collisions occurring within the channel, which have a beam-hardening effect due to the preferential attenuation of low-energy particles [157, 234, 235].

Figure 5.7: Temperature dependence of the amplitude. Amplitudes obtained by curve-fitting experimental speed distribution measurements are plotted in red. The curve shown in blue is calculated using data from the deposition rate experiment reported earlier.

The best-fit parameters also provide evidence of this effect. Data fitting was accomplished on the basis of least-squares reduction using two parameters. In the point source approximation the angular spread of the beam exceeds prediction and the amplitude scaling is non-unity. Larger values for α_e (or r_s) could be caused by (i) the formation of a collision-induced virtual vapour source at the exit of the channel or (ii) direct evaporation at the outer surfaces of the effusion cell due to spitting. Calculated amplitudes are plotted in [Figure 5.7](#) as a function of oven temperature. The results are quantitatively similar to the distribution of deposition rate ratios discussed earlier, which decrease with temperature. This behaviour occurs due to an overestimate of the rate that would be measured without velocity selection, calculated using off-axis measurements and the cosine law of emission.

Off-axis deposition rate measurements, summarized in [Table 5.1](#), deviate from theory at high temperatures. Enhanced effusion in the near-forward direction is expected due to the effect of gas-phase collisions, and could also be related to the occurrence of spitting to some extent. Such behaviour is in contrast to the measurement taken

Table 5.1: Average off-axis deposition rate as a function of temperature.

Temperature [K]	Knuden number	$\langle R_d \rangle$ [$\text{\AA}/\text{s}$]	
		Measured	Expected
1448	2.2	0.046 ± 0.011	0.050 ± 0.004
1498	1.1	0.144 ± 0.006	0.10 ± 0.01
1573	0.43	0.340 ± 0.004	0.28 ± 0.02
1673	0.14	0.71 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.08

at 1673 K, which is less than the expected value. While uncertainty could account for the difference, the work of Wahlbeck *et al.* offers another possibility [50, 143]. They observed similar fluctuations behaviour that they attributed to specular reflection. Experimental measurements of the angular distribution of the atomic beam at high temperature could provide new insight and a better understanding of the effusion process.

5.1.4 Ionization gauge measurements

The simultaneous use of multiple detection methods offers a powerful tool for understanding effusion and evaporation processes. We designed an experiment that simultaneously measured the speed distribution in a silver atomic beam, produced with the effusion source at 1623 K, using a QCM and hot-filament ionization gauge. The unique feature of the apparatus is the flow-through ionization gauge, positioned directly below the QCM surface. The results of this study, however, are limited to a single experiment that was performed using an early velocity selector prototype before alignment calibration.

Figure 5.8: The transmission function is calculated from the ionization gauge signals i_c and i_e that are plotted in (a) as a function of time. (b) The chamber pressure is subtracted from the current ratio using different sensitivity factors. (c) The transmission function is plotted and compared with velocity-selected QCM measurements.

The raw emission current (i_e) and collector current (i_c) signals are plotted in Figure 5.8a. Using the same procedure discussed previously, data is only taken while the spindle rotates at a constant speed ω_i . As shown in the inset, a measurement delay is introduced while the speed is incremented to ω_{i+1} . The chamber pressure was monitored using a secondary gauge and subtracted from the current ratio according to $i_c/i_e - sP_r$, where s is a sensitivity factor. The background-corrected signal

is plotted in [Figure 5.8b](#); each step in the distribution provides a measure of transmission at a particular rotation speed, ω_i . The transmission distribution is therefore retrieved from the time average $\langle (i_c/i_e - sP_r)(t) \rangle$, which is shown in [Figure 5.8b](#) for two sensitivity factors. Average values for $s = 8.7 \text{ Torr}^{-1}$ are plotted in [Figure 5.8c](#) and compared with velocity-selected deposition rate data. As indicated, consistent fluctuations in the transmission spectra suggest both signals respond to changes in the same physical phenomena, that is a variation in particle flux/density induced by temperature, for example. This observation demonstrates the efficacy of acquiring simultaneous measurements from two independent modalities, and the potential for yielding high-precision data.

A comparison with theory is not possible without a method to correct for variations in particle number density. As implemented for QCM-based detection experiments, this could be achieved with an additional ionization gauge placed in direct line-of-sight of the source. With the current apparatus, an alternative method could be to average repeated measurements. Repeated measurements with and without the ionization gauge turned on could also provide information on the amount of vapour that is collected by the ionization gauge, which is likely a small percentage.

5.2 Open effusion cell experiments

We also measured the speed distribution with an open effusion cell, operated without a lid. The experiments relied on QCM-based detection using the same experimental setup and procedures described in [subsection 5.1.3](#). Such experiments may be useful to understanding evaporation. During the related process of effusion, atoms released by the surface undergo gas-phase collisions and adsorption/desorption events on the

isothermal walls of the oven before escaping through a small opening into vacuum. In contrast, at a sufficiently low temperature in an open-cell configuration, atoms released by the evaporant can travel directly to a detector, without collisions. This allows for a direct measurement of the speed distribution of evaporated atoms, which can provide useful information on the mechanism for evaporation.

Shown in [Figure 5.9a](#) for Ag at 1373 K, the measured off-axis deposition rate consistently decreased throughout the current experiments. This requires consideration since temperature control is essential for reliable measurements of the speed distribution. In modelling an open conical cell, we found that temperature regulation does not produce a constant particle flux since the surface area of the melt decreases with time as material evaporates. To demonstrate this effect consider an expression for the time-varying mass inside the crucible,

$$m(t) = m_i - \Gamma t, \quad (5.1)$$

where m_i is the initial mass and Γ is the mass evaporation rate, which is taken to follow [Equation 2.7](#) and directly proportional to the area of the source. A simple relation between mass and the source radius, r , is $m/\rho = \pi r^3/(3 \tan(\nu/2))$, where ρ is the density of the evaporant and ν is the opening angle of a right circular cone. Upon substitution, numerical methods can be used to solve [Equation 5.1](#) for r at time t given an initial value for the source radius. For comparison with experiment, we determined $r(t)$ for an initial radius of 4.4 mm given $\nu = 10.0^\circ$, the opening angle of the pBN crucible, and then calculated the time-dependent deposition rate using [Equation 2.15](#). We find good agreement between experiment and theory for a rate-dependent beaming exponent of $n = 2.2$ determined from curve fitting². Given

the model applies at constant temperature, the observed agreement supports the reliability of such experiments.

Figure 5.9: (a) A comparison of experimental and theoretical deposition rates as a function of time. (b) Low-temperature open effusion cell transmission measurements are compared with the point source model for thermal beams.

The examination of the speed distribution considered Ag heated to 1273 K in an open cell. As shown in Figure 5.9b, the point source model for thermal beams is in good agreement with experimental measurements of the transmission distribution. The best-fit effective pitch angle, ϕ_e , is large in comparison to results from previous effusion experiments, likely because the source-to-detector alignment changed slightly after removing the lid. The best-fit value for α_e , the effective divergence or spread of the beam, was determined to be $0.62 \pm 0.01^\circ$. Rather than previous treatments based on the weighted divergent beam model, formulated for a cosine emitter, here we used off-axis deposition rate measurements to relate this value to the size of the source. To obtain an average rate of 0.18\AA s^{-1} , we calculated a radius between 5.2 and 6.5 mm for beaming exponents between $n = 2.2$ and $n = 1.0$. Similar to

²Reasonable agreement is also obtained for $n = 1.0$ assuming the initial radius is 5.5 mm, which is larger than the value measured outside vacuum.

high-temperature effusion experiments, the need for either a beaming exponent or larger source radius supports the occurrence of collisions [122, 152]. Evidence also comes from the residual distribution, which exhibits a discernible oscillatory pattern analogous to those plotted in Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6. Thus, it may be necessary to reduce the source temperature to avoid thermalization via collisions above the surface and yield information on the speed distribution of evaporated atoms. This is possible with the current apparatus given the results of our low-temperature effusion study.

5.3 Electron-beam evaporation experiments

Electron-beam heating is an important physical vapour deposition technique because of its ability to evaporate virtually any material with little contamination from surrounding components. Different mechanisms govern the evaporation process at different electron-beam powers or source temperatures. At high temperature, departures from the Maxwellian distribution have been observed and broadly result from collision processes above the vapour source [103–106, 159]. At low temperature when the particle number density above the surface is sufficiently small, collisions between particles are rare and the vapour cloud expands by ballistic, collisionless atomic motion. The Maxwellian distribution is normally applied to evaporation problems in this extreme [54–60, 63, 64]. Knowledge of the speed distribution becomes important for the study of thin films condensed from velocity-selected atomic vapour, and low-temperature measurements could provide valuable insight into the mechanism for evaporation.

5.3.1 Deposition conditions and material

We used a 3 kW rod-fed bent-beam electron gun to deposit high-purity Ag into vacuum. The Ag rods were purchased from Stanford Advanced Materials and specified to be >99.99% pure, with impurity levels of 20.0 ppm for Al, 15.0 for Fe, 10.0 for Si and 10.0 for Cu. All other impurities had levels ≤ 2.0 ppm. Prior to deposition, the source was degassed at high temperature for several hours to preferentially remove contaminants. Details of the equipment and methods are provided in previous chapters.

Figure 5.10: Photos of the electron-beam process at increasing power. The electron beam is visible due to cathodoluminescence as a blue/green dot.

A steady deposition rate was difficult to maintain at low electron-beam powers. We found that vibrations, either from the velocity selector or from the stepper motor used to advance the rod, had a substantial effect on stability of the melt pool and the deposition rate at low temperature, whereas no effect was observed at high temperature. By increasing the electron-beam power, shown progressively in [Figure 5.10](#), a convex vapour emitting surface formed due to the surface tension of the evaporant and a steady state was achieved. Accordingly, speed distribution experiments were only reliable at moderate/high evaporation rates.

5.3.2 Speed distribution measurements

We used a mechanical velocity selector coupled with quartz crystal resonators to measure the speed distribution in a silver atomic beam produced by an electron-beam-heated surface. The average deposition rate measured by an off-axis QCM placed in direct line-of-sight of the source was $\langle R_d \rangle = 14.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ \AA s}^{-1}$. The surface temperature, T_s , consistent with this rate varies from 1715 K to 1585 K for source diameters between 4.5 and 9.6 mm, which correspond to the electron-beam spot diameter and the diameter of the rod, respectively. To determine the reliability of these estimates, calculated on the basis of the cosine emission law, an experiment could also examine the angular distribution of the vapour [226].

Figure 5.11: Experimental measurements of the transmission spectrum during electron-beam evaporation (303 mA emission current, 8.46 kV accelerating voltage) are compared with theory.

The distribution of transmission measurements, collected by an on-axis QCM above the velocity selector, is plotted in Figure 5.11. The observed departure from

collision-free flow behaviour clearly indicates that collisions occurred during the evaporation process. An excellent fit to the data was obtained for transmission based on the shifted Maxwellian distribution with the flow velocity u_k and temperature T_k . These parameters were determined upon curve fitting to be $440 \pm 40 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $1000 \pm 150 \text{ K}$, respectively. The amplitude, effective pitch angle, and the effective beam divergence angle were additional fit parameters determined to be $a = 0.63 \pm 0.02$, $\phi_e = 2.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$, and $\alpha_e = 0.22 \pm 0.04^\circ$, respectively. We obtained similar values using the transmission model based on the Maxwellian distribution, except the analysis produced a poor-quality fit and greatly overestimated the temperature ($>3500 \text{ K}$).

The flow velocity u_k and temperature T_k are consistent with predictions based on Knudsen-layer formation theory. At the boundary of a Knudsen layer, various treatments have shown that the Mach number is unity and that the T_k to surface temperature ratio, T_k/T_s , is 0.65 for an ideal monoatomic gas [59]. By comparison, the Mach number calculated from the data is 1.2 ± 0.1 and the ratio for T_k/T_s is between 0.58 and 0.63. Based on the observed agreement, the number of collisions per particle was sufficient to establish a Knudsen layer with minimal adiabatic expansion. The agreement also indicates that acceleration due to vapour ionization/excitation was negligible during the experiment [105].

Chapter 6

Conclusions and future work

Significant research efforts have been devoted to GLAD-based thin film engineering. Recent work has shown that thin film properties are influenced by the kinetic energy of the impinging vapour flux due to steering [35] or the surface trapping mechanism [37]. Since the effect is more pronounced at low energies and for glancing angle impacts, the selective deposition of velocity-selected beams offers a promising strategy for achieving further nanostructural control in GLAD-based thin films deposited by thermal evaporation. Thermal evaporation methods based on PVD include, for example, resistive thermal evaporation and electron-beam evaporation. In general, however, a detailed understanding of the energy/velocity distribution is still needed, and important aspects of evaporation phenomena remain unanswered. Accordingly, we constructed and rigorously tested an apparatus to measure the speed distribution in PVD-generated atomic beams.

6.1 Conclusions

The apparatus we constructed measured the speed distribution in atomic beams using a mechanical velocity selector coupled with flux- and density-sensitive detectors under high vacuum conditions. The bulk of our measurements were collected using an on-axis QCM, mounted along the beam centreline. We also implemented a flow-through ionization gauge and demonstrated the simultaneous use of flux- and density-sensitive detection methods. To compare experimental data with theory, we presented transmission models based on various forms of the MB distribution (speed, flux, and shifted) for point source and extended source geometries. The results of our study have demonstrated that the experimental apparatus is capable of measuring the speed distribution under a variety of deposition conditions.

We carried out benchmark effusion studies over a wide range of Knudsen numbers, extending from $\text{Kn} = 41$ to 0.18 . Excellent agreement with transmission models based on the MB distribution were obtained at low temperature, above $\text{Kn} \geq 2.2$. Based on calculations of the rms transmitted speed, the high-velocity side of the distribution was clearly analyzed to velocities in excess of 1400 ms^{-1} . At higher oven temperatures, for $\text{Kn} \leq 1.1$, we observed collision-induced departures from Maxwellian statistics. Similar departures were observed for the emission from an open effusion cell, indicating the occurrence of collisions above the heated surface.

We also measured the velocity distribution produced by an electron-beam-heated surface. Excellent agreement was obtained with the shifted MB distribution, suggesting that collisions occurred above the surface. The values obtained for the flow velocity and temperature were consistent with predictions based on Knudsen-layer formation theory. Based on the observed agreement, we expect that the collision frequency

in the vapour phase was sufficient to establish a Knudsen layer with minimal adiabatic expansion beyond the boundary or effects due to vapour ionization/excitation.

6.2 Future work

We envision two main areas of future research to continue the work presented in this thesis. First are speed distribution measurements in the vapour produced by a heated surface at low temperature, towards the collisionless limit. Given the results of our low-temperature effusion study, these experiments are achievable with the current apparatus and could provide valuable insight into the evaporation mechanism. Examples include measurements with the open effusion cell at lower temperatures, the use of a resistive thermal boat, and the use of an electron-beam evaporator with beam sweeping capability to better achieve a steady state.

Second is an examination of the structure and physical properties of thin films condensed from velocity-selected atomic vapour. Such experiments are important in order to examine impact-driven effects such as steering-enhanced roughing, which may allow thin film engineers to gain further nanostructural control. Given the apparatus described here, the experiments could be achieved simply by placing a substrate in a glancing angle configuration above the velocity selector. To eliminate the dependence on the deposition rate, the rotation speed of the velocity selector could also be varied to select for two different speeds with equal transmission probability.

The equipment and experimental procedure could also be modified to improve the quality of the results. We identify two main areas of interest: (i) an understanding of the angular distribution of the vapour flux and (ii) the design of the velocity selector. Over the course of these experiments it became clear that speed distribution

measurements should be accompanied by direct measurements of the angular distribution. The angular distribution can be measured *in situ* by scanning a QCM over the vapour source. Combining these measurements would lead to a more quantitative understanding of effusion phenomena, including the effect of specular reflection. These measurements would also significantly advance our ability to estimate surface temperature and model transmission behaviour.

Moving forward with further experiments, we would also construct a new velocity selector. The use of a high-transmission velocity selector yields a high signal-to-noise ratio at the expense of resolution. In future designs, the channels of the velocity selector (i.e. pitch, angular aperture) could be modified to increase resolution and provide access to the low-velocity side of the speed distribution. To improve the alignment between the velocity selector axis and the source-detector axis, future designs could also include a straight channel, or two to avoid a dynamical imbalance.

Part II

N-heterocyclic carbene
self-assembly on Au(111)

Chapter 7

Introduction

Molecular self-assembly refers to the spontaneous process whereby molecules from solution or the gas/vapour phase adsorb onto the surface of a material and then organize into an ordered ensemble [236]. From a microscopic perspective, the activation energies associated with hopping or bond making/breaking must allow the molecules to sample many different configurations/conformations to form ordered (low-energy) structures. This process of self-assembly occurs spontaneously, and is driven by the complex interplay of attractive and repulsive intermolecular and molecule-substrate interactions. In the past few decades, self-assembly has been studied on a large number of low-index metal surfaces with an even greater variety of molecules, particularly small organic molecules such as porphyrins [237] and phthalocyanines [238]. In many cases, the molecules interact via weak non-covalent intermolecular interactions, such as van der Waals (vdW) interactions, hydrogen bonding, halogen bonding, or $\pi - \pi$ interactions [239]. The self-assembly pattern that forms if molecules are only weakly bound to the surface is steered by these tunable intermolecular interactions, and often reflects complex (directional) interactions in addition to the shape/size of the

molecules [236]. Stronger molecule-substrate interactions can have a marked influence on the self-assembly process, including molecule-induced surface reconstructions [240] and the formation of adatoms, which are sometimes incorporated into the assembly through metal-ligand bonding [241]. These self-assembly patterns can reach a remarkable degree of complexity, and have provided a versatile platform to develop functional materials.

An important application of self-assembly is the use of organic molecules to modify or functionalize surfaces by the formation of a self-assembled monolayer (SAM). Initially, the study of SAMs focused on organic molecules without terminal functionalities [242]. Today, a wide variety of functionalized SAMs have been investigated due to the flexibility with which the chemical nature of the top surface layer (i.e. the tail group pointing outward from the surface) can be tuned to modify the chemical and physical properties of the surface [236, 243]. Among a large and growing number of applications include their use for corrosion prevention [244] and other interfacial phenomena, such as wetting, friction, and adhesion [245], anti-stiction coatings in microelectromechanical systems [246, 247], to stabilize and sometimes functionalize nanosized objects (e.g. nanoparticles [248–250] and nanorods [251]), and nanopatterning [252, 253]. SAMs are also being used in device fabrication as sensors and actuators [243] and as molecular motors [254]. In biology and medicine, SAMs are used as artificial biomolecular recognition surfaces for biosensing (e.g. protein adsorption) [255–257] and, for example, cell culture substrates [245, 258]. Recently, there has also been a growing interest in molecular self-assembly on semiconductor surfaces (e.g. InAs [259] and GaAs [260]), as well as 2D surfaces including graphene and hexagonal boron nitride in order to tune their electronic properties [261]. Clearly, the

applications of SAMs are abundant and involve many scientific disciplines; see, for example, [245] and [243] for more detailed reviews.

The majority of these advancements were realized by the adsorption of alkanethiols (i.e. thiol-terminated alkyl chains, given by the general formula $\text{SH}-(\text{CH}_2)_{n-1}-\text{CH}_3$), which are by far the most studied class of SAMs [245, 262]. In 1983, Nuzzo and Allara at Bell Laboratories were the first to observe an ordered monolayer of organic disulphide molecules on gold [242]. Shortly thereafter, alkanethiols were observed to self-assemble into a well-ordered monolayer on gold surfaces [263]. Interest in alkanethiols has since been ongoing, largely because (i) they are relatively stable due to the high affinity of the thiol group for noble metals, (ii) they exhibit molecular order with flexible chemical functionality, and (iii) the convenience with which they can be prepared from gas-phase or from solution [264]. It is generally accepted that the adsorption process proceeds with a short initial physisorption stage followed by a chemisorption stage that involves the formation of a thiolate through the sulphur head group of the molecule following the cleavage of the S–H bond [243, 265]. The formation of a S–Au covalent bond leaves the molecules standing nearly upright in a closely-packed array; lateral interactions between neighbouring alkyl groups (i.e. vdW interactions and steric effects) then guide the resulting architectural structure. Such organosulphur monolayers have been generated mostly on Au(111), for which S–Au bond is known to be reasonably strong with a bond energy of about 30 kcal mol^{-1} , or $\sim 1.3 \text{ eV}$ [266].

Surface functionalization using alkanethiols through the controlled adjustment of

the terminal functional group has led to a number of interesting findings. For example, methyl- and trifluoromethyl-terminated (i.e. $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CF}_3$) alkanethiol monolayers make the surface hydrophobic, whereas carboxyl ($-\text{COOH}$), amino ($-\text{NH}_2$), and hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) end groups make the SAM surface hydrophilic [250]. Surface functionalization is particularly interesting when it comes to stabilizing and functionalizing nanosized objects that have a high surface-to-volume ratio. Thiol-terminated ($-\text{SH}$) alkanethiols, or alkanedithiols, are especially well-studied, since these coordinating ligands can be used to protect and stabilize nanoparticles, establish cross-links between them, or allow for the attachment of nanosized objects [250, 267, 268]. Micrometer scale ‘lab-on-chip’ sensors have also been developed from functionalized gold surfaces for a variety of applications ranging from biomedical research to bacterial detection for environmental monitoring to healthcare and the detection of cancer biomarkers to security [269–271]. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) based biosensors, for example, rely on the optical excitation of surface plasmon polaritons and measure the resonant wavelength shift or the change in intensity that occurs upon the targeted adsorption of an analyte [270]. Among several new and exciting applications include graphene-based chemical and biological sensors, which are attractive because adsorbed single molecules and assemblies on 2D materials can significantly affect their electronic properties [261, 272]. In a recent study, for example, functionalized graphene using alkanethiols was integrated into field-effect transistor devices for heavy metal sensing [272].

Although thiol-based SAMs are very versatile, they offer limited thermal and chemical stability due to the strength of the Au–S bond and susceptibility to oxidation [243, 273]. These drawbacks seriously limit their practical application. New

approaches in the formation of thermally and chemically stable SAMs of upright molecules include the use of *N*-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs), which may be superior to thiol-based systems [274–276]. NHCs are a class of carbenes that have a divalent carbon atom bonded to at least one nitrogen atom in a heterocyclic ring structure [277]. Unlike typical carbenes that are highly reactive and unstable, heteroatoms increase the stability of NHCs, which has allowed a broad range of NHCs to be synthesized and crystallized [274]. Among them include NHCs derived from imidazoline, imidazole, triazole, and benzimidazole, Figure 7.1. NHCs have important advantages compared to thiol-based systems, most notably their chemical tunability and ability to form very strong carbon-metal bonds, especially with late transition metals such as gold [274,276].

Figure 7.1: A selection of common NHC scaffolds.

Following their synthesis by Arduengo *et al.* in 1991 [278], NHCs found widespread use in transition-metal-catalysis [279] and organocatalysis [280,281]. More recently, they have also been applied as ligands in self-assembly processes. Seminal work by Siemeling [282] and Johnson [283] showed that NHCs bind to planar gold surfaces. Later, in 2014, Crudden *et al.* demonstrated the first example of a stable SAM of NHCs on gold [274]. Once formed, the NHC-protected surfaces were treated with dodecanethiol and showed no incorporation of sulphur or loss of carbene from the

surface. Remarkably, over half of the thiols from a dodecanethiol-covered surface were also removed when exposed to NHCs, demonstrating the strong binding affinity of NHCs with gold. Crudden *et al.* have also demonstrated that NHC SAMs on gold are stable to high temperature, resistant to oxidation and acid and base treatment, and can remain stable for months in air or water [274,275]. Given NHC SAMs can also be functionalized in a manner similar to alkanethiols [284], they offer a promising alternative to ubiquitous thiol-based systems.

Figure 7.2: Benzimidazolylidene NHCs bearing (a) methyl, (b) ethyl, and (c) isopropyl wingtips.

In this thesis, I present a detailed scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) study of NHC adsorption and self-assembly on Au(111) single-crystal surfaces. My research interests focus on alkylated benzimidazolylidenes, Figure 7.2, which have attracted considerable interest for a wide range of applications, especially on gold surfaces and nanoparticles. A notable application was their successful use in SPR-based biosensing [275] and their latest application in the detection of the measles virus [285], which represents a significant advancement towards the detection of other biological agents, including SARS-CoV-2 [286]. NHC SAM applications also include their use in molecular electronics [287, 288], in microcontact printing [289], and for the stabilization and/or functionalization of metal nanoparticles [290]. Underpinning the successful

use of NHCs in these applications is an understanding of the nanoscale physical and chemical processes driving NHC adsorption and self-assembly. Efforts to understand these processes were crucial in advancing the chemistry and applications of thiol-based SAMs, and will similarly offer critical strategies for the design of upright NHC SAMs and their applications.

Many fundamental properties of NHC-based SAMs are not well-understood, especially the mechanisms by which NHCs bind to gold surfaces, and the factors that control their orientation. Ligand geometry is critical in virtually every potential NHC-SAM application since it controls the structure, density, and stability of the SAM, and its use in biosensing where upright adsorption configurations are needed. Several groups have shown that the substituents on the nitrogen atoms (i.e. the wingtip groups) play a key role in determining NHC orientation [274, 291–294], however a general picture of the adsorption process still needs to be clarified, as does the effect of NHC structure on ordering. In this work, I show that NHC orientation depends not only on wingtip structure but also on the surface coverage and substrate temperature. The dependence on these factors is linked to fundamental physical and chemical phenomena, which include the minimization of molecule-surface steric interactions, the production of Au adatoms by the effect of NHC adsorption on the underlying gold substrate, and the reactivity and stability of the ligands and the complexes they form. I show that these effects are crucial in determining how NHCs bind to the surface. At least four binding modes are resolved that sometimes co-exist and concurrently self-assemble on the surface, including surface- and adatom-bound NHCs attached in upright/tilted geometries, NHC monomers, and flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. These form a rich variety of self-assembly structures that differ substantially in terms

of mobility, density, stability, and adatom involvement. By characterizing and modelling these arrays at the molecular level, I provide new insights into molecule-molecule and molecule-substrate interactions, as well as the role of surface modifications and on-surface chemical reactions in the formation of NHC SAMs.

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows. I review the basic principles of STM and relevant imaging methods in [chapter 8](#). In [chapter 9](#), I provide a summary of the general structure and properties of NHCs. The chapter also includes background information relevant to NHC deposition and adsorption. Experimental results are presented in the next two chapters. In [chapter 10](#), I study the adsorption and self-assembly behaviour of upright NHCs and place a particular emphasis on a zig-zag lattice formed by adatom-bound NHCs. In [chapter 11](#), I study NHCs that dimerize to form flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes and focus in particular on a non-porous chiral Kagome lattice containing trapped NHC monomers. Finally, I conclude with a brief summary and future outlook in [chapter 12](#).

Chapter 8

Experimental methods

This chapter describes the experimental methods used in this thesis, with a focus on STM. The first part describes the basic theory of tunnelling in order to establish the imaging contrast mechanism. The second part provides a description of the STM apparatus, with a focus on the principles of operation. Important aspects of surface relaxations and reconstructions are also discussed. Finally, a method for real-time drift compensation is presented.

8.1 Scanning tunnelling microscopy

STM is a scanning probe technique used to detect local properties at a surface or interface with nanometre or even atomic scale spatial resolution ([Figure 8.1](#)). The basic principle relies on electron tunnelling, a quantum mechanical phenomenon in which electrons tunnel through a classically forbidden potential barrier. A tunnelling current is established when a bias is applied between a sharp metal tip (i.e. the probe) and a conductive substrate placed in close proximity (within ~ 10 Å). In what

follows, I consider different approximations for the tunnelling current, focusing on the tip position, bias, and local density of states (LDOS) dependence. The theory of quantum tunnelling has been addressed by many authors; for additional details see [72, 295–301].

Figure 8.1: Schematic drawing illustrating the basic principles of STM.

8.1.1 Tunnel junctions

The STM tunnel junction consists of a tip and a sample separated by a vacuum gap, as shown in Figure 8.2. The Fermi energy, E_F , corresponds to the highest level occupied by electrons, which normally lies below the vacuum level by several eV (i.e. the work function, Φ) [302]. Classically, an electron remains trapped unless it gains sufficient energy to overcome this potential barrier. In quantum mechanics, however, electrons are described by wavefunctions that exponentially decay in vacuum, extending beyond the surface. When the tip and sample wavefunctions overlap, electrons can tunnel through the barrier.

A net tunnelling current (I) develops when a bias (V) is applied between the tip and the sample. The applied bias shifts the relative position of the Fermi levels by eV , establishing unoccupied states into which electrons can tunnel [302]. Elastic

Figure 8.2: Energy level diagrams for the STM tip-sample tunnel junction. (a) At positive sample bias, electrons tunnel from occupied tip states to unoccupied sample states. (b) At negative sample bias, electrons tunnel from occupied sample states to unoccupied tip states.

electron tunnelling only occurs within the bias window (in the zero temperature limit) since there are no available transitions from an occupied state to an unoccupied state above or below. When a positive bias is applied to the sample (Figure 8.2a), E_{F_s} shifts down in energy relative to E_{F_t} and the tunnelling current flows from occupied tip states to unoccupied sample states. When a negative bias is applied to the sample (Figure 8.2b), E_{F_s} shifts up in relation to E_{F_t} , which reverses current flow such that electrons tunnel from occupied sample states to unoccupied tip states.

8.1.2 Theory of STM

Bardeen established the original formalism for metal-insulator-metal tunnel junctions [303], which carries over to STM by considering a vacuum gap between the tip and the sample. The basic idea of the model is that the two electrodes are independent systems, and that independent elastic scattering events (transitions) between initial (occupied) and final (unoccupied) states contribute to the total current [298]. To model inelastic effects including electron-electron and electron-phonon scattering, more sophisticated approaches have been developed using the non-equilibrium

Green's function method [304]. While theoretical treatments based on this method have provided the most rigorous description for the tunnelling current, in what follows I focus on two approximations within the Bardeen formalism. The models apply in the weak tip-sample coupling regime and are more generally useful for interpreting image contrast in STM.

In the energy-dependent approximation of the Bardeen model, the tunnelling current is

$$I = \frac{4\pi e}{\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f(\epsilon - eV) - f(\epsilon)) \rho_t(\epsilon - eV) \rho_s(\epsilon) T(\epsilon, V, d) d\epsilon, \quad (8.1)$$

where $\rho(\epsilon)$ is density of tip/sample states in the energy interval ϵ and $\epsilon + d\epsilon$ relative to E_{Fs} , $f(\epsilon)$ is the Fermi-Dirac distribution, and $T(\epsilon, V, d)$ is the electron transmission factor [295]. Whereas states above (below) the Fermi level are completely empty (filled) at absolute zero, the Fermi functions account for the occupation probabilities at finite temperature¹.

The transmission factor, $T(\epsilon, V, d)$, is approximately given by

$$T(\epsilon, V, d) \propto \exp\left\{-2d \left[\frac{2m}{\hbar^2} \left(\bar{\phi} + \frac{eV}{2} - \epsilon\right)\right]^{1/2}\right\}, \quad (8.2)$$

where m is the electron mass and $\bar{\phi}$ is the average work function [295]. The expression has a dependence on the barrier height, which is determined by the tip/sample work functions, the applied voltage, and the electron energy, ϵ . For example, the energy dependence of the tunnelling probability attenuates the contribution of low-lying states, which have the largest barrier height (indicated by horizontal arrows

¹The Fermi-Dirac distribution describes the occupation probability of a particular energy level such that at finite temperature, the density of occupied states in the energy interval ϵ and $\epsilon + d\epsilon$ is $f(\epsilon)\rho(\epsilon)d\epsilon$.

in Figure 8.2). The dominant factor is the exponential dependence on distance, d . This dependence is what makes the tunnelling current so sensitive to corrugation, increasing by approximately one order of magnitude for every 1 Å decrease in d [296]. The local aspect of STM is also highlighted by the exponential decay with distance; most of the tunnelling current flows between a single atom protruding at the tip apex and the sample directly below ($\sim 90\%$ if the apex atom protrudes by 1 Å) [305]. The strong distance dependence therefore gives STM the ability to probe local (electronic) properties with atomic-scale lateral and vertical resolution [297].

Finally, the tip and the sample density of states enter the expression for the tunnelling current symmetrically. To more readily obtain information on the surface, the tips used in STM are chosen to have a featureless density of states. Accordingly, a widely used approximation in STM theory removes the tip density of states dependence.

In the Tersoff-Hamann approximation, the STM tip is described by a single spherical s -type² wavefunction [300]. At low temperature and for small bias voltages, the tunnelling current is simply related to the local density of states (LDOS) along the sample's Fermi contour at the tip position \mathbf{r}_t , written as

$$I \propto \rho_s(E_F, \mathbf{r}_t). \quad (8.3)$$

Thus, to a first approximation, the tunnelling current is a property of the surface alone, and provides contours of constant charge density in the constant-current imaging mode of STM [295]. This result offers a simple approach for simulating STM

²Chen extended the Tersoff-Hamann model to account for more detailed models of the tip, clarifying the role of tip orbital structure in high-resolution STM imaging [299, 306, 307].

images based on LDOS calculations obtained with DFT [308]. The origin of the contrast due to adsorption is also clarified within the Tersoff-Hamann approximation. The contrast of an adsorbate present on the surface is determined by the way it changes the LDOS at the Fermi level. That is, if it enhances (depletes) the LDOS, it images as a protrusion (depression) during scanning.

8.2 Low-temperature UHV STM apparatus

All experiments presented in this thesis were performed using a low-temperature UHV STM apparatus designed by CreaTec. Details on the apparatus are provided here. I also briefly summarize methods for imaging and noise isolation in the STM system. Information on LabVIEW-based control software that we developed for imaging experiments and drift compensation is provided in [Appendix C](#).

8.2.1 Overview

The low-temperature UHV STM setup is shown in [Figure 8.3](#). The vacuum system consists of (i) an STM chamber attached to a bath cryostat, (ii) a sample preparation chamber, and (iii) a load-lock chamber for quick tip/sample transfer into UHV. Sample preparation and analysis was carried out in the STM and preparation chambers at a base pressure on the order of 10^{-10} mbar. The chambers are separated by a gate valve, and independently pumped with ion and titanium sublimation pumps. The load-lock chamber can also be pumped independently. It is equipped with its own high-vacuum pumps (roughing, turbomolecular), which avoids the need to break vacuum in the main chambers when replacing tips or samples.

A four-axis manipulator mounted on the preparation chamber allows for

Figure 8.3: Picture of the CreaTec chamber.

tip/sample transfer into the UHV-STM. The manipulator is also equipped with electron-beam and direct current heating options, and a LN₂ flow cryostat for sample cooling (<135 K). Monitoring techniques include pyrometry and type-K thermocouples attached near the sample. In this way, surfaces can be prepared through sputter/anneal cycles, samples can be heat treated, and molecules can be deposited onto a cold surface and subsequently scanned by STM.

The STM scanner is suspended under a liquid helium (LHe) bath cryostat to allow imaging at cryogenic temperatures. The cryostat contains an inner dewar that can be filled with LHe or LN₂ and radiation shielding cooled by a reservoir of LN₂ to reduce the evaporation rate of the liquid. Both cooling stages have outer radiation shields that enclose the STM scanner, which are used to achieve thermal equilibrium. During measurements, the scanner is suspended from the cryostat on springs and stabilized

with magnetic eddy-current damping for vibration isolation.

8.2.2 Imaging

The main parts of the STM scanner include (i) a tip holder, (ii) a sample holder, and (iii) a piezoelectric scanner. As with many STM designs, a single piezoelectric tube is used for fine motion control during scanning [295]. Piezo scanner tubes are thin cylinders equipped with an inner electrode and segmented electrodes on the outside surface to provide nano-positioning XYZ control [309]. When a voltage is applied to the inner electrode, the tube expands or contracts in Z . When voltages with opposite polarity are applied to opposite outside electrodes, the tube bends, providing lateral movement in the XY plane. In the CreaTec design, the piezo tube is fitted with a tip holder and imaging is performed by scanning the tip over the sample. Precise positioning of the tip on the picometre scale is readily achieved within a range on the order of $1\ \mu\text{m}$. For coarse positioning, the piezo scan tube is driven in a Pan-style type design, which contains slip-stick piezo motors for XYZ motion in the millimetre range. The coarse approach mechanism is needed to reduce the tip-sample distance to within range of the piezo scan tube. The ability to move the tip a macroscopic distance from the sample surface also facilitates *in situ* tip/sample exchange.

To acquire an STM image, the tip is raster-scanned over the sample surface while measuring the tunnelling current. The images presented in this thesis were acquired in the constant-current mode of STM, which uses a feedback loop to adjust the tip-sample distance in order to maintain a constant tunnelling current. Accordingly, the images correspond to surface height/LDOS maps, referred to as STM topography [295].

8.2.3 Noise

The tunnelling current in STM is usually very small, in the range of 10 pA to 10 nA. It is therefore converted to an amplified voltage signal using an internal or external preamplifier, which also amplifies various types of noise. Experimentally, the tunnelling current noise is evidenced as flicker ($1/f$) noise, thermal (Johnson) noise, and shot noise, originating predominantly from the tunnel junction and the I/V preamplifier [310]. Thermal [311] and shot noise [312] are white noise sources relevant at high frequencies, which become less important at lower frequencies where the characteristic $1/f$ noise dominates [313, 314]. Other sources for current noise include electromagnetic interference along the current path to the preamplifier and vibrations transmitted to the STM tip/sample [310]. Here I consider noise problems encountered in the CreaTec system, which may apply to other low-temperature UHV STM systems as well.

Noise sources can be identified by spectral analysis of the tunnelling current. We performed noise measurements on clean Au(111) with a Pt/Ir tip under constant-current³ conditions (100 mV bias, 20 pA current). The spectral density of AC components of the tunnelling current are plotted in Figure 8.4 for room temperature, LN₂, and LHe conditions. The spectrum obtained at room temperature is mostly featureless, except spectral peaks at odd harmonics of our line frequency (60 Hz). Peaks are also identified at these locations in the noise spectra recorded at LN₂ and LHe. Compared to the room-temperature data, the spectra show lower noise levels (reduced by ~ 20 fA/Hz^{1/2}) and several new spectral features. Peaks at 3.0 Hz (LN₂) and 4.2 Hz

³Constant-current STM imaging relies on feedback control, which filters low-frequency noise [315, 316]. We also recorded noise spectra with open-feedback conditions that showed characteristic $1/f$ -like behaviour.

(LHe) are indicated and known to be the resonance frequency for the spring suspension system. Similarly, a disturbance to the cryostat produced peaks around 110 Hz that decreased in magnitude over time. Both spectra also show a prominent peak at 142 Hz.

Figure 8.4: Spectral density plots acquired using the original STM cryostat with constant current feedback enabled at a fixed (xy) tip position.

The 142 Hz noise peak correlated with visible noise produced in STM images. The peak-to-peak amplitude of the noise measured approximately 6 pm, which severely limited our ability to acquire STM data with adequate quality. To determine if the noise was electrical or mechanical, we retracted the tip from the sample since the current only responds to vibrations that modulate the tip-sample distance in tunnelling range. Spectra collected outside tunnelling range were largely the same, indicating an electronic origin for most features in [Figure 8.4](#). The 142 Hz peak, however, was not observed, and is therefore attributed to vibrational noise.

To optimize the STM performance, variations of the tip-sample distance due to external vibrations should be minimized (e.g. to 1 pm or less). Whereas floating the chamber on its vibration isolation legs or varying strength of the eddy current damping

had no appreciable effect on the magnitude of the 142 Hz noise peak, pumping on the cryostat did. Pumping on the liquid nitrogen reservoir is a common method used to cool the liquid below its boiling point, which temporarily suppresses boiling and the formation of bubbles. Cryogen bubbling is a well-known source for vibrational noise in low-temperature STM applications [317,318]. Bubble-induced noise is manifested here by the strong spectral resonance at 142 Hz, which severely limited STM performance and ultimately required the replacement of the cryostat. The noise performance of the microscope improved significantly with the new cryostat, with the 142 Hz noise peak reduced by more than one order of magnitude.

8.3 Sample preparation

High-quality NHC SAMs can be formed by immersing a substrate into a solution of the organic molecules or prepared *in situ* by physical vapour deposition (PVD) in UHV [275]. In this work, NHC films were deposited onto Au(111) by flash evaporation in the preparation chamber under high-vacuum conditions (10^{-7} mbar). The preparation of atomically clean, well-ordered Au(111) surfaces involved repeated cycles of Ar ion sputtering (1.5 keV beam energy, 3 μ A crystal current, 5 to 10 minutes) and subsequent heating to 575 °C over 5 minutes (~ 100 °C/min). During deposition, the substrate temperature was held at room temperature or 135 K using the LN₂ flow cryostat.

The source consists of an oxidized silicon wafer (low resistivity p-type) that is electrically connected to a filament at each end. Its preparation involved dissolving hydrogen carbonate salt of the NHC precursor in ethanol and adding a single droplet from the solution to the centre of the wafer. Passing a large current (~ 3 A) through

the wafer for just a few seconds produces a rapid temperature rise that causes the molecules to desorb from the surface onto the substrate placed in line-of-sight. By varying the molarity of the solution (e.g. between 5 and 50 mM), this technique can reliably produce submonolayer to full-monolayer surface coverages.

An advantage of the flash evaporation technique is that it uses small quantities of organic matter, which reduces contamination of the vacuum system. The introduction of contaminants into the deposition process was tested by exposing a clean Au(111) surface to a heated wafer devoid of NHCs. In an initial experiment, no evidence for surface contamination was detected by STM. However, the surface coverage of contaminants was around 0.5 ML after long-term use of the source to deposit organic matter. A visual examination of the source revealed discolouration and a buildup of deposits on the inner surface of the housing that surrounds the wafer. Ultrasonic cleaning was effective in removing the deposits and significantly reduced the contamination resulting from the flash deposition process.

8.4 Au(111) substrate

All STM investigations were performed using a Au(111) single crystal substrate. Clean Au(111) undergoes a well-known $22 \times \sqrt{3}$ surface reconstruction to reduce tensile surface stress [319, 320]. The reconstruction involves a rearrangement of atoms in the surface layer, which move towards a smaller lattice constant due to the lack of neighbouring atoms on the plane above the surface. STM images of the reconstruction (Figure 8.5a, 8.5b, and 8.5c) show bright lines, called domain or soliton walls, that extend along the $\langle 11\bar{2} \rangle$ directions in a herringbone pattern.

In the $22 \times \sqrt{3}$ unit cell (Figure 8.5d), 23 Au atoms fit into 22 lattice sites along

Figure 8.5: STM images of the reconstructed Au(111) surface showing (a) the herringbone pattern formed by soliton walls on a terrace (100 mV, 100 pA, $45.0 \times 45.0 \text{ nm}^2$), (b) a monatomic step crossed by soliton walls (500 mV, 100 pA, $45.0 \times 25.0 \text{ nm}^2$), and (c) an atomically resolved image (100 mV, 100 pA, $8.5 \times 4.5 \text{ nm}^2$). (d) Schematic model of the Au(111)- $(22 \times \sqrt{3})$ surface reconstruction.

the close-packed $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction, amounting to a 4.3% compression in the surface layer [321]. The lattice mismatch between the first two atomic layers produces soliton walls that separate wide fcc and narrow hcp stacking regions, with Au atoms in the top layer slowly alternating between bridge sites and fcc and hcp three-fold hollow sites [319, 321]. In STM, the soliton walls appear as 0.1 to 0.3 Å protrusions, arranged in pairs that periodically bend by $\pm 120^\circ$ every 20 to 25 nm across terraces and monatomic steps [319]. The three rotational domains result from the threefold

symmetry of a (111) surface, and provide an overall isotropic reduction of the tensile stress across the surface [319].

STM images of the reconstructed Au(111) surface were used to calibrate the piezo constants (nm/V) of the tube scanner. To calibrate the Z -piezo, monatomic step height measurements were corrected to the expected value of 2.35 Å [322]. The piezo constants in the X and Y directions were calibrated in a similar way based on lattice spacing measurements in atomically resolved STM images. To account for any differences in the piezo response, the X and Y piezo constants were calibrated separately with measurements taken along the three close-packed directions⁴. The X and Y calibration constants were also routinely checked by the periodicity of the soliton walls, which have a well-defined 6.3 nm separation distance between adjacent pairs [324].

The overall accuracy of the STM measurements is generally limited by thermal drift and piezo nonlinearities such as creep and hysteresis [325], which produce an uncertainty in distance measurements that typically ranges from 5 to 10 % [326]. In an effort to improve the measurement accuracy of the STM, we developed real-time techniques for correcting image distortion.

8.5 Lateral drift compensation

The relative motion between the tip and the sample due to thermal drift is a common problem in STM and other scanning probe techniques that causes image distortions [326, 327]. The distortion is often linear and can be compensated or corrected

⁴The underlying bulk imposes an atomic spacing of $a_0 = 2.88$ Å at the surface that measures 2.76 Å along the compressed directions perpendicular to the soliton walls [323].

in real-time or with post-image processing software. One strategy for drift compensation relies on atom-tracking STM, which locks the tip over a single feature (i.e. an atom or an adsorbate) [328, 329]. By tracking a stationary feature, the lateral drift velocity can be measured and subsequently offset [330]. Other approaches for drift correction rely on image registration [327].

We implemented an image-based registration method for drift compensation using the TurboReg/StackReg plugin [331]. The registration technique relied on linear transformations to align two or more images by minimizing the mean square intensity difference. In general, a number of image processing applications become available with image registration, including noise reduction by image averaging or stacking [332]. Here, our interest is to correct drift-induced distortions. The drift velocity between two images can be calculated from the results of the image translation and the scanning parameters. One application of this approach is to apply post-processing corrections to STM images. We also register STM data in real time to actively compensate drift during scanning. An advantage of using real-time drift compensation is the ability to image the same region on the surface for extended periods of time.

For real-time drift compensation, noisy multi-channel STM data were processed (plane subtraction, gaussian blurring) and registered automatically during scanning. The drift vector determined for consecutive image pairs was then used to offset the X and Y scanning piezos. We found that exponentially weighting successive drift vectors reduced the impact of outliers caused by tip changes or noise. The appropriate weighting factor was dependent on the imaging conditions and determined using a trial-and-error approach to improve performance. To reduce the effect of creep

distortion [326], which is apparent when changing the scan region or when imaging large areas on the surface, a sufficiently long delay was introduced to the beginning of every scan (10 to 20 seconds nominal during scanning).

Figure 8.6: Lateral drift compensation during STM measurements on an NHC-covered Au(111) surface. The scatter plot shows the X and Y drift rate measured for pairs of sequential images over 20 hours.

The performance of our drift correction method is characterized in Figure 8.6. The drift vector was measured and used to offset the piezos in real time over 20 hours for an NHC-covered Au(111) surface at 77 K (Movie S1). As shown, the drift between consecutive images approached a steady state value centred at zero, measuring on average $\langle \Delta v_x \rangle = -0.004 \pm 0.012 \text{ nm h}^{-1}$ and $\langle \Delta v_y \rangle = -0.01 \pm 0.02 \text{ nm h}^{-1}$. For comparison, the drift correction to the piezos varied between 1.2 and 0.3 nm h^{-1} over the course of the measurements. Hence, the data indicate that the method provides accurate, real-time drift compensation.

Overall, the use of real-time drift compensation reduced image distortions and allowed the same area of the surface to be scanned for hours or days. The drift

consistently stabilized to rates below 0.01 nm h^{-1} between consecutive scans, and was robust to noise, sudden tip changes, and the movement of adsorbates on the surface.

8.6 Image processing

STM data visualization and analysis was performed using Gwyddion open source software. Image processing was performed without the use of filters (e.g. Fourier filtering), and usually limited to levelling (plane, three points) and Gaussian blurring. Statistical quantities, including median height value and x and y centre value distributions, were determined from image thresholding analysis based on height parametrization. Potential bias was avoided based on careful consideration of the grain shapes after thresholding (shape, height, symmetry). Statistical analysis was then performed on the data, including nearest-neighbour analysis to determine lattice constants.

Chapter 9

N-heterocyclic carbenes: Review

N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) readily bind to transition metals with a high metal-ligand bond dissociation energy, owing to their strong σ -donating and weak to moderate π -accepting ability. In this chapter I focus on the structure and electronic properties of NHCs, both isolated and adsorbed on transition metal surfaces. The hybridization and structure has been reviewed in detail by many authors; for additional information see [277, 333–336].

9.1 Structure

Carbenes are highly reactive molecules, given by the general formula $R-(C:)-R$ (or $R=C:$), that have a neutral divalent carbon atom with two unshared valence electrons. Singlet carbenes have a planar geometry with a sp^2 -hybridized carbon atom; a lone-pair of non-bonding electrons is localized in one of the hybrid orbitals and an unoccupied p orbital crosses the plane. Triplet carbenes¹, on the other hand, do not have the remaining valence electrons spin-paired in the same orbital. Instead,

the unshared electrons occupy different orbitals and have the same spin. Linear geometries can result from sp -hybridized carbon, for which the two hybrid orbitals form σ bonds while the two remaining valence electrons occupy mutually orthogonal p orbitals. Alternatively, bent geometries can form when the carbon atom is sp^2 hybridized with one of the unshared electrons in one of the hybrid orbitals and the other in the unhybridized p orbital with a parallel spin. For example, the simplest example of a carbene molecule is methylene, CH_2 , which has a bond angle that depends on spin multiplicity. Singlet methylene has a bond angle of about 105° , while triplet methylene has a bond angle of about 135° [337]. Provided certain substituents such as nitrogen are not bonded directly to the divalent carbon atom, the triplet state is usually favoured energetically due to the greater electron-nucleus attraction energy of high-spin states (i.e. there is diminished screening of the nucleus when the electrons have parallel spins), which is in accordance with Hund's rules for orbital filling [338].

In contrast to classic carbenes, singlet carbenes can be electronically stabilized using nitrogen, oxygen, sulphur, or halides due to mesomeric and inductive effects. The mesomeric effect involves the delocalization of π -electrons in the system due to the overlapping p orbitals of the carbene carbon atom and its substituents, while the inductive effect refers to the asymmetric electron density in a bond that occurs due to uneven electronegativities. For instance, consider a singlet carbene stabilized by two nitrogen atoms next to the divalent carbon atom, [Figure 9.1](#). Electron density from each nitrogen lone pair is donated to the formerly vacant p orbital of the carbene moiety and at the same time the electronegative nitrogen atoms inductively withdraw electron density through the σ bonds [277, 334]. The π -electron-donating and

¹This nomenclature comes from the spin quantum number of the system; $s = 0$ and $m_s = 0$ for singlet carbene since both electrons occupy a single orbital and are thus spin-paired, while triplet carbene has two unpaired electrons yielding $s = 1$ with spin components $m_s = -1, 0, 1$.

σ -electron-withdrawing effects increase the energy gap between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) and, in particular, the singlet-triplet energy gap increases, which correlates with increasing thermodynamic stability [339, 340]. A simple energy level diagram is shown [Figure 9.1a](#) that identifies the energy levels of the singlet ground state and higher-lying triplet excited state (delineated by two singly-occupied molecular orbitals, or SOMOs).

Figure 9.1: (a) Singlet ground state and triplet excited state energy levels of carbene stabilized by two π -electron-donating and σ -electron-withdrawing substituents, X. (b) Orbital interaction diagram of imidazolylidene.

NHCs such as imidazolylidene shown in [Figure 9.1b](#) exhibit a singlet ground state electronic configuration. The singlet state is promoted by the cyclic geometry of the ligand, which forces the divalent carbon atom to adopt a more bent, sp^2 -like, arrangement with the HOMO and LUMO best described as a lone-pair-occupied sp^2 hybrid orbital and a vacant p (often written p_π) orbital, respectively [277]. In addition to their surface binding properties, the popularity of NHCs is linked to the convenience with which their properties can be fine-tuned through various structural modifications to the carbene backbone structure or wingtip groups while maintaining stability [335]. With reference to many NHC subclasses shown in [Figure 9.2](#), nitrogen heteroatoms

can be introduced into the molecular framework at different positions and possibly substituted with S or O atoms, the ring size can be adjusted, though five-membered azole rings are the most common [341], or substituents can be introduced on the backbone or at the wingtip positions (i.e. attached to the nitrogen heteroatoms). Hundreds of NHCs based on different scaffolds are already known in literature to date (e.g. see Figure 9.3 for several imidazole-based NHCs), demonstrating their structural diversity, and this number continues to grow due to the nearly boundless library of additional side groups [334].

Figure 9.2: Several common NHC subclasses. To obtain their name, the suffix 'ylidene' must be added each caption.

The synthesis of functionalized NHCs is recent and exciting as this new class of ligands is more diverse than thiol-based ligands due to their highly tunable structural and electronic properties. Here, I will refer to functionalization as the synthetic modification of an NHC that contains only alkyl or aryl substituents through the addition of a functional group. NHCs for use as ligands in catalysis or as building blocks for self-assembly can be functionalized via substituent groups attached to the nitrogen heteroatoms [279]. This design pattern is displayed in Figure 9.4a for the generic class of imidazol-2-ylidene molecules for which functionalizing agents, F_n , are

Figure 9.3: Structure and acronym for several common NHCs.

attached to the N₁/N₃ positions. For example, this method was used by Johnson and coworkers to functionalize gold surfaces using NHCs with aryl bromide and β -methylstyrene substituents [283]. Backbone functionalization at the C₄ or C₅ position is also possible, shown in Figure 9.4b, which was recently used by Crudden *et al.* to develop NHC films for surface plasmon resonance-based biosensing [275].

Figure 9.4: Common functionalization patterns for NHCs.

9.2 NHC precursors

NHCs are often air- and moisture-sensitive and must therefore be kept in dry and inert environments [342]. Several approaches to increase their bench stability have been developed on the basis of masked NHCs. For example, NHC–Ag complexes, NHC–CO₂, –COS, and –CS₂ adducts, and (benz)imidazolium hydrogen carbonates ([NHC(H)][HCO₃]) have all been employed as NHC precursors that can be stored and handled under ambient conditions [342, 343].

NHC carboxylates have been widely used as ligand precursors in catalysis, formed by the nucleophilic addition of the electron deficient region of CO₂ to the carbene lone pair [342]. The reverse reaction (decarboxylation) usually has a small bond dissociation energy; upon heating the NHC–CO₂ adducts release CO₂, cleanly generating free NHC, under mild conditions that vary according to the NHC scaffold and wingtip substituents. For example, thermogravimetric measurements under an atmosphere of N₂ for various NHC–CO₂ adducts in the solid state (i.e. solid is the stable condensed phase) revealed thermal decarboxylation at temperatures ranging from 200 °C to as low as 70 °C (162 °C for IMe and 155 °C for IMes)² [344]. Though the decarboxylating ability of masked NHCs depends on electronic effects, Van Ausdall *et al.* showed steric interactions due to the addition of bulky substituents are largely responsible for the decreased onset of thermolysis [344].

NHC–CO₂ adducts were recently used for the *in situ* deposition of free NHC by thermal activation in vacuum [276, 345]. For example, Fuchs *et al.* thermally evaporated CO₂ adducts of IMe, IMes, and IPr at temperatures ranging from 320 K to 350 K onto atomically clean Au(111) surfaces at a base pressure near 10^{−9} mbar. They

²Since it is well-known pressure can inhibit thermal dissociation, these results may vary under vacuum conditions [196].

Figure 9.5: Schematic illustrating the procedure used to deposit free NHCs on Au(111) by PVD in UHV. For clarity, the N–C–N resonance is shown to highlight the delocalization of π electrons, which follows the notation adopted by Nelson and Nolan [334].

presented a scheme similar to the one shown in Figure 9.5, wherein decarboxylation occurs readily and further heating generates a stream of free NHCs. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy showed no evidence of oxygen on the substrate, which is consistent with the adsorption of free NHC rather than its precursor³. In addition, direct-inlet mass spectrometry at 10^{-7} mbar confirmed that decarboxylation occurred under all reaction conditions (305 K to 520 K). Therefore, unlike alkanethiols that undergo dissociative adsorption [243], these experiments indicate that free NHCs are readily produced in vacuum and support the binding of free NHC, rather than its precursor, to the Au(111) surface.

Figure 9.6: Schematic illustrating the generation of free NHCs from NHC•H₂CO₃ salts.

This work relies on the use of (benz)imidazolium hydrogen carbonates with the general formula NHC•H₂CO₃. Hydrogen carbonate salts are often used to produce NHC SAMs due to the convenience with which they can be prepared and stored in

³CO₂ readily desorbs from Au(111) at ambient temperature [72].

air [275]. Similar to the decarboxylation of NHC–CO₂ adducts, thermogravimetric measurements combined with mass spectrometry indicate that the precursors release H₂O and CO₂ at temperatures between 108 and 280 °C depending on the wingtip groups and the electronics at the C₂ position [342]. Free carbenes are therefore readily produced by heating (Figure 9.6), supporting the use of (benz)imidazolium salts to generate high-quality NHC SAMs.

9.3 Adsorption

NHC ligands usually form metal coordination complexes via their divalent carbon atom (C₂). The lone pair that lies along the plane of the ring structure is nucleophilic, or σ -electron-donating, while the p_π orbital is electrophilic with variable π -electron-accepting ability [277]. Such properties make NHCs excellent candidates to form strongly bound metal-organic (organometallic) complexes, especially with late transition metals such as gold [274,276]. In recent years, significant progress has been made towards understanding the mechanisms by which NHCs bind to metals. With reference to the schematic shown in Figure 9.7, I consider key concepts involved in metal-NHC bonding in what follows.

In the usual account of molecular adsorption⁴ on transition metal surfaces, the adsorbate interacts with the HOMO, which has a high electron occupation (e.g. doubly-occupied), and a higher-lying LUMO with little or no electron occupation, as determined by the energy of these orbitals with respect to the Fermi level [72]. In

⁴While weakly-bound physisorbed molecules may retain their gas-phase electronic properties, new electronic states form when a molecule is adsorbed through strong chemical bonds.

Figure 9.7: (a) Upper graphic: lone pair donation into a vacant metal d orbital resulting in the formation of a σ -bond. Lower graphic: the donation of π -electron density from a filled metal d orbital to the LUMO of the ligand, which is an antibonding π^* orbital. (b) The corresponding energy level diagram for the orbital interactions is shown.

Figure 9.7a, this is represented for transition metals (M) that have a partially-filled d -band with non-degenerate d_{z^2} and d_{xz} (or d_{yz}) orbitals that form σ and π bonds with imidazol-2-ylidene, respectively. The σ -electron-donating ability of the sp^2 -hybridized lone pair to the LUMO of the transition metal results in the formation of a σ bond (upper panel in Figure 9.7a) [277,346]. While this dominates the strength of the bonding interaction, contributions of both π -donation from, and π -backdonation into, the π and antibonding π^* orbitals of the NHC group can be significant. With regard to terminology, recall the unhybridized p orbital of the carbene carbon atom is saturated by the aromatic six- π -electron system within the five-membered heterocyclic ring. As a result, the five out-of-plane p atomic orbitals combine to form π and antibonding π^* molecular orbitals, which contain the so-called p_π orbital at the carbene centre that is populated with a fraction of the π -electron density from the heterocycle [346]. The π backbonding interaction (lower graphic in Figure 9.7a) is of particular interest; when an unoccupied antibonding π^* orbital and a doubly-occupied metal d orbital are close in energy they can combine to form a lower-energy bonding orbital (see

energy level diagram in [Figure 9.7b](#)) that strengthens the metal-ligand bond [\[346\]](#). This interaction was initially assumed unimportant, probably because antibonding orbitals are associated with high energies, however σ -bonding and π -backbonding are synergic and it is now understood that π interactions contribute to the overall bond energy [\[277, 347, 348\]](#).

In addition to the energy of the metal orbitals (e.g. d or p) and the number with a suitable symmetry to participate in the interaction, the extent of these interactions (i.e. the amount of charge transfer) depends on the architecture of the NHC ligand [\[346\]](#). Since variations to the NHC scaffold or the addition of bulky substituent groups in the wingtip positions affect the orbital energies and the electron density distribution in the complexes, systematic tuning of key structural parameters can help advance our understanding of the bonding mechanism.

General aspects of the NHC adsorption process are known to involve surface- and adatom-binding, and the formation of flat-lying bis-NHC metal adatom complexes. These binding modes are illustrated in [Figure 9.8](#). DFT calculations by Tang and Jiang showed that NHC adsorption on Au(111) involves the partial lifting of the contact Au atom from its equilibrium position ([Figure 9.8a](#)) due to repulsive steric interactions between the wingtip groups and the surface [\[294\]](#). By examining optimized structures, they concluded that the incorporation of Au adatoms enhances the binding. For NHCs bearing bulky wingtip groups, the most favourable binding mode corresponded to an upright NHC bound to an Au adatom ([Figure 9.8b](#)). In contrast, less sterically bulky NHCs, including the simple methyl-substituted NHC, energetically preferred flat-lying binding motifs, with two ligands attached to an Au adatom ([Figure 9.8c](#)).

Figure 9.8: Structural models illustrating distinct binding modes.

Although numerous experimental and theoretical studies have examined NHC adsorption [276,291–294,345,349–352], the topic remains somewhat controversial. Fuchs *et al.* provided early evidence for the involvement of adatoms [276]. Based on STM measurements and first principles calculations, they suggested that NHCs, including imidazole derivatives bearing methyl substituents (IMe, Figure 9.3a), can fully extract a gold atom from the surface, leaving behind a transient vacancy that is simultaneously filled by an atom in the sub-surface atomic layer. STM data by Papa-georgiou *et al.*, however, indicate that IMe forms flat-lying bis-NHC-metal complexes on Cu(111), Ag(111), and Au(111) [345]. A recent NEXAFS study by Venkataraman *et al.* confirmed that IMe adopts a planar geometry on Au(111) [293]. In addition, they determined that replacing methyl substituents with isopropyl-phenyl groups (IPr, Figure 9.3h) enforced nearly upright orientations, suggesting that bulky wingtip groups prevent complex formation.

Crudden *et al.* provided the first critical examination of the impact of NHC structure on binding and orientation [291]. They vapour-deposited benzannulated carbenes bearing methyl, ethyl, and isopropyl wingtips onto Au(111) and Cu(111). Using STM combined with HREELS, they demonstrated that isopropyl-substituted NHCs adsorb in a perpendicular orientation to the surface, standing upright, while the

less sterically bulky methyl- and ethyl-substituted NHCs form complexes that lie flat on the surface. On the other hand, Cyganik *et al.* recently suggested that the simple methyl-substituted NHC binds to Au(111) in an upright orientation [352]. While this could point to an appreciable difference between solution- and vapour-deposited films, an analysis of the packing density is consistent with iodine contamination.

So far, an important limitation in terms of interpreting the STM data has been that the molecules appear as bright protrusions, with no discernible structure. In the following two chapters, I present high-quality STM images of several distinct NHC binding modes. These include surface- and adatom-bound NHCs attached in upright/tilted geometries, NHC monomers, and flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, which self-assemble into a variety of lattices that differ substantially in terms of mobility, density, stability, and adatom involvement. The physical factors affecting the adsorption and self-assembly behaviour are examined in detail, and found to include surface coverage and substrate temperature, in addition to wingtip structure. The chapters are loosely divided according to the binding mode of the ligand, and place an emphasis on a zig-zag lattice formed by upright NHCs and a non-porous chiral Kagome lattice formed by flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes.

Chapter 10

Self-assembly of upright NHCs on Au(111)

NHCs have found a growing number of applications in the field of materials science ranging from catalysis [279–281,353–355] to biosensing [275,356] and bioimaging [357] to microcontact printing [289] and nanoscale electronic devices [287,288]. When fabricating molecular assemblies for devices such as biosensors, it is of practical importance that the NHCs stand upright, in ordered and densely packed arrays. One family of NHCs with emerging potential are benzimidazoles, which are an important class of NHCs due to the thermal, oxidative, and chemical robustness of their SAMs. This family of NHCs have been examined on Au(111), Cu(111), Ag(111), and Pt(111) surfaces [274,291,293,358], with upright adsorption configurations observed in many NHC-SAM systems.

In addition to upright adsorption geometries, benzimidazole-based NHCs sometimes dimerize to form flat-lying bis-NHC-metal complexes [291,293]. This behaviour

is often exclusive, and possibly impedes their ability to be exploited in functional surface systems. The important role of the wingtip substituents on NHC orientation and self-assembly is addressed in many works [274, 291–294]; however, a general picture of the factors that govern NHC adsorption phenomena is still needed. In this chapter, I present an in-depth STM study of alkylated benzimidazolylidenes on Au(111), providing much needed information on NHC orientation and organization through systematic control of NHC structure, surface coverage, deposition temperature, and annealing temperature. The main results of this study have been submitted for publication and are available on ChemRxiv [359].

10.1 Binding modes

This section introduces several factors that affect the binding and self-assembly of 1,3-diisopropyl benzimidazol-2-ylidene ($\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$), including temperature and surface coverage. Before examining the effect of NHC structure, we place an initial emphasis on this molecule. The NHC films were prepared in vacuum by deposition of the hydrogen carbonate salt, $\text{NHC}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$, onto room-temperature or LN_2 -cooled Au(111) substrates. The resulting films were characterized by UHV-STM at surface coverages up to saturation and after different post-deposition heat treatments. All imaging was performed at LN_2 temperature.

10.1.1 Adatom-mediated self-assembly

Figure 10.1 shows a large-scale STM image of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111). In ordered regions, the self-assembly pattern consists of bright features organized in a zig-zag lattice. The zig-zag lines span a range of 1 to 12 nm and measure an average length of 4 nm,

corresponding to approximately 9 features or molecules. The image was taken after mild annealing¹, to promote organization, near saturation coverage. The surface coverage was defined by the fraction of area occupied by the zig-zag lattice to be approximately 0.8 ML. In the assembly, three ordered domains are observed, labeled as I, II, and III. The domains are rotationally equivalent, reflecting the three-fold symmetry of the surface. Using image thresholding techniques, we measured the packing density in a domain to be $\sim 1.6 \text{ nm}^{-2}$. This value is more than twice the adatom density of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes on Au(111) [359], which suggests that each feature corresponds to an upright/tilted molecule.

Figure 10.1: 0.8ML coverage of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111) formed by depositing the molecules onto the surface at room temperature and subsequently annealing the sample to 75°C . The large-scale STM image shows three rotational domains of the zig-zag lattice (100 mV, 20 pA, $48.0 \times 48.0 \text{ nm}^2$). The inset shows a large vacancy island containing self-assembled $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ molecules (100 mV, 20 pA, $13.5 \times 13.5 \text{ nm}^2$).

Vacancy islands, or etch pits, are also observed in the image. The vacancy islands have lateral dimensions of 2 to 8 nm with shapes that are often quasi-triangular, characteristic for vacancy islands on fcc(111) surfaces [360, 361]. Despite constraints

¹Characteristic of such surfaces are dark regions populated with flat-lying molecules, discussed in detail in subsequent sections.

imposed by their shape and size, most vacancy islands accommodate molecules. The vacancy island shown in the inset, for example, contains NHCs organized in zig-zag rows. Using image thresholding techniques, we determined the STM height difference of NHCs inside the pit compared to those on the terrace to be 231 ± 8 pm. This value corresponds to a depth of one atomic step (236 pm) and is representative for most vacancy islands. Vacancy islands with a monatomic step height have also been observed in STM studies of thiol SAMs, where self-assembly is mediated by gold adatoms [265, 362, 363].

It is well-known that thiol adsorption on Au(111) lifts the herringbone reconstruction, generating the (1×1) surface by the removal of the extra 4.4% Au atoms in the surface layer [364–368]. The mechanism by which the reconstruction is lifted has been widely investigated in terms of adsorbate-induced surface stress [362, 363, 369]. Thiols and other species that withdraw charge from the surface, such as oxygen [370], chlorine [371, 372], and NO_2 [373], generally induce compressive stress, which can relieve the high tensile surface stress in the unreconstructed (1×1) surface. Adatoms generated by the lifting process are key structural components in thiolate SAMs [363]. The lifting process can also be accompanied by the extraction of additional atoms from terraces, which creates vacancies that can coalesce to form vacancy islands [363, 367].

Adsorbates that donate charge to the surface can also create adatoms on, and vacancies in, the surface layer [369]. A notable difference is the effect on the herringbone reconstruction. Charge flow to the surface generally induces a tensile stress in Au(111) that reduces the periodicity of the herringbone reconstruction [369, 374]. We might expect similar behaviour for $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111) due to the direction of charge transfer. In Figure 10.1, however, the corrugation of the herringbone reconstruction is

not clearly identified under the molecular layer. It therefore remains unclear whether the reconstruction is distorted or (partially) lifted by the adsorption process. Despite difficulties in resolving the surface reconstruction on NHC^{*i*Pr}-covered surfaces, some observations can be made here. One interesting aspect is that the vacancy islands in Figure 10.1 appear ordered, separated by an approximate distance of 8 to 10 nm. This value closely corresponds to the distance between elbow sites on the herringbone reconstruction. Similar ordering has been observed upon the adsorption of 1,4-phenylene-diisocyanide on Au(111) [369], which could point to how the Au vacancy islands are created during SAM formation. Their presence also indicates the presence of Au adatoms on the surface layer, which may become incorporated into the self-assembly. In fact, we commonly observe adatom-mediated motifs in NHC SAMs on Au(111).

Figure 10.2: (a) Close-up STM image of the zig-zag lattice (50 mV, 80 pA, $6.0 \times 6.0 \text{ nm}^2$). Here, a positive bias corresponds to empty state imaging. (b) Measurements of the unit cell lattice parameters (b_1 and b_2).

Figure 10.2a shows a high-magnification drift-corrected STM image of the zig-zag

lattice taken near saturation coverage. NHCs in the lattice are assembled in dense packed rows that form a rectangular unit cell. Using image thresholding analysis, we measured the b_1 and b_2 lattice constants to be 1.00 ± 0.01 nm and 2.39 ± 0.01 nm, respectively. These measurements were extracted from Gaussian fitting of the spacing distributions shown in Figure 10.2b. A similar analysis showed that the spacing between nearest-neighbour molecules in the lattice is between 0.54 to 0.57 nm, which is close to two atomic spacings on Au(111).

Figure 10.3: Unit cell for the zig-zag lattice. Adatom positions are shown in red and nearest-neighbour surface atoms are highlighted for visibility.

A possible matrix to describe the zig-zag lattice is $(2, 2|-8, 8)$, as shown in Figure 10.3. The model assumes NHCs bind upright to an adatom that sits above a three-fold hollow site. In a given zig-zag row, the three-fold hollow sites are assumed equivalent (e.g. fcc or hcp). The unit cell spans two rows, where $b_1 = 2\sqrt{3}a_0 = 1.00$ nm and $b_2 = 8a_0 = 2.31$ nm for the lattice constant $a_0 = 0.2884$ nm. The lattice geometry was defined in connection with the lattice parameter measurements shown in Figure 10.2b. The reason why the unit cell spans two rows instead of one is due to the offset (δ) between adjacent rows. To form a repeating pattern, 4 molecules are contained in the unit cell, which corresponds to a molecular density of 1.74 molecules or adatoms per square nanometre. Inside the unit cell, the adsorption sites were chosen based on the measured distance between neighbouring molecules. That is, to

reproduce a separation distance of two atomic spacings.

We find that the $(2, 2|-8, 8)$ matrix model provides the best description over all considered models, such as the $(2, 2|-7, 8)$ matrix. Based on the symmetry of the proposed lattice, only three domains are expected, which is consistent with our experimental observations. These are equivalent rotational domains, where the \mathbf{b}_2 vector points along a close-packed direction, consistent with the domains observed in [Figure 10.1](#). The lattice also has glide-reflection symmetry, since it is superimposable on its mirror image, which limits the number of domains to three. Symmetry considerations further preclude surface site and bridge site binding models. That is, a translation of the lattice cannot establish an equivalent bridge site or surface site binding model. The agreement obtained with the $(2, 2|-8, 8)$ matrix model is therefore based on three-fold hollow site adsorption, or upright NHCs attached to gold adatoms that sit above three-fold hollow sites.

DFT calculations also point to an energetic preference for adatom-mediated motifs over other binding modes. Compared to flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes (-2.57 eV) or $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ molecules attached directly to the surface (-1.73 eV), adatom-bound molecules in upright/tilted configurations are the most stable, with binding energies up to -2.63 eV. DFT simulations for a collection of molecules in this configuration arranged in the $(2, 2|-8, 8)$ lattice are in excellent agreement with the STM data. [Figure 10.4a](#) and [Figure 10.4b](#) show a structural model and STM simulation obtained from the relaxed DFT structure of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ in the proposed zig-zag lattice. A comparison of the images shows that the bright features coincide with the aromatic ring on the $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ backbone. This result provides an interpretation for the contrast observed in the STM data. Similarly, the close agreement with the experimental image

in Figure 10.2a provides further support for the proposed binding model. An important point that I address in subsequent sections is that, in the relaxed assembly, NHCs tilt and rotate into favourable orientations to maximize non-covalent interactions, including vdW, CH/ π and π - π . A result of the intermolecular interactions is that repeating pairings form among NHCs, which is captured in both simulated and experimental STM images by a splitting of the nearest-neighbour distance between molecules. In what follows, I investigate NHC^{iPr} adsorption and self-assembly at step edges to provide further evidence for the involvement of Au adatoms.

Figure 10.4: DFT calculations of NHC^{iPr} in the experimentally observed zig-zag lattice. (a) Relaxed configuration comprising NHC^{iPr} molecules in the adatom attachment geometry. (b) Simulated empty-state STM image.

A comparison of the apparent height of NHCs at steps compared to NHCs on terraces, in the bulk of the zig-zag lattice, provides further evidence for the involvement of Au adatoms. In general, we find that NHCs attach to the upper step edge according to the model shown in Figure 10.5a. When NHC^{iPr} self-assembles at step edges it forms one-dimensional arrays, which may be used to reference the apparent height of NHCs on terraces according to Figure 10.5b. To a first approximation, a height difference of approximately one atomic step (236 pm) would be expected if NHCs on the terrace attach directly to surface atoms. By comparison, adatom-mediated binding would result in a much smaller apparent height difference, Δz . Factors that

contribute to the apparent height difference in STM include geometric and electronic effects, such as differences in tilting of the molecules and electronic effects due to the local coordination at step edges compared to NHCs on terraces. These contributions are estimated and compared with experimental STM height difference measurements in what follows using DFT methods within the traditional Tersoff-Hamann approximation [359].

Figure 10.5: Structural models of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111). (a) Linear array of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ at a step edge. (b) Adatom-bound NHCs on a terrace in proximity to NHCs at a step edge.

The STM image in Figure 10.6a shows two terraces separated by a monatomic step. Along the step edge, $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ molecules form a one-dimensional lattice with a mean separation distance of 0.60 ± 0.03 nm. A similar result is obtained in Figure 10.1, where NHCs decorate the step edges of pits with a spacing of approximately $2a_0$. Due to steric constraints at step edges, the most likely adsorption scenario corresponds to the structural model in Figure 10.5a, which shows a linear array of upright NHCs attached to every other atom at the upper step edge.

The STM image also contains NHCs organized in the zig-zag lattice on the lower terrace. The proximity of the zig-zag lattice to NHCs at the step edge allows for a direct comparison of their heights. Using image thresholding techniques, we estimated the median apparent height of NHCs in the bulk of each array. Compared to NHCs at steps, NHCs in the zig-zag lattice have an apparent height that is reduced by

Figure 10.6: (a) STM image showing the zig-zag lattice and a step edge decorated by NHCs (100 mV, 20 pA, $18.0 \times 18.0 \text{ nm}^2$, 125°C). (b) Simulated STM images of NHC^iPr in the proposed zig-zag lattice (top panel) and step edge packing arrangement (bottom panel). (c) Line profiles taken from the experimental and simulated STM images.

72 ± 11 pm. This value is much smaller than the height of a single atomic step (236 pm), which points to the involvement of Au adatoms. It also agrees with the value recovered from simulated STM images. Figure 10.6b shows STM simulations of the experimentally observed zig-zag lattice and the proposed binding model for NHC^iPr molecules at a step edge. The corresponding height difference is highlighted

in [Figure 10.6c](#). The figure shows line profiles from both experimental and simulated STM images. A value of 57 pm was obtained from the simulated images, which is in remarkable agreement compared to the experimental value of 72 ± 11 pm. The main contributions to the apparent height difference were found to be geometric and electronic effects. These include changes in NHC tilt (NHCs in the zig-zag lattice adopt nearly upright orientations whereas NHCs at step edges may tilt by as much as 21°) and the C–Au bond length [[359](#)]. For comparison, the predicted height difference between a tilted NHC at the step edge and an upright NHC bound to an adatom shows a similar value of approximately 60 pm.

10.1.2 Coverage dependence

Surface coverage is critical to the formation of the zig-zag lattice and, more generally, the binding mode of the NHC ligand. [Figure 10.7a](#) shows an STM image taken after depositing a saturation coverage of NHC^{*i*Pr} onto a room-temperature Au(111) substrate. The image contains pits decorated by upright NHCs and bright features on the terrace. These are upright, adatom-bound NHCs, which form disordered regions and domains of the zig-zag lattice. Molecules in the disordered regions predominantly form trimer packing arrangements, similar to how NHCs in the zig-zag lattice terminate rows (see [section 10.2](#)). Disordered arrangements generally form when the surface coverage is too high or when the temperature is too low since, under these conditions, a molecule may form a defective arrangement and become trapped by the further addition of molecules. Our observations suggest that these arrangements only form at room temperature and saturation coverages and undergo a disorder-to-order transition at temperatures as low as 50 °C, similar to the data shown in [Figure 10.1](#).

Figure 10.7: (a) Au(111) surface saturated with upright, adatom-bound $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ molecules (100 mV, 20 pA, $45.0 \times 45.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) Critical coverage required to form the zig-zag lattice (100 mV, 20 pA, $45.0 \times 45.0 \text{ nm}^2$). Vacancy islands and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes are also identified in the image (dotted circles and arrow, respectively).

Below saturation coverage, the NHC adsorption process is substantially more complicated. Our findings suggest that a critical coverage is needed to produce a chemisorbed layer of NHCs bound to Au adatoms. For $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, the minimum coverage needed to observe the zig-zag lattice is around 0.4 ML, [Figure 10.7b](#). This value was determined experimentally and relates to the process by which $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ removes gold atoms from the surface via adsorbate-induced surface stress modification ([subsection 10.1.1](#)). At this coverage, the surface contains pits, which are found at elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction. These form by the removal of Au atoms from the top surface layer, providing a source for Au adatoms that are incorporated into the zig-zag lattice. A number of other species are also present on the surface, including flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, NHC monomers, and surface-bound NHCs, as determined by their shape and apparent height compared to NHCs in the zig-zag lattice. Our work with methyl- and ethyl-substituted NHCs allowed us to easily identify

(NHC)₂Au complexes in the image. These species were mobile on the surface and occasionally captured in motion by the STM. Less discernible are NHC monomers and surface-bound NHCs, however these features were resolved by inspecting a sequence of STM images obtained in this region and by comparison with low-coverage data.

Figure 10.8: Array of upright, surface-bound NHCs in proximity to a step edge (400 mV, 50 pA, 30.0 × 30.0 nm²). The inset shows a 8.0 × 8.0 nm² detail.

Reducing the surface coverage promoted arrays containing (NHC)₂Au complexes and NHCs bound to surface atoms. At coverages just below 0.4 ML, the surface is devoid of vacancy islands and the zig-zag lattice. Instead, most molecules seem to attach directly to surface atoms. Figure 10.8 shows an STM image of NHC^{*i*Pr} molecules decorating a step edge together with an organized molecular system extending over the lower terrace. Much like the zig-zag lattice, the molecules are self-assembled in a close-packed structure with a density of about 1.6 nm⁻². The main difference here is that the apparent height of NHCs at the step compared to NHCs in the lattice is 237 ± 7 pm. This value corresponds to the height of one atomic step (236 pm), and is consistent with molecules that bind directly to the metal surface.

Figure 10.9: (a) Model showing an NHC^{Pr} molecule attached to the upper step edge together with an NHC attached directly to a surface atom on the lower terrace. The height difference, Δz , was extracted from the simulated STM image for empty states within 0.1 eV above the Fermi energy. (b) Simulated STM image for surface-bound NHCs in a $(3, 3|-7, 7)$ lattice.

In the proposed binding model shown in [Figure 10.9a](#), a height difference (Δz) of approximately one atomic step is expected between an NHC at a step edge and an NHC bound to a surface atom. DFT calculations based on this model predict a height difference of about 219 pm. This value is in close agreement with the experimental value of 237 ± 7 pm, with electronic and geometric effects, such as the C–Au bond length, the partial extraction of Au atoms from the surface, and NHC tilt, contributing to the small departure from a single atomic step. Further DFT calculations were performed assuming a $(3, 3|-7, 7)$ matrix for NHCs in the surface bound lattice, [Figure 10.9b](#). The simulated STM image captures essential features in the experimental data ([Figure 10.8](#)), though it may be possible to find better agreement with a different matrix model. The results of the calculations show that the surface

atoms are partially extracted much further from the surface compared to an isolated molecule, reducing the Δz value to 190 pm. This result is likely related to the proximity between molecules in the lattice, highlighting the effect of molecule-molecule and molecule-substrate interactions on the amount by which the Au atoms are extracted from the surface.

Figure 10.10: Mixed lattice of surface-bound NHCs and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes (100 mV, 20 pA, $40.0 \times 40.0 \text{ nm}^2$). The inset shows a $8.0 \times 8.0 \text{ nm}^2$ detail.

A more exotic lattice was also observed at coverages just below 0.4 ML, shown in [Figure 10.10](#). Whereas small arrays were mobile on the surface and occasionally captured in motion by the STM, with instances found both in this image and in [Figure 10.8](#), large arrays were stable for imaging. A well-resolved STM image is shown in the inset, which contains rows of bright features that are consistent with upright, surface-bound NHCs. That is, their apparent height is lower compared to NHCs at steps by 220 pm, or approximately one atomic step. Along a given row, the molecules are also arranged in pairs, similar to the surface-binding model shown in [Figure 10.9b](#). In the region separating adjacent rows, dimmer features are observed that have three

distinct lobes. These building blocks are more difficult to identify, however they may be $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in flat-lying or bent adsorption geometries. This assignment is based on their shape, height, and availability on the surface. For example, $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes decorate the perimeter of the observed lattices, appearing and disappearing between successive STM images. This observations demonstrates that $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes have sufficient energy to diffuse across Au(111) terraces at 77 K, especially under the influence of the STM tip. Accordingly, we expect the complexes to play an important role in NHC transport and self-assembly.

Finally, [Figure 10.11](#) shows a series of STM images taken in a very low coverage regime. The ordering at step edges is consistent with all other STM data, independent of coverage. We therefore attribute these features to upright/tilted NHCs according to the binding model shown in [Figure 10.5a](#). The STM image also reveals several bright features that preferentially group in pairs at elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction. Since these features have an STM height that is comparable to NHCs at steps, we tentatively assign them to upright, adatom-bound NHCs. A limitation in interpreting the STM data comes from the sensitivity of elbow sites to contamination, due to under-coordinated Au atoms around edge dislocations. However, a number of observations support this assignment. Our STM measurements indicate that $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ molecules decorate most elbow sites, giving rise to a long-range-ordered structure. This binding behaviour is both reproducible and recoverable upon annealing saturated surfaces. Similar behaviour has also been reported in low-coverage self-assembled thiol layers, where elbow sites act as preferential nucleation centres for adatom extraction [375]. It therefore seems more likely that NHCs, as opposed to contaminants, adsorb at elbow sites.

Figure 10.11: Sequence of STM images showing the rapid diffusion of molecules along fcc regions of the herringbone reconstruction (100 mV , 20 pA , $48.0 \times 48.0\text{ nm}^2$, $12.0 \times 15.0\text{ nm}^2$ inset). Molecules at step edges and elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction were immobile between successive images.

A number of distinct molecular species also preferentially adsorb in fcc regions of the herringbone reconstruction, including surface-bound NHCs, flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, and NHC monomers. The inset highlights a small array of surface-bound molecules in proximity to a step edge. A close inspection of the image also shows $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes and three-lobed features, which we attribute to NHC monomers, decorating the perimeter of the array. In contrast to NHCs at steps or elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction, these three species readily diffuse across flat Au(111) terraces at 77 K . The mobility is illustrated here by the comparison of successive STM images, where NHCs continuously aggregate and separate in fcc stacking areas. The molecular packing is mainly disordered, accompanied by few instances of the surface-bound lattice and the mixed lattice. These data suggest that while NHCs may attach to reactive sites first, including step edges and elbow sites, low-coverage films prepared at room temperature also consist of a highly mobile 2D gas-like phase involving several molecular species. The transformation to a single phase of upright NHC molecules with increasing coverage is therefore a complex process, possibly driven by competitive adsorption or chemical reactions.

10.1.3 NHC precursors and magic finger growth

It is not possible to resolve individual features when NHCs are deposited onto LN₂-cooled Au(111) surfaces. The sequence of STM images in Figure 10.12 were acquired by depositing NHC^{*i*Pr} onto a LN₂-cooled Au(111) surface, held at approximately 135 K, in the high coverage regime. Step regions are characterized by the growth of gold nanofingers, which point in the $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction with lengths up to 20 nm and widths in the range of 3 to 8 nm. These nanoscale features form by repeated scanning of the STM tip at 77 K under both extreme tunnelling conditions and very weak tunnelling conditions, at 100 mV and 20 pA. The restructuring process is known as magic finger growth and is common to every NHC system we studied, including NHC^{Me}, NHC^{Et}, and imidazol-based NHCs.

Figure 10.12: Tip-induced modification of step edges on an NHC^{*i*Pr}-covered Au(111) surface (100 mV, 50 pA, 64.0 × 64.0 nm²). Each image has a timestamp marking the time it was acquired.

Magic finger growth arises due to the rearrangement of gold atoms at step edges by atomic manipulation with the STM. It is well-known that the STM tip can be used to modify the structure of step edges on Au(111) under appropriate high-field conditions, at high bias voltages (1.0-1.5 V) and tunnelling currents (30-50 nA) [376, 377]. Repeated scanning over a step edge produces an array of nanofingers that grow in one of the three $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ directions. The fingers have a typical width of 3 to 8 nm and a length

restricted only by the size of the atomically flat terraces. The likely mechanism of surface restructuring is that the high electric field in the tip-sample junction induces the detachment of atoms from step edges, which are then deposited and nucleate to form nanofingers [378]. Nanoscale fingers have also been observed after modification of the Au(111) surface with adsorbed molecules, including (S)-lysine [379] and styrene [380]. The important difference compared to finger formation on clean Au(111) is the need for smaller tunnelling currents (≤ 2 nA), whereby adsorbates facilitate the detachment and displacement of gold atoms from steps.

We observe magic finger growth under extreme tunnelling conditions but also under very weak tunnelling conditions, at 100 mV and 20 pA. The restructuring process also occurs over a wide range of NHC coverages, in both the low and high coverage regimes. Warming the surface shown in [Figure 10.12](#) to room temperature, for example, triggered the formation of the zig-zag lattice. Analogous behaviour is observed in the low-coverage regime, where thermal activation suppresses finger growth and recovers an equivalent room-temperature-prepared film. Since individual molecules are not resolved in magic finger growth experiments, it is difficult to comment on how the NHCs bind to the surface and how they participate in the growth of Au nanofingers. However, the inability to resolve molecules in the STM data may point to the existence of a highly mobile precursor state that preferentially forms on cold surfaces, possibly consisting of physisorbed NHC monomers. Similar to (S)-lysine adsorption [379], it also seems likely that NHC-substrate interactions facilitate the displacement of Au atoms from step edges, triggering the formation of nanofingers under mild tunnelling conditions. Future experiments may be able to identify species involved in magic finger growth by reducing the temperature of the STM.

10.1.4 Effect of heating

Annealing room-temperature-prepared films has an appreciable effect on NHC ordering and orientation. The STM image shown in [Figure 10.13a](#) was generated after heating a saturated monolayer to 50 °C. The image contains large domains of the zig-zag lattice that are separated by vacancy islands. Compared to NHC films prepared at room temperature (e.g. [Figure 10.7a](#)), the ordering is significantly enhanced. With further annealing, vacancy islands progressively disappear and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes form at the expense of the zig-zag lattice. The STM image in [Figure 10.13b](#) shows the effect of annealing to 100 °C. Any vacancy islands left on the surface are very small and difficult to identify by STM. The thermal healing of vacancy islands (e.g. annihilation at steps) is commonly observed upon heating thiol SAMs [381–383], and is accompanied here by a reduction in the number of upright, adatom-bound NHCs. As shown, the zig-zag lattice covers a reduced area in the coverage range of ~ 0.6 ML. The reduction in surface coverage is possibly due to NHC desorption and/or the formation of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, which appear as motion-blurred features around the perimeter of the zig-zag lattices.

The characteristic herringbone reconstruction is also visible in [Figure 10.13b](#) on the bare Au(111) surface regions. As indicated, the $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ molecules adsorb preferentially on fcc regions of the herringbone reconstruction, forming zig-zag domains with sizes and shapes that contour the soliton walls. A careful examination of the STM data shows that the molecules adsorb preferentially along the fcc regions of Au(111), then the narrower hcp-packed regions, and then finally on the soliton walls. Similar to the high-coverage data, the modulation due to the underlying herringbone

Figure 10.13: Large-scale STM images showing the effect of temperature on the binding and self-assembly of NHC^{iPr} on Au(111). (a) NHC^{iPr} -covered surface annealed to 50 °C (100 mV, 20 pA, $45.0 \times 45.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) NHC^{iPr} -covered surface annealed to 100 °C (100 mV, 20 pA, $45.0 \times 45.0 \text{ nm}^2$).

(0.1 to 0.2 Å) is difficult to identify under large arrays. However, bright trimer defects with a 0.5 Å apparent height difference compared to NHCs in the zig-zag lattice are common in regions where soliton walls are expected based on the periodicity of the herringbone. This observation suggests that trimers preferentially form on soliton walls, forming defects in the molecular assemblies on Au(111). By comparison with Figure 10.13a, this observation may also indicate the presence of a distorted surface reconstruction pattern at saturation coverage, where the stress distribution is modified both by vacancy islands and adsorbates [384].

Further heating a saturated surface to 140 °C resulted in large arrays of flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. DFT calculations suggest that these complexes do not form a strong covalent bond with the surface, which could explain their high observed mobility. The array shown in Figure 10.14 was subject to constant structural rearrangement in the boundary regions and was mostly unchanging near its centre. The inset shows

Figure 10.14: Lattice of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes produced by heating an $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ -covered surface to 140°C (100 mV, 30 pA, $32.0 \times 32.0 \text{ nm}^2$). The inset shows a $9.0 \times 9.0 \text{ nm}^2$ detail. A unit cell of complex centres is indicated in black.

an STM image taken in the centre region, providing a detailed look at the structure of the $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. Most complexes are symmetric about their long molecular axis, showing four protrusions corresponding to the wingtip substituents and a bright central protrusion that corresponds to the Au adatom. These features agree with the expected structure of a flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ on Au(111) shown in [Figure 10.15](#). In the next chapter, I provide a much more detailed description of the binding and self-assembly behaviour of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes.

Figure 10.15: DFT-calculated adsorption geometry for a flat-lying bis-NHC-metal complex on Au(111).

The results of these experiments clearly indicate that heating promotes the formation of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes at the expense of upright, adatom-bound NHCs. Although details on the reaction mechanism occurring at high temperature remain unknown, complexes remain on the surface as we cool it to 77 K for imaging, which indicates that the interconversion process occurs irreversibly. This finding is consistent with many nanoparticle- and nanocluster-based publications [349, 385], which have identified bis-NHC-metal complexes as thermodynamic sinks. In general, we also find that the number of complexes on the surface increases with temperature. This relationship allowed for the stable imaging of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, which so far have only been observed for NHCs bearing primary substituents (Me, Et, *n*-Bu) [291–293, 345]. That is, while individual complexes and even small arrays diffuse freely across the surface at 77 K, in sufficient numbers they become spatially constrained and self-assemble into lattices stable for imaging.

10.2 Examination of the zig-zag lattice

This section presents an in-depth study of the $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ zig-zag lattice. By examining the structure of the lattice in more detail, we provide useful information on molecule-molecule and molecule-substrate interactions that steer the self-assembly process.

10.2.1 Nearest-neighbour distance measurements

Figure 10.16a and Figure 10.16b show close-up STM images of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ arranged in the zig-zag lattice. To calculate the nearest-neighbour spacing distribution, we identified the position of each molecule in the lattice using image thresholding methods. In what follows, we compare the spacing between NHCs in the zig-zag lattice to the

spacing between molecules terminating the zig-zag rows, [Figure 10.16c](#).

Figure 10.16: Close-up STM images of the zig-zag lattice with termination patterns that are predominantly (a) left-handed (100 mV, 20 pA, $13.0 \times 13.0 \text{ nm}^2$) and (b) right-handed (100 mV, 20 pA, $13.0 \times 13.0 \text{ nm}^2$). The mask was constructed by considering the largest possible zig-zag pattern in a given row (grey) and then marking the position of any additional molecules (red, blue). (c) The molecules adopt a chiral arrangement when an additional NHC terminates a zig-zag row.

NHCs in the zig-zag lattice show an average separation distance of $0.58 \pm 0.04 \text{ nm}$. This value was extracted from Gaussian fitting of the distribution of nearest-neighbour distances shown in the top panel of [Figure 10.17a](#). It also agrees with expected value of $2a_0 = 0.577 \text{ nm}$ from the proposed $(2, 2|-8, 8)$ matrix model. Interestingly, a further examination of the spacing along zig versus zag directions showed two distinct peaks separated by approximately 0.03 nm. This splitting is examined in detail in the following section, and may be relevant in understanding how NHCs attach to the end of zig-zag rows.

An additional NHC often attaches to end of a zig-zag row, disrupting the self-assembly pattern. The possible packing arrangements are related by symmetry operations, [Figure 10.16c](#), and include two chiral domains. An examination of the STM data shows no indication for an enantiomeric preference. For example, in [Figure 10.16a](#) the packing is predominantly left-handed and in [Figure 10.16b](#) the packing

is predominantly right-handed. The STM data also show a non-random dispersion of terminating NHCs, which provides some insight into the growth and self-assembly process. In most cases, the terminating NHCs alternate between opposite ends of adjacent zig-zag rows. The most likely explanation for this type of packing is that steric constraints prevent the placement of NHCs at the same end of adjacent rows.

Figure 10.17: (a) Normalized histograms showing the distribution of nearest-neighbour distances for adjacent sites in the zig-zag array (top panel) and trimer arrangements formed when zig-zag rows are terminated by an additional NHC (lower panel). (b) Adsorption models for zig-zag segments that are terminated by an additional NHC. The adatom positions are shown in red and the nearest-neighbour surface atoms are highlighted for visibility.

To study the effect on spacing, we evaluated the nearest-neighbour distribution for subsets containing three NHCs, following Figure 10.16c. As shown in the lower panel of Figure 10.17a, the average spacing determined from curve fitting is 0.55 ± 0.06 nm. This value is very close to two atomic spacings on Au(111), which points to adsorption scenarios based on the models shown in Figure 10.17b. The small difference of 0.03 nm could arise from variations in NHC tilt/rotation. In what follows, we show that spacing between adjacent molecules in the zig-zag lattice is not uniform, and that a similar spacing of 0.53-0.54 nm arises due to intermolecular interactions between

adjacent NHCs.

10.2.2 Bimodal splitting

Figure 10.18 shows a high-magnification drift-corrected STM image of the zig-zag lattice taken near saturation coverage. In the lattice, NHC^{iPr} molecules attach to adatoms that sit above three-fold hollow sites. Structural models have previously indicated that the molecules adopt nearly upright orientations with a nearest-neighbour distance of just two atomic spacings. Here, we consider small structural distortions in the self-assembly pattern that may arise due to molecule-molecule and molecule-substrate interactions.

Figure 10.18: High-magnification STM image of the zig-zag lattice (50 mV, 80 pA, $15.9 \times 10.8 \text{ nm}^2$). The inset shows a $6.0 \times 6.0 \text{ nm}^2$ detail.

Using image thresholding techniques, we measured the distance between adjacent sites in the zig-zag pattern. Figure 10.19a shows the histogram of nearest-neighbour distances. The distribution has two distinct peaks at 0.54 ± 0.01 and 0.57 ± 0.01 nm, which correspond to the distance between zig and zag line segments indicated in Figure 10.18. These values were obtained from bimodal curve fitting, giving a small

separation distance of 30 ± 9 pm. To minimize the effect of thermal drift in the measurement, the STM image was acquired under low drift conditions (using active drift compensation) and further corrected using a post-processing technique based on image registration. As shown, the post-processing correction had only a small effect on the peak locations and did not affect the observed bimodal behaviour. Small (5% changes) in the piezo calibration factors also did not affect the bimodal behaviour.

(a) Intermolecular spacing between NHCs

(b) Even versus odd zig-zag rows

Figure 10.19: (a) Normalized histograms showing the drift-distorted and drift-corrected distribution of nearest-neighbour distances for adjacent sites in the zig-zag lattice. (b) Normalized Zig and zag spacing measurements.

We also consider the nearest-neighbour spacing distribution along even and odd zig-zag rows. On the unreconstructed Au(111) surface, zig-zag rows alternate between fcc and hcp hollow adsorption sites. DFT calculations of NHC-Au adatom adsorption on Au(111) show the fcc hollow site is energetically preferred to the hcp hollow site by about 14 meV, which could affect the structure of the self-assembly pattern (e.g. how NHCs tilt/rotate in adjacent zig-zag rows). While in [Figure 10.19a](#) the zig and zag distributions are approximately Gaussian, an examination of the separate contributions, [Figure 10.19b](#), seems to suggest that the zig and zag distributions are a mixture of two normal distributions. The separation distance between zig and zag line

segments is 30 ± 11 pm when considering even rows and 33 ± 9 pm when considering odd rows. The close correspondence between these values makes it difficult to determine whether there is a significant difference between adsorption sites along even and odd rows. Further analysis with an increased number of samples could lead to more accurate and representative results. Considering, however, that $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ adsorption likely does not lift the herringbone reconstruction, NHCs in even and odd rows may not alternate between fcc and hcp adsorption sites, thereby limiting the conclusions that can be drawn from the analysis.

The observed bimodal spacing could be caused by the Au(111) herringbone reconstruction, which has a 4.34% uniaxial compression along one of the three closed-packed $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ directions. Although the reconstruction is not easily identified under the molecular layers, its presence could give rise to unequal zig and zag line segments that measure 0.55 and 0.57 nm, which are in close agreement with the experimental data. Its presence would also interrupt the alternating arrangement of fcc and hcp adsorption sites between adjacent zig-zag rows. On the $22 \times \sqrt{3}$ surface reconstruction, soliton walls separate wide fcc-like and narrow hcp-like stacking regions [319, 321]. These regions are difficult to identify at saturation coverage. However, the herringbone reconstruction may be substantially distorted due to adsorbate-induced surface stress and further obscured by zig-zag domains extending over regions where the stacking is predominantly fcc or hcp. Accordingly, the close correspondence in spacing for even and odd zig-zag rows is perhaps not surprising. To further examine the effect of the herringbone reconstruction on the structure of the zig-zag lattice, the following section considers STM data taken at sub-monolayer coverages, where the reconstruction is visible.

10.2.3 Effect of the herringbone reconstruction

Sub-monolayer coverages of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111) allowed us to study the effect of the herringbone reconstruction on the spacing between NHCs in the zig-zag lattice. The reconstruction is visible in STM images of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}/\text{Au}(111)$ films that contain bare surface regions. This includes films with and without vacancy islands, prepared below saturation coverage (e.g. Figure 10.7b) or by annealing saturated films. The STM images shown in Figure 10.20 were acquired by heating an $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ -covered surface to temperatures of 100-120 °C. In Figure 10.20a and Figure 10.20b, the orientation of the lattice remains fixed while the compression direction changes orientation, pointing along either the zig or zag line segments where the unit cells are indicated. In what follows, we analyze the intermolecular spacing between NHCs in the vicinity of these unit cells.

Figure 10.20: STM images showing the $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ zig-zag lattice on Au(111) together with the herringbone reconstruction visible in the bare surface regions. (a) Saturated monolayer heated to 100 °C (100 mV, 20 pA, $45.0 \times 45.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) Saturated monolayer heated to 120 °C (100 mV, 20 pA, $30.0 \times 30.0 \text{ nm}^2$). Rectangles define the unit cell of the zig-zag lattice and compression directions are indicated by arrows.

The herringbone reconstruction has a 4.34 % uniaxial compression in the top surface layer that runs along a close-packed direction perpendicular to the soliton walls. Depending on its orientation relative to the zig-zag lattice, the compression direction can align with either the d_{zig} or d_{zag} line segments, as shown in Figure 10.21a. An examination of the available STM data showed no evidence for the third domain where the compression direction runs at an angle to d_{zig} and d_{zag} . While this could suggest a preference due to atomic spacing, with favourable configurations occurring when adjacent molecules are slightly closer together, it is only a preliminary finding since the number of images in which the herringbone reconstruction is clearly resolved is limited.

Figure 10.21: (a) Unit cell of the zig-zag lattice shown in relation to compression directions, indicated by arrows that run along close-packed rows. (b) Histograms showing the total nearest-neighbour distribution (blue) and the zig (green) and zag (orange) components from upper (dashed) and lower (dotted) regions of the NHC^{zPr} zig-zag lattice.

The effect of the herringbone reconstruction on the structure of the zig-zag lattice in Figure 10.20a is shown in Figure 10.21b. In the vicinity of the upper unit cell, the compression direction is aligned with d_{zig} line segments. Near the lower unit

cell, the compression direction is aligned with d_{zag} line segments. The histograms show the distribution of nearest-neighbour distances in each region, as well as the total zig and zag contributions. Surprisingly, the results show that the orientation of the herringbone reconstruction with respect to the zig-zag lattice has no effect on d_{zig} and d_{zag} measurements (0.53 ± 0.02 nm and 0.59 ± 0.02 nm). Similar results were also obtained from [Figure 10.20b](#), reducing the possible role of systematic error. The reason why zig and zag spacing measurements remain exactly the same, despite changes in compression direction, remains an open question. As explained in the following section, these results are unlikely to be caused by scan distortions. One possibility could be related to how the NHCs tilt/rotate in the lattice.

10.2.4 NHC–NHC coupling

The STM image in [Figure 10.22](#) shows two terraces separated by a monatomic step. The lower terrace contains three domains of the zig-zag lattice, which are related by 120° rotations. At the step edge, NHCs are highly organized in a one-dimensional lattice. A comparison of the intermolecular spacing between NHCs in these arrays provides a useful means for assessing small structural distortions in the zig-zag lattice. By comparison of the results with a distorted lattice model and with DFT, we also provide insight into the intermolecular interactions between NHCs in the zig-zag lattice.

[Figure 10.23](#) compares the distance between adjacent sites in the zig-zag lattice to the spacing between NHCs along the step edges. The top panel shows a histogram of nearest-neighbour distances in the zig-zag lattice. While the total distribution is approximately Gaussian (with peaks between 0.55 and 0.56 nm for each domain),

Figure 10.22: STM image of an $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}/\text{Au}(111)$ film that was heated to $125\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (100 mV , 20 pA , $60.0 \times 60.0\text{ nm}^2$). The $30.0 \times 30.0\text{ nm}^2$ detail shows a linear array of NHCs at the step edge and three domains of the zig-zag lattice on the lower terrace.

the bimodal behaviour observed in [Figure 10.19a](#) is recovered when the zig and zag line segments are plotted separately. In each domain, the zig-zag pattern alternates between short and long zig and zag line segments. The distributions obtained by combining measurements in the three domains are approximately Gaussian, centred at 0.53 ± 0.03 and $0.58 \pm 0.02\text{ nm}$, respectively. This bimodal behaviour appears to be direction independent, showing no appreciable differences in peak position due to the orientation of the lattice with respect to the fast scan direction. These data suggest that scan distortions do not significantly affect structure.

The bottom panel of [Figure 10.23](#) shows a histogram of the spacing between NHCs at steps. The average nearest-neighbour distance determined from curve fitting is $0.60 \pm 0.03\text{ nm}$, which corresponds to a distance of two atomic spacings on $\text{Au}(111)$. This value also agrees with the $0.58 \pm 0.02\text{ nm}$ spacing between NHCs in the zig-zag pattern. The close agreement between these values highlights the reliability of

Figure 10.23: Histograms showing the distribution of nearest-neighbour distances for NHCs in the zig-zag lattice and NHCs at steps. The top panel shows the total distribution (blue) as well as the zig (green) and zag (orange) components for NHCs in the zig-zag lattice. The bottom panel shows the spacing between NHCs at the step edge.

the proposed NHC binding models, which specify the same intermolecular spacing of $2a_0$ for molecules at steps and in the zig-zag lattice. In what follows, we consider small departures from the proposed $(2, 2|-8, 8)$ matrix model to investigate why some NHCs might have a reduced intermolecular separation distance in the range of 0.53 to 0.54 nm.

The slight deviation from the ideal packing structure is considered assuming NHCs are displaced from equilibrium three-fold hollow sites towards high symmetry (top, bridge) sites by an amount δ , as shown in [Figure 10.24](#). The displacement to intermediate sites could involve the displacement of the Au adatoms or it could be caused by tilt.

Figure 10.24: Position between a three-fold hollow site and a bridge site on an fcc(111) surface.

To examine the structural dependence on δ , we considered distorted zig-zag patterns based on the $(2, 2|-8, 8)$ matrix model. In the configuration shown in [Figure 10.25](#), NHCs in three-fold hollow sites are displaced towards bridge sites to create zig and zag line segments (d_{zig} and d_{zag}) with dissimilar lengths, consistent with the observed bimodal behaviour.

Figure 10.25: Zig-zag pattern with adjusted spacing. Au adatom positions are shown in red and nearest-neighbour surface atoms are highlighted for visibility.

The length of the zig and zag line segments are

$$d_{zig} = \left(4a_0^2 - 2\sqrt{3}a_0\delta + \delta^2\right)^{1/2}, \quad (10.1)$$

and

$$d_{zag} = \left(4a_0^2 + \delta^2\right)^{1/2}, \quad (10.2)$$

respectively. These vary from $2a_0$ when $\delta = 0$ to $1.71a_0$ and $2.02a_0$ when δ equals the

distance between a three-fold hollow site and a bridge site, $\sqrt{3}a_0/6$. The displacement parameter δ also does not influence the lattice parameters, such that $b_1 = 2\sqrt{3}a_0$ and $b_2 = 8a_0$, in keeping with the experimental data.

Figure 10.26: Histograms showing nearest-neighbour distance distributions for NHCs in the zig-zag lattice. The top panel shows experimental data and middle panel and lower panels show simulated data generated by drawing 66 and 7000 random samples from normal distributions with means and variances chosen to match experiment.

Experimental results are compared with d_{zig} and d_{zag} in Figure 10.26. The top panel plots zig-zag lattice measurements from Figure 10.23 and the bottom panels show simulation results. Zig and zag distributions were sampled from normal distributions centred at d_{zig} and d_{zag} , as determined by δ , with widths chosen match to experiment. Excellent agreement with experiment is obtained when $\delta = 0.6\delta_{max}$, where $\delta_{max} = \sqrt{3}a_0/6$ is the distance between a hollow site and a bridge site.

The middle panel considers a small sample size, chosen to equal the number of experimental data points. The total distribution is approximately Gaussian and centred at 0.56 ± 0.04 nm. It has zig and zag components that peak at 0.53 ± 0.03 nm and 0.58 ± 0.02 nm, respectively. The bottom panel shows a weak bimodal pattern that was recovered by increasing the number of samples. It has zig and zag components determined from fitting to be 0.53 ± 0.03 nm and 0.58 ± 0.03 nm, respectively. The close correspondence between theory and experiment seems to support this model. A possible explanation for the displacement to intermediate sites could be that NHCs tilt into favourable orientations that maximize non-covalent interactions, forming repeated pairings.

Figure 10.27: Structural models of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111). (a) Side view and (b) top view showing three molecules in a zig-zag row. (c) Simulated empty-state STM image of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ in the zig-zag lattice.

These findings are supported by DFT calculations [359], which show that molecule-molecule interactions play an important role in $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ self-assembly. Non-covalent interactions, including vdW interactions, $\pi - \pi$ stacking between aromatic rings, and CH- π hydrogen bonding, increase the binding energy of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ molecules in the self-assembly by as much as 0.16 eV/NHC. In addition to the added stability,

non-covalent interactions determine the equilibrium geometry of the (2, 2|−8, 8) zig-zag lattice. DFT calculations reveal that, in the relaxed assembly, NHCs and their wingtip groups tilt and rotate into favourable orientations to maximize non-covalent interactions. The deformations are subtle, shown in [Figure 10.27a](#) and [Figure 10.27b](#) for a single zig-zag row. Important considerations include the configuration of the wingtip substituents, which consist of a methine (CH) group pointing towards the surface and a methyl group oriented to promote ordering via CH– π interactions with the aromatic group of an adjacent NHC. Within each line, the NHCs also undergo a small tilt and rotation that breaks the translational symmetry of the lattice, resulting in closely spaced intermolecular separation distances. Measurements taken from the simulated STM data in [Figure 10.27c](#) revealed d_{zig} and d_{zag} distances of 0.57 and 0.58 nm, respectively. The small difference of 0.01 nm captures the essential behaviour observed in the experimental data, highlighting the important role of molecule-molecule interactions on the structure of the zig-zag lattice.

10.3 Effect of NHC structure on ordering

This section investigates the effect of wingtip size on NHC orientation and ordering. The wingtip substituents determine the propensity for NHCs to bind in either upright or flat-lying adsorption geometries. They also play a key role in intermolecular NHC–NHC interactions, facilitating the formation of highly ordered structures. In what follows, we examine structural variants of NHC^{*i*Pr} produced by the addition (NHC^{*t*Bu}) and deletion (^{Et}NHC^{*i*Pr}) of methyl groups. We also examine overlays prepared with its perdeuterated analogue (NHC^{*i*Pr}– d_{14}).

10.3.1 Fine-tuning the intermolecular interactions between NHCs

To determine whether CH- π interactions impact the ordering in NHC^{*i*Pr} films, we prepared its deuterated analogue, NHC^{*i*Pr}-*d*₁₄, by substituting hydrogen atoms of the isopropyl wingtips for deuterium. In aggregate and condensed matter systems, the H/D isotope effect for the CH- π interaction is known to be significant [386–389]. Here, we expect the modification to reduce the ability of the wingtip groups to create CH- π hydrogen bonds [359] without significantly impacting steric interactions of the NHC ligand. Geometric changes to the ligand are presumably negligible since vibrationally averaged CD bonds are only ~ 0.005 Å longer than CH bonds [389]. Any differences in the self-assembly of protonated and deuterated NHCs should therefore reflect the diminished strength of CD- π interactions compared to CH- π interactions.

Figure 10.28: Effect of CH- π interactions on NHC^{*i*Pr} self-assembly. (a) NHC^{*i*Pr} film prepared on a room-temperature Au(111) substrate (100 mV, 20 pA, 45.0 \times 45.0 nm²). (b) NHC^{*i*Pr}-*d*₁₄ on Au(111) at a similar surface coverage (800 mV, 30 pA, 45.0 \times 45.0 nm²). (c) Close-up STM image of the NHC^{*i*Pr}-*d*₁₄ film (1.0 V, 20 pA, 30.0 \times 30.0 nm²).

The STM images in Figure 10.28a and Figure 10.28b show NHC^{*i*Pr} and NHC^{*i*Pr}-*d*₁₄ films prepared on room-temperature Au(111) substrates. Both samples show a similar number of vacancy islands, which suggests the adsorption processes are similar and involve Au adatoms. Based on an analysis of STM height measurements in these

images, we attribute the bright features in [Figure 10.28b](#) to upright, adatom-bound NHCs. Like $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, adatoms were only incorporated into the assembly above a critical coverage. In the low-coverage regime, features with a much lower apparent height compared to NHCs at step edges, including NHC monomers and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, were observed on terraces. These species likely make-up the regions with dimmer contrast in [Figure 10.28b](#), similar to $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ films prepared below saturation coverage. Unlike $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, however, $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}-d_{14}}$ does not self-assemble into ordered lattices on Au(111).

The molecular arrangement of upright, adatom-bound $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}-d_{14}}$ molecules is disordered, as shown in [Figure 10.28c](#). Interestingly, no differences in ordering occurred upon heating the sample to 50 °C. The lack of ordering is in stark contrast to $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, which self-assembles into a zig-zag lattice under a wide variety of experimental conditions. In considering factors that might affect ordering, we note that $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}-d_{14}}$ films in [Figure 10.28](#) were prepared under the same experimental conditions with a similar surface coverage. Considering also the adsorption behaviour observed at low coverages and upon heating, it seems unlikely that the difference in ordering is related to the deposition process, molecular coverage, chemical cleanliness, or thermal treatment. Our interpretation of these results is that the loss of order occurs due to the isotope effects of deuteration, stressing the importance of CH- π interactions in stabilizing the zig-zag lattice.

10.3.2 Effect of increasing the steric bulk

To examine the effect of wingtip structure on $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ binding and self-assembly, we prepared and deposited the structural variant $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$, [Figure 10.29a](#). The STM

image in Figure 10.29b shows the overlay that forms when $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ is deposited onto a room temperature Au(111) surface at saturation coverage. Several structural motifs can be identified that are isomorphic with those observed on $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ -covered surfaces, including trimers, lines, and zig-zag lines. The most common structural motif are short, one-dimensional lines running parallel to the close-packed $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ directions. On average, each line consists of 3-5 molecules separated by 0.57 ± 0.05 nm, or two atomic spacings on Au(111). These results were determined by Gaussian fitting the experimental data shown in Figure 10.29c.

Figure 10.29: (a) Schematic structure of $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$. (b) STM image of a $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ film prepared on a room-temperature Au(111) surface at saturation coverage (100 mV, 20 pA, $30.0 \times 30.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (c) Histograms showing the number of molecules in each one-dimensional array (top panel) and the corresponding distance distribution between neighbouring $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ molecules (bottom panel).

The small distance separating adjacent $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ molecules suggests that their adsorption orientation on Au(111) is upright. To determine whether the molecules bind to adatoms or surface sites, we compared the STM heights for $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ at steps and on terraces. The STM image in Figure 10.30a shows a monatomic step separating two terraces. Like $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, the molecules adopt distinct binding modes on terraces, giving rise to regions with bright and dim contrast. Features observed in the dim

regions are analogous to those observed in $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Pr}}$ films and may be the result of flat-lying NHCs, surface-bound NHCs, or contamination. For comparison, the STM height increases in bright regions by approximately 220 pm. Further analysis shows that bright molecules on the lower terrace have approximately the same apparent height compared to NHCs at the step edge, which form a well-defined array with a characteristic spacing of $2a_0$. Accordingly, the most likely adsorption scenario corresponds to the structural model shown in Figure 10.5, where $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ attaches to atoms in the upper row at steps and to adatoms in the bright regions on terraces.

Figure 10.30: (a) STM image of an $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}/\text{Au}(111)$ film that was heated to 50 °C (100 mV, 20 pA, $28.0 \times 28.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) 50 : 50 co-deposition of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ onto a room-temperature $\text{Au}(111)$ surface (600 mV, 20 pA, $30.0 \times 30.0 \text{ nm}^2$).

To verify Au adatom involvement, we performed a 50 : 50 co-deposition of $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on $\text{Au}(111)$. As shown in Figure 10.30b, the NHCs phase-separate, with $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ self-assembling into the characteristic zig-zag lattice and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ forming one-dimensional arrays along the $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ directions. Using image thresholding techniques, we determined the height difference between NHCs in the bulk of these arrays

to be 56 ± 9 pm. This value is much smaller than the height of an atomic step, which is consistent with both $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ in upright orientations bound to Au adatoms. It is also in close agreement with the 45 pm height difference obtained through STM simulations of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ in the proposed zig-zag lattice and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ in the linear arrangement shown in Figure 10.31 [359]. The simulations considered empty states at a low bias voltage, within 100 meV above the Fermi energy, to minimize the effect of LDOS variations. Under these conditions, the main contributions to the height difference were found to be changes in the C–Au bond length and the vertical position of the Au atom. The close agreement between theory and experiment provides strong evidence that $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ shares the $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ attachment geometry, binding in upright orientations on adatoms. This assignment is further supported by DFT calculations, which show that NHCs with bulky substituents, including $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$, energetically prefer binding to Au adatoms in upright/tilted orientations on Au(111) to minimize steric interactions with the surface [359]. Accordingly, it appears that the effect of the additional methyl groups is mainly reflected in differences in the molecular organization of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ SAMs.

Figure 10.31: (a) Side view and (b) top view of adatom-bound $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ molecules in the proposed linear arrangement. In the considered adsorption geometry, the $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ molecules stand upright with an intermolecular spacing of every other atom. Each molecule is also attached to gold adatom that sits above a three-fold hollow site.

Unlike $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, which self-assembles into two-dimensional structures on Au(111),

NHC^{tBu} SAMs maintain only short-range one-dimensional order. The difference in molecular ordering could be related to enhanced NHC–NHC interactions. The presence of the additional of methyl groups should result in stronger intermolecular interactions, which may freeze-in a disordered structure by impeding the critical ability of the molecules to adjust/rectify their positions in an ensemble during the self-assembly process. Another difference between these two ligands is their binding energy. The DFT-calculated binding energies for upright, adatom-bound NHC^{iPr} and NHC^{tBu} molecules are -2.63 and -2.15 eV, respectively [359]. Such a high difference in binding energy, amounting to approximately 0.5 eV, could offer an alternative explanation for the observed differences in molecular ordering. Whereas NHC^{iPr} films are thermally stable on Au(111), showing a dramatic increase in ordering upon heating to 50 °C, heating NHC^{tBu} films did not improve ordering and instead resulted in appreciable NHC desorption between 50 and 100 °C. If high temperatures (>50 °C) are required to promote molecular self-assembly, then NHC^{tBu} might be unable to form ordered, equilibrium structures due to its poor thermal stability on Au(111).

10.3.3 Effect of decreasing the steric bulk

To examine the effect of decreasing steric bulk, we prepared and deposited the structural variant ^{Et}NHC^{iPr}. The carbene structure is similar to NHC^{iPr}, [Figure 10.32a](#), with the only difference being the deletion of a single methyl group on one the wingtips. The STM image in [Figure 10.32b](#) shows a representative surface region after depositing a monolayer of ^{Et}NHC^{iPr} onto Au(111) at room temperature. By comparison with the structural model shown in [Figure 10.32c](#), we identify each feature in the self-assembly pattern to be a flat-lying (NHC)₂Au complex. The structural

model well-reproduces both the size and shape of the features, with the bright central protrusion corresponding to the position of the metal Au adatom and the four neighbouring protrusions corresponding to the wingtip substituents.

Figure 10.32: (a) Schematic structure of $\text{Et}^t\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$. (b) STM image of $\text{Et}^t\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ film prepared on a room-temperature Au(111) surface near saturation coverage (400 mV, 30 pA, $8.0 \times 8.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (c) Side and top views of a flat-lying (NHC)₂Au complex on Au(111).

The result that $\text{Et}^t\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ forms a single phase of flat-lying (NHC)₂Au complexes on Au(111) is remarkable considering the minor change in wingtip structure. The energetic preference for flat-lying (NHC)₂Au complexes is captured by total energy calculations, which predict surface- and adatom-bound NHCs in upright/tilted geometries to be less stable in comparison [359]. These calculations also predict a significant energetic preference for the (NHC)₂Au complex geometry for methyl- and ethyl-substituted NHCs. As well, characterization with STM shows that these NHCs exhibit very similar binding and self-assembly behaviour compared to $\text{Et}^t\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$. The study of flat-lying (NHC)₂Au complexes, and the lattices they form, is the main focus of the next chapter.

Chapter 11

Self-assembly of flat-lying NHCs on Au(111)

Much of our research efforts have focused on alkylated benzimidazolylidenes, which are an important class of NHCs due to the thermal, oxidative, and chemical robustness of their SAMs. Their utility applies to upright binding modes; however, many NHCs lie flat on the surface. In this chapter I present an in-depth study of flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, including the mechanisms by which these structures form and self-assemble into lattices, by means of scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) and density functional theory (DFT). In particular, I focus on benzannulated NHCs bearing methyl and ethyl wingtip groups (NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et}), which react with Au atoms on room temperature Au(111) substrates to form $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes.

11.1 Introduction

The NHC films were prepared on room temperature Au(111) substrates by vacuum deposition of hydrogen carbonate salts of the general form $\text{NHC}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3$, Figure 11.1. The resulting films were imaged by STM at 77 K at coverages from sub-monolayer to saturation. Similar to how $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ adsorbs on Au(111) at low coverages, NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} show an initial preference for step edges, where the molecules adopt upright geometries. Rather than adopting upright geometries on terraces, however, the NHCs form flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, which diffuse either as single molecular units or collectively in small arrays at 77 K. Surface diffusion was readily apparent below saturation coverage, where small, ordered structures of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes were occasionally captured in motion by the STM. At or near saturation coverage, the NHCs became spatially confined on the surface, which limited NHC transport and improved our ability to distinguish and resolve single complexes. Further deposition gave rise to a multilayer, with $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes still visible on the surface, which suggests that the UHV-deposited films do not undergo a transformation from flat-lying to upright geometries with increasing coverage.

Figure 11.1: Schematic showing the production of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes on Au(111).

The following section provides a detailed discussion of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. First I demonstrate that Au adatoms participate in the formation of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. I also consider the mechanism by which NHCs combine with Au adatoms on Au(111).

In subsequent sections, I examine a rich variety of self-assembled structures through careful control of the surface coverage and annealing temperature with an emphasis on film structure and thermal stability.

11.2 NHC-metal complexes

Several groups have studied the effect of wingtip structure on NHC binding. Many studies have found that NHCs with limited steric bulk favour flat-lying adsorption geometries [291, 293, 294, 345]. Other studies have suggested that NHCs bearing a variety of substituents, including methyl wingtip groups, adopt upright orientations [276, 292, 352], leaving some debate over the binding mode. Challenges in the determination of the binding mode seem to be related to challenges in the interpretation of STM data. So far, the structure of flat-lying bis-NHC complexes has not been resolved in sufficient detail to unambiguously determine orientation or adatom involvement.

In what follows, we demonstrate that NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} form flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes when deposited onto a room-temperature Au(111) surface. Clear evidence for Au adatom involvement is provided based on (i) the structure of the observed features, (ii) total energy calculations, (iii) the observation of pits, and (iv) voltage-dependent imaging experiments.

11.2.1 High-magnification STM images

High-magnification STM images of NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} on Au(111) are shown in [Figure 11.2a](#) and [Figure 11.2b](#), respectively. The features show a bright central protrusion and appear symmetric about the long molecular axis in both images. Based

on their shape and approximate dimensions, we attribute these features to $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. To support this assignment, we also compare the STM images with DFT calculations. Details on the computational approach method are summarized in [359], where we examine a closely related system.

Figure 11.2: Close-up STM images of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes taken at 77 K. Both the (a) NHC^{Me} film (100 mV, 3.5 nA, $3.0 \times 3.0 \text{ nm}^2$) and the (b) NHC^{Et} film (100 mV, 60 pA, $3.0 \times 3.0 \text{ nm}^2$) were prepared near saturation coverage by flash deposition onto a room-temperature Au(111) surface.

The following four configurations were examined by DFT: (i) an upright NHC bound to a surface atom, (ii) an upright NHC bound to an adatom, (iii) an adatom-bound NHC in a tilted configuration, and (iv) a flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex. These are labeled as atop, adatom upright, adatom tilted, and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex for NHC^{Me} on Au(111) in Figure 11.3. In the conformations we have considered, the adatom resides above a three-fold hollow site, which is predicted to be the most stable binding geometry compared to atop or bridge sites.

STM simulations corresponding to the adsorption configurations for NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} are shown in Figure 11.4. NHCs in upright configurations show a bright protrusion associated with their aromatic backbone, which may be relevant when

Figure 11.3: Binding motifs for NHC^{Me} on Au(111). The adsorption configurations labeled atop, adatom upright, adatom tilted, and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex were relaxed by DFT.

identifying features observed at step edges and elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction. In flat-lying configurations, the $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes formed by NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} show a bright central feature that corresponds to the Au metal atom. The simulated STM images also show that the wingtip structure is better resolved for NHC^{Et} complexes compared to NHC^{Me} complexes, which is consistent with the STM imaging. Overall, we find excellent agreement between these results and the experimental data in [Figure 11.2](#).

Figure 11.4: Constant-current STM simulations within the Tersoff-Hamann approximation corresponding to occupied states within 0.1 eV of the Fermi level for NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} in different adsorption configurations. Scale bars show apparent height variations in Ångström.

The propensity for NHCs to bind in either upright or flat-lying configurations is also captured by total energy calculations. Figure 11.5 shows the DFT-calculated binding energy for NHC^{Me} , NHC^{Et} , ${}^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ on Au(111) in the considered adsorption configurations. In contrast to $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$, which show an energetic preference for the adatom tilted configuration, the flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex configuration is the most stable binding mode for NHC^{Me} , NHC^{Et} , and ${}^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$. These results are consistent with our observations that $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ stand upright when deposited onto a room-temperature Au(111) surface while NHC^{Me} , NHC^{Et} , and ${}^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ form $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes.

Figure 11.5: Binding energies for NHC^{Me} , NHC^{Et} , ${}^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ on Au(111) obtained by DFT. As the size of the wingtip groups increases, the energetically preferred binding mode transitions from flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes for NHC^{Me} , NHC^{Et} , and ${}^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ to mono-NHC-gold adatom complexes in upright/tilted configurations for $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$.

The binding energies for NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} complexes reported in Figure 11.5 are -2.53 eV and -2.64 eV, respectively. These values are roughly equivalent to the adsorption energy of four benzene molecules on Au(111). Benzene physisorbs on Au(111) with an adsorption energy of about -0.73 eV [390]. Similar to the important role van der Waals (vdW) interactions play in its interaction with the surface, DFT calculations have shown that the interaction of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes with the surface is mediated by vdW dispersion interactions with minimal covalent character. The absence of a strong covalent bond is also consistent with the high mobility of

(NHC)₂Au complexes observed experimentally.

11.2.2 Vacancy islands

Surfaces saturated with NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} are accompanied by vacancy islands, similar to those observed on NHC^{iPr}-covered surfaces. STM images of the vacancy islands, or pits with a depth of a single atomic layer, show that they form predominantly at elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction. In Figure 11.6 they are visible as protrusions on terraces with a 75 ± 20 pm height difference, measured at a setpoint of 500 mV and 100 pA, compared to flat-lying (NHC)₂Au complexes on terraces. The bright signature is attributed to upright NHCs that decorate the pits. STM images indicate that NHCs occupy both the edges of vacancy islands and substrate step edges in a similar manner, showing no appreciable difference in height or ordering. We reported a similar finding for NHC^{iPr}, which attaches at upper step edges in an upright/tilted configuration [359].

Figure 11.6: STM images showing vacancy islands and ordering at step edges. (a) Vacancy islands on a NHC^{Me}-covered surface (500 mV, 100 pA, 22.0×22.0 nm²). A comparison with NHC binding at step edges shows that the bright signature is the result of upright/tilted NHCs. (b) A step edge decorated by upright/tilted NHC^{Me} molecules (200 mV, 60 pA, 22.0×12.0 nm²). (c) NHC^{Et}-covered surface with vacancy islands in proximity to a step edge (100 mV, 60 pA, 12.0×22.0 nm²). (d) Large-scale STM image with vacancy islands predominantly at elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction (100 mV, 60 pA, 29.0×29.0 nm²).

Vacancy island formation was previously discussed in relation to adsorbate-induced surface stress for NHC^{iPr} adsorption. Adsorbates that withdraw charge

from Au(111), including sulphur, oxygen, chlorine, and NO₂ induce compressive stress that increases the herringbone periodicity until the reconstruction is eventually lifted [370–373, 391]. Up to 0.63 adatoms/nm² are generated by the lifting process, which are ejected from the surface layer. Many species, including thiols, extract additional Au atoms from terraces, leaving behind mobile vacancies that can nucleate to form vacancy islands [362–364]. Related effects also arise for charge donating, rather than accepting, adsorbates. Such adsorbates generally induce a tensile stress that decreases the periodicity of the herringbone reconstruction [369]. Induced tensile stress has not been shown to lift the reconstruction, unlike compressive stress, which can compensate the tensile stress in an unreconstructed (1 × 1) surface.

The effect of charge donating adsorbates, including alkali metals and some organic molecules, on the herringbone reconstruction has been studied in a number of STM works. Barth *et al.* studied the response of the herringbone reconstruction to the adsorption of sodium and potassium atoms and reported a continuous decrease in the herringbone periodicity (250 to 100 Å) with increasing coverage [374]. Sterrer *et al.* have extensively examined the adsorption behaviour of 1,4-phenylene-diisocyanide (PDI) on Au(111) [369, 392]. Flat-lying (PDI–Au)_n oligomer chains were observed for UHV-deposited films up to to saturation coverage and for solution-deposited films exposed to a low PDI concentration. Despite the incorporation of Au atoms, SAM formation occurred without significantly distorting the herringbone reconstruction. Structural modifications were also observed for solution-deposited films in the form of Au ad-islands and vacancy islands [369]. Instead of being randomly distributed over the surface, the ad-islands and vacancy islands showed long-range ordering consistent with the presence of preferential nucleation sites in specific regions on the

herringbone reconstruction. Based on the observed ordering, they proposed that the extraction of Au atoms occurs from elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction, which act as nucleation sites for the further extraction of Au atoms and vacancy island formation. The preference for elbow sites was attributed to their high reactivity, which is common adsorption phenomena arising from under-coordinated Au atoms around edge dislocations. It remains unclear, however, whether PDI adsorption on Au(111) is directly followed by the extraction of Au atoms from elbow sites. An alternative scenario is that PDI modifies the herringbone reconstruction in the initial stages of adsorption, leading to a slight relaxation that triggers the extraction of Au atoms.

The herringbone reconstruction is visible under molecular layers of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, which may be expected given the sign of the adsorbate-induced stress (i.e. NHCs donate charge to Au(111)). However, it also appears largely intact and the STM data show a preferential distribution of vacancy islands at elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction. These results indicate that NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} adsorption behaviour is similar to PDI. In particular, the observation of ordered vacancy islands could suggest that Au atoms are extracted from elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction in the early stages of NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} adsorption. Less clear is whether or not NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} modify the herringbone reconstruction in the initial stages of adsorption, causing it to undergo a relaxation that triggers the release of Au atoms and, in turn, the formation of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. To provide insights into the effect of adsorbate-induced stress, we consider low-coverage STM data.

A low-coverage STM image of NHC^{Me} on Au(111) is shown in [Figure 11.7a](#). The ordering at step edges is consistent with [Figure 11.6](#). Many features are also present

Figure 11.7: NHC^{Me} adsorption on Au(111) at low surface coverage. (a) STM image showing NHC molecules on terraces separated by a monatomic step (-400 mV, 60 pA, 30.1×31.8 nm²). (b) Line profile comparing the apparent height of molecules on terraces and at the step edge. (c) Surface binding model based on calculated apparent height differences.

on terraces, which were mobile and occasionally captured in motion by the STM. A line profile across the step edge is plotted in Figure 11.7b to compare the STM height measurements. The data show (i) NHCs on the upper terrace have a similar apparent height compared to NHCs at steps, and (ii) the apparent height difference between NHCs on the upper and lower terrace is close to a single atomic step (~ 245 pm). A proposed binding model is shown in Figure 11.7c that assigns the features on terraces to upright, surface-bound NHCs. If (NHC)₂Au complexes exist on terraces, they were not captured in motion by STM or clearly resolved in the STM data. The lack of adatom involvement at low coverages suggests that the driving force for the release of Au atoms is mediated by the relaxation of the herringbone reconstruction due to adsorbate-induced surface stress. Due to the rapid diffusion of molecules on terraces, however, more work would be needed to conclusively determine whether NHC bonding

involves Au adatoms at low coverage. The binding mode may be investigated further by STM at a lower sample temperature, to limit surface diffusion, or by spectroscopic measurements, such as NEXAFS.

Finally, a notable difference compared to the PDI system is the lack of Au ad-islands. Interestingly, alkanethiol and arenethiol SAMs also diverge when it comes to ad-island formation on Au(111) [393, 394]. One of the key differences between alkanethiol and arenethiol SAMs has been attributed to the mobility of Au adatoms/vacancies during the self-assembly process. Liu *et al.* proposed that Au adatoms released by the surface diffuse rapidly and merge at neighbouring steps on alkanethiol-covered surfaces but become significantly less mobile during the formation of arenethiol SAMs, resulting in small ad-islands [394]. Kyriakou *et al.* investigated triphenylphosphine on Au(111) and introduced a related proposal based on its molecular packing density, whereby adatoms released by the herringbone reconstruction can become kinetically trapped within the molecular layer and coalesce into small islands [395]. Hence, while it could be possible that every Au atom extracted from the surface is subsequently incorporated into an $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex during SAM formation, some Au adatoms may also diffuse across the surface and merge at neighbouring step edges.

11.2.3 Bias-dependent imaging

An examination of the electronic states in STM experiments offers a direct method for establishing the presence of adatoms in organometallic complexes. Accordingly, we investigated the bias-dependent appearance of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. [Figure 11.8](#) shows large-scale STM images of NHC^{Me} on Au(111) for bias voltages in the range of

-2 V to 2 V , where a negative bias corresponds to filled state imaging and a positive bias corresponds to empty state imaging. Images were taken in 0.1 V increments and displayed here in 1.0 V increments. The structure of the $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, including individual adatoms, are clearly resolved for negative tunnelling voltages. In contrast, changes in appearance were observed at $+1\text{ V}$ that became more pronounced with increasing bias. The STM image at $+2\text{ V}$ clearly demonstrates the change in appearance, where each complex appears as a single bright protrusion centred at the Au adatom.

Figure 11.8: Effect of increasing bias on the appearance of NHC^{Me} complexes. The sequence of images also show structural rearrangements under the influence of the STM tip.

Similar observations have been reported in related systems that contain adatoms. For example, Persson *et al.* investigated the adsorption of 1,3,8,10-tetraazaperopyrene (TAPP) on $\text{Cu}(111)$, which coordinates to Cu adatoms in a porous network [396, 397]. They identified Cu adatom involvement by means of bias-dependent imaging experiments combined with density functional calculations [396]. At high positive sample bias, above $+3\text{ V}$, the TAPP molecules appeared as bright protrusions at the location of the adatoms. By examining the LDOS they determined the origin of the observed contrast to be a characteristic resonance state, or an unoccupied electronic state caused by the coordination of the organic ligands to Cu adatoms. A considerable number of systems, including Cu on $\text{Cu}(111)$ [398], Au on $\text{NiAl}(110)$ [399], Cu and Co

on Au(111) [400], and S on Ag(111) [401], also exhibit adatom-induced resonances.

The comparison with these studies suggests that the bright protrusions observed at high positive biases arises from an electron resonance at the adatom. Additional insight into the origin of the observed contrast in bias-dependent STM images may be obtained from an analysis of the LDOS by spectroscopy experiments and first principles calculations.

11.3 Densely packed arrays

This section presents an in-depth study on self-assembled structures formed by NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} . The films were prepared on a room-temperature Au(111) surface and subsequently imaged by STM at 77 K. Due to the observed mobility of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, most of our research efforts focus on arrays at or near saturation coverage.

11.3.1 NHC^{Me} self-assembly

The STM image in [Figure 11.9a](#) shows a disordered layer of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes that forms when NHC^{Me} is deposited onto a room temperature Au(111) surface just below saturation coverage. The observed molecular ordering is consistent with complexes that closely align along the close-packed $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ directions of the Au(111) surface. In general, the distinct orientations lead to distinct packing motifs, which play a crucial role in determining the structures that can form by self-assembly. Among the most common packing motifs observed in the STM data are shown in [Figure 11.9b](#). The propensity for $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes to form these arrangements, and the architectural structures that result, are discussed in detail in what follows.

Line profiles corresponding to the three packing motifs identified in [Figure 11.9a](#)

Figure 11.9: (a) $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes formed by depositing NHC^{Me} onto a room-temperature Au(111) surface (200 mV, 50 pA, $16.0 \times 16.0 \text{ nm}^2$). The complexes form a close packed network with no long range ordering. (b) Arrangement of common packing motifs.

are shown in [Figure 11.10a](#). The measurements highlight the spacing between neighbouring complex centres, which varies between 0.90 and 1.50 nm depending on their relative orientation within the assembly. To better quantify the spatial distribution of the Au complex centres, we calculated the radial distribution function. As shown in [Figure 11.10b](#), it exhibits only local order, with peaks at 0.91 ± 0.04 , 1.26 ± 0.03 , and 1.56 ± 0.09 nm corresponding to the three packing motifs.

The first packing motif involves a parallel arrangement of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes separated by a distance of 0.91 ± 0.04 nm. This motif is exclusively observed for NHC^{Me} , possibly because methyl wingtip groups are less sterically imposing compared to ethyl and isopropyl wingtip groups, allowing the complexes to pack more closely together. For comparison, the second and third packing motifs are also prevalent in the self-assembly of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes with bulkier wingtip groups, including

Figure 11.10: (a) Line profiles for the three common packing motifs show the distance between Au metal centres. (b) Average radial distribution function for NHC^{Me} calculated based on the analysis of three images to improve the signal-to-noise ratio.

NHC^{Et} and NHC^{iPr} . They involve complex pairs that form an angle close to 120° and similarly oriented complexes displaced by 1.56 ± 0.09 nm. In what follows, we consider well-ordered assemblies formed by these arrangements.

Heating the sample to 50°C promotes a densely packed lattice of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. The STM image in Figure 11.11a consists of a single domain with contrast modulation due to the underlying Au(111) herringbone reconstruction. As shown in Figure 11.11b, the apparent height distribution of Au complex centres is approximately Gaussian, with at most 4.4 ± 2.5 pm height difference arising from the surface corrugation. Equivalent rotational domains that reflect the three-fold symmetry of the Au(111) surface were also observed in the STM data. Among the largest domain sizes showed ordering that exceeded 100 nm in lateral dimensions. Defects observed at elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction only seem to disrupt the local ordering. Our observations suggest that the length scale of the observed ordering is mainly governed by step edges and boundaries with neighbouring domains.

Figure 11.11: (a) NHC^{Me} self-assembles into a well-ordered array upon annealing to 50 °C (200 mV, 60 pA, 38.8 × 38.8 nm²). (b) Median apparent height distribution for approximately 1000 Au complex centres. For comparison, the data are fit to Gaussian ($R^2 = 0.93$) and bimodal ($R^2 = 0.97$) distributions.

The close-up STM image in [Figure 11.12a](#) shows that the (NHC)₂Au complexes arrange in a double herringbone pattern. Using image thresholding techniques, we measured the density of Au centres to be approximately 0.64 nm⁻². We also examined the spacing between Au centres, shown in the top panel of [Figure 11.12b](#). The spectrum shows three peaks at 0.90 ± 0.03 nm, 1.25 ± 0.03 nm, and 1.54 ± 0.06 nm, resulting from the packing motifs characterized in [Figure 11.10b](#). The spectrum also contains a series of peaks between 1.87 ± 0.04 nm and 2.97 ± 0.09 nm, which act as a fingerprint for how (NHC)₂Au complexes arrange in the unit cell. In what follows, we introduce a lattice model and determine its structural characteristics for comparison with experiment.

We considered the $(-12, 6|0, 13)$ matrix model shown in [Figure 11.13a](#) and [Figure 11.13b](#) to describe the NHC^{Me} lattice structure. In the model, we assume that the metal Au centres reside above three-fold hollow sites and that the (NHC)₂Au

Figure 11.12: (a) STM image showing (NHC)₂Au complexes arranged in a double herringbone lattice (100 mV, 60 pA, 12.8 × 12.8 nm², 50 °C). (b) Normalized histograms showing the distribution of nearest-neighbour distances calculated using measured (top panel) and modelled (lower panel) Au metal centre positions.

complexes are aligned with their long molecular axis parallel to a close-packed $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ direction. The unit cell consists of (NHC)₂Au complexes that are centred above equivalent (e.g. fcc or hcp) three-fold hollow sites along the \mathbf{b}_1 lattice vector. Along the \mathbf{b}_2 vector, complexes alternate between fcc and hcp three-fold hollow sites. The dimensions in the half unit cell, bound by $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_2$, are $6\sqrt{3}a_0$ and $\sqrt{127/3}a_0$, which agree with the lattice constants indicated in Figure 11.12b. The bottom panel of the figure shows a histogram of the spacing between adsorption sites in the unit cell. The observed agreement suggests that the proposed model, or related models that consider small variations in the placement of (NHC)₂Au complexes inside the unit cell, adequately describe the experimental data. The adsorption sites were chosen here in connection with a given packing motif, based on the expected distance between Au centres. Qualitatively, the model also captures the shift between the diagonal

rows that join four $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, as outlined in Figure 11.12a and by δ in Figure 11.13a.

Figure 11.13: (a) Unit cell showing the metal Au centres in red. Adjacent surface atoms are highlighted for visibility. (b) Structural model for the ordered NHC^{Me} assembly.

Further modelling would be needed to establish the effect of the herringbone reconstruction on the structure of the lattice. It also remains an open question as to whether $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes sit above three-fold hollow sites or tend towards intermediate sites or bridge sites. A DFT study could provide additional insights into the preferred orientation and binding location of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in the lattice. For example, the lattice structure may be affected by interactions between neighbouring $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, which could include vdW interactions, electrostatic interactions, CH- π hydrogen bonding, and agostic interactions. DFT calculations would help determine the importance of these interactions and, by relaxing the arrangement of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, model the structure of the lattice.

11.3.2 NHC^{Et} self-assembly

Surfaces saturated with NHC^{Et} self-assemble into close-packed structures at low annealing temperatures. As shown in Figure 11.14a, $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes self-assemble into a pattern that appears rhombic upon annealing to 50°C . An analysis of the STM data shows that the complexes stack in alternating orientations with the angle between adjacent complexes varying between 50 and 70° . Disordered regions are found to form at pits and elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction, resulting in domains with short-range order (~ 10 nm). Heating the molecular layer to higher temperatures had a substantial effect on the observed ordering and the preferred orientation of NHC^{Et} complexes.

Figure 11.14: STM images showing the effect of temperature on NHC^{Et} self-assembly on Au(111). (a) NHC^{Et} -covered surface annealed to 50°C (100 mV, 60 pA, 8.85×8.85 nm 2). (b) Subsequent annealing to 60°C improved ordering (-200 mV, 60 pA, 8.85×8.85 nm 2). A unit cell of complex centres is indicated in black in each image.

Well-ordered domains, exceeding 50 nm in lateral dimensions, were observed following a 60 °C anneal. A representative STM image of the surface is shown in [Figure 11.14b](#). The lattice structure is oblique, comprised of NHC^{Et} complexes that closely align along a high-symmetry direction of the Au(111) surface. Compared to the rhombic lattice, the complexes pack more densely in this arrangement, with the density of Au centres increasing from 0.59 to 0.64 nm^{-2} . Similar structures persisted to high temperature (125 °C) and were also observed for $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ and $\text{EtNHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111), which likely indicates a thermodynamic preference for lattices based on this structure for $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes with bulky wingtip groups.

Figure 11.15: (a) Normalized histogram showing the distribution of Au centre separation distances. (b) Oblique unit cell marked with Au centres and their separation distances.

To characterize the lattice structure in [Figure 11.14b](#), we calculated the distance distribution between Au metal centres based on the image thresholding method. As shown in [Figure 11.15a](#) and [Figure 11.15b](#), the lattice is characterized by the lattice constants $|\mathbf{b}_1| = (1.18 \pm 0.02) \text{ nm}$ and $|\mathbf{b}_2| = (1.27 \pm 0.01) \text{ nm}$ and vertical and

horizontal separation distances 1.68 ± 0.02 nm and 1.78 ± 0.02 nm, respectively. An important feature in the data is that each nearest-neighbour spacing, when considered independently, is uniformly distributed. A variety of factors can affect these measurements, including (i) drift distortion, (ii) the x and y piezo calibration factors, and (iii) compression due to the herringbone reconstruction. The STM imaging was performed with active drift compensation and was qualitatively unaffected by small (5%) changes in the x and y calibration factor. These measurements also seem to be invariant to the compression direction of the underlying herringbone reconstruction. In what follows, we consider structural models based on three-fold hollow site and bridge site adsorption.

Figure 11.16: Three-fold hollow site adsorption model. (a) Unit cell showing Au positions in red and nearest-neighbour atoms highlighted for visibility. (b) Structural model for the ordered NHC^{Et} assembly.

We first considered the $(8, 1|-3, 5)$ matrix model based on three-fold hollow site adsorption to describe the complex lattice, as shown in Figure 11.16a and Figure 11.16b. Along the \mathbf{b}_2 lattice vector, $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes are centred above

equivalent (e.g. fcc or hcp) three-fold hollow sites. Conversely, the complex centres alternate between fcc and hcp three-fold hollow sites along the \mathbf{b}_1 vector such that, in the half unit cell bound by $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}_1$, the structure is oblique and the separation distances agree with the experimental data. In this model, however, the spacing between complex centres is only uniform along the \mathbf{b}_2 vector (1.26 nm). For example, the spacing between adjacent centres along the \mathbf{b}_1 lattice vector varies between 1.17 and 1.30 nm, which is not observed experimentally. Variations of this model that displace the top two complex centres by one or two three-fold hollow sites encounter the same problem. Accordingly, it may be possible that the metal Au centres sit above intermediate sites or bridge sites rather than equilibrium three-fold hollow sites. This could be a property of arrays self-assembled from $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes containing bulky wingtip groups, such as NHC^{Et} , $^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, and $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, which lift their metal centre far from the surface.

Figure 11.17: (a) Close-up STM image of the oblique lattice (-200 mV, 60 pA, 4.8×3.9 nm²). The image was rotated counterclockwise by 2° for comparison with the proposed structural model. (b) Structural model for the NHC^{Et} assembly based on bridge site adsorption.

To explore possible lattice structures, we have considered a bridge site adsorption model of the form $(4, 0.5 | -3, 5)$. As shown in [Figure 11.17a](#) and [Figure 11.17b](#),

the observed structure is in good agreement with the proposed model. The model well-reproduces the oblique lattice structure, including the apparent shift between complexes along the vertical and horizontal axes. A visual inspection of the data also indicates that the longitudinal line segment bisecting the unit cell forms a small angle with the long molecular axis of the complexes. The experimental value is close to 4° and a similar angle was recovered in the conformation we have considered, where the long molecular axis of each complex aligns along a close-packed direction of the Au(111) substrate.

The unit cell is defined in [Figure 11.18a](#) and an analysis of the intermolecular distances between Au centres on a perfectly hexagonal Au(111) surface is shown in the top panel in [Figure 11.18b](#). The dimensions of the unit cell show four characteristic peaks at 1.23, 1.25, 1.75, and 1.77 nm, which correspond to the lattice constants $|\mathbf{b}_1|$ and $|\mathbf{b}_2|$ and the horizontal and vertical separation distances, respectively. While the structure is qualitatively similar the experimental distribution provided in [Figure 11.15a](#), neighbouring peaks are separated by 0.02 nm, which is much smaller than the experimental values of 0.09 and 0.10 nm. Given the Au(111) – $(22 \times \sqrt{3})$ surface reconstruction is visible in STM under the molecular layer, we also consider its effect on the structure of the proposed lattice.

We model the reconstructed Au(111) surface as a uniaxially contracted hexagonal lattice. Along a $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ close-packed direction, 23 surface atoms fit into 22 lattice sites, which amounts to a contraction of about 4.3%. The effect on the molecular lattice depends on its orientation relative to the contraction direction, which varies along $[10\bar{1}]$, $[1\bar{1}0]$, and $[0\bar{1}1]$ in [Figure 11.18a](#). The most appreciable differences resulted when the surface was contracted along the $[10\bar{1}]$ and $[1\bar{1}0]$ directions. As shown in

Figure 11.18: (a) Unit cell with the metal Au centres in red and adjacent surface atoms highlighted for visibility. The effect of the herringbone reconstruction on the proposed lattice structure is shown for all three compression directions. (b) The top panel shows the spacing distribution between Au metal centres on a perfectly hexagonal $\text{Au}(111) - (1 \times 1)$ surface. The lower panel shows the effect of the herringbone reconstruction on the spacing distribution given a contraction along the $[10\bar{1}]$ (type 1) and $[1\bar{1}0]$ (type 2) directions.

the bottom panel of [Figure 11.18b](#), the separation distance increased between either the lattice constants $|\mathbf{b}_1|$ and $|\mathbf{b}_2|$ or the interior (vertical/horizontal) line segments. Comparing with the experimental data presented in [Figure 11.15a](#), we do not find good agreement, which suggests the need to consider revised binding models.

It may be possible to find better agreement with revised versions of the proposed matrix models. Given experimental measurements of the lattice structure over different domains of the herringbone reconstruction seem to be invariant, an alternative explanation could be that the Au metal centres do not preferentially orientate above equilibrium adsorption sites. For example, some degree of relaxation is expected due to interactions between neighbouring $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in an array. DFT calculations of the $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex array would likely provide new insights and help in identifying the favoured adsorption configuration.

11.3.3 Stability

A series of annealing experiments were performed to obtain information on the stability of NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} molecular layers. In general, we found that the NHC^{Et} film was stable to temperatures in excess of 150°C . Heating the film to 75°C produced an oblique lattice, [Figure 11.19a](#), that persisted to 125°C . The dimensions of the unit cell closely compare to those for the oblique lattice shown in [Figure 11.14b](#). The main difference seems to be the orientation of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in the lattice, which could suggest that their rotation angles were optimized with heating. Beyond 150°C , we observed a rhombic lattice, [Figure 11.19b](#), resembling the one shown in [Figure 11.14a](#). While its presence may indicate that there is little or no thermodynamic preference for one lattice over another, heating the surface to 150°C was accompanied by a reduction in surface coverage, which is also a factor that influences NHC-SAM formation [359].

Figure 11.19: STM images showing the effect of high-temperature annealing on the self-assembly of NHC^{Et} on Au(111). (a) NHC^{Et} film annealed to 75°C (100 mV, 60 pA, $8.9 \times 8.9 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) Subsequent annealing to 150°C (100 mV, 20 pA, $8.9 \times 8.9 \text{ nm}^2$). A repeating lattice of complex centres is indicated in black in each image.

Further heating of the NHC^{Et} film to 175 °C resulted in an appreciable reduction in surface coverage. A comparable reduction in surface coverage was observed after heating the NHC^{Me} film to 75 °C, which is consistent with the weaker binding energy of NHC^{Me} complexes (-2.53 eV) compared to NHC^{Et} complexes (-2.64 eV) predicted by DFT. We estimate that the surface coverage was reduced from 1 ML to around 0.5 ML for both systems. These estimates follow from the presence of small arrays of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes on the surface, which were occasionally captured in motion in the STM data. In general, however, an accurate determination of the surface coverage was very challenging due to the high mobility of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes below saturation coverage. This limitation could have a significant impact on our interpretation of NHC film stability, especially since, given the small (0.1 eV) difference in binding energies, we might expect the NHC^{Me} and NHC^{Et} films to exhibit similar thermodynamic stability.

The observed mobility also made it difficult to identify chemical species present on the surface. Heating an NHC-covered surface to high temperature may result in desorption that proceeds via decomposition. TPD spectra have shown that, while upright NHCs remain intact as they desorb from Cu(111), flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Cu}$ complexes decompose [291]. In general, the NHC desorption process could be substantially more complicated as well, depending not only on the binding mode but also on the temperature ramp, and possibly involving on-surface chemical reactions in a multi-step process. Accordingly, it would be interesting to image the adsorbates and possible decomposition products on Au(111) that result from higher annealing temperatures. To better resolve features in the STM data, the diffusive motion of the molecules can be limited by reducing the sample temperature (e.g. 5 K).

11.4 Non-porous chiral Kagome lattice

An interesting aspect of NHC^{Me} SAMs on Au(111) is the ability to form chiral domains. Below saturation coverage, we observe an appreciable population of NHC monomers on the surface. When the disordered NHC assembly is annealed to 50 °C, these species self-assemble with $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes to form a non-porous chiral Kagome lattice. To date, only a few systems have been found to produce Kagome lattices through molecular self-assembly [402–407]. Kagome lattices have been attracting considerable attention owing in part to their electronic band structure [408] and possible applications in host-guest chemistry [409] and spin-frustrated magnetism [410]. Many of the building blocks are linear molecules, including simple hydrocarbons and functionalized polyphenyl molecules, which self-assemble without chemical reactions to form nano-porous structures. By contrast, we find that the co-existence of on-surface synthesized $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes with NHC monomers gives rise to non-porous chiral architectures. In what follows, I describe the structure of the Kagome lattice, the emergence of chirality, and the distinct features observed inside the nanocavities.

11.4.1 Kagome lattice

An STM image of the Kagome lattice is shown in [Figure 11.20](#). It consists of a trihexagonal tiling structure with small triangular voids and quasi-hexagonal voids populated by protrusions, which we attribute to NHC monomers. The domain size ranges from 10 to 20 nm and is mainly interrupted by step edges and domain boundaries. In many cases, domain boundaries form with the double herringbone lattice.

We find that these two phases only co-exist for NHC-SAMs prepared below saturation coverage, which contain an appreciable population of NHC monomers. At or above saturation coverage, we exclusively observe $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes arranged in the double herringbone lattice. For comparison, $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in this lattice pack more densely than in the Kagome lattice, which has an Au-adatom density that measures approximately 0.55 nm^{-2} .

Figure 11.20: STM image of the Kagome lattice, rotated to align the nanocavities along the horizontal direction (100 mV, 100 pA, $12.0 \times 12.0 \text{ nm}^2$). $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes are centred at the vertices of the trihexagonal tiling structure, indicated in black.

The structure of the Kagome lattice is characterized in the top panel of [Figure 11.21a](#). The histogram shows three distinct peaks corresponding to the distance distribution between Au metal centres over one unit cell. The peak at $2.48 \pm 0.05 \text{ nm}$ corresponds to the $|\mathbf{b}_1|$ and $|\mathbf{b}_2|$ lattice constants defined in [Figure 11.21b](#), which form an angle close to 60° . Uniformly distributed peaks are also observed at

1.24 ± 0.02 nm and 2.15 ± 0.04 nm that correspond to the distance between nearest neighbours and next nearest neighbours, respectively.

Figure 11.21: (a) Nearest-neighbour spacing distributions calculated using measured (top panel) and modelled (lower panel) Au metal centre positions. (b) Close-up STM image of the Kagome lattice, rotated by 2° for comparison with the proposed structural model (100 mV, 100 pA, 5.3×4.1 nm²). The rhombic frame defines the unit cell.

In matrix notation, the structure is best described by the $(10, -2|2, 8)$ lattice. Structural models of the proposed unit cell are shown in [Figure 11.22a](#) and [Figure 11.22b](#). In the considered adsorption geometry, the $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes reside above three-fold hollow sites with their long molecular axes parallel to a close-packed $\langle 1\bar{1}0 \rangle$ direction. The unit cell consists of equivalent (e.g. fcc or hcp) three-fold hollow sites and is specified by lattice vectors that span the same length, $|\mathbf{b}_1| = |\mathbf{b}_2| = 2\sqrt{21}a_0$. Based on the symmetry of the model, only two domains are expected. That is, the lattice remains invariant under rotations of 60 and 120° whereas a reflection about either the x or y axis establishes a second domain with a non-superimposable lattice structure.

The bottom panel of [Figure 11.21b](#) shows the spacing distribution between adsorption sites in the proposed unit cell. Based on the lattice structure, we find that the proposed binding model is in good agreement with the experimental data. By

Figure 11.22: (a) Metal Au centre positions in the proposed unit cell. Adjacent surface atoms are highlighted for visibility. (b) Structural model for the Kagome lattice.

way of comparison, we generally found poor agreement with related models, such as the $(10, -1|2, 8)$ matrix model. The further study of this lattice could consider bridge site binding models or the effect of the herringbone reconstruction.

11.4.2 Chiral domains

As shown in [Figure 11.23a](#), the Kagome lattice has a mirror-symmetric domain with opposite handedness. Each domain is non-superimposable on its mirror image, which underlines the chiral symmetry of the Kagome lattice. The observation of just two domains is consistent with the symmetry of the proposed lattice model. Chirality likely emerges here because the complexes preferentially align along the major symmetry directions of Au(111), which imposes a constraint on the closest packing motifs. For example, the triangular motifs that form the Kagome lattices are shown in [Figure 11.23b](#). They are close-packed chiral arrangements that provide a hierarchical link to the self-assembly of structures with opposite handedness.

Figure 11.23: (a) Mirror-image domains of the chiral Kagome lattice (left: 200 mV, 60 pA, $13.5 \times 4.4 \text{ nm}^2$; right: 100 mV, 100 pA, $13.5 \times 4.4 \text{ nm}^2$). The STM images were rotated to align the nanocavities along the horizontal direction. (b) Structural model of the triangular packing units.

Early observations suggest a 10 : 1 enantiomeric excess of right-handed enantiomers, which points to a strong selection bias in the available STM data. To more accurately determine the relative abundance of the two enantiomers, areas of the surface would need to be randomly sampled.

11.4.3 Nanocavity structure

The hexagonal cavities of the Kagome lattice are occupied in STM. As shown in [Figure 11.24a](#), we observe two features, each with bright and dark states. These are (i) nearly circular protrusions with hexagonal symmetry, and (ii) protrusions with six-fold symmetric lobes. Similar features have been observed in Kagome networks synthesized with dicyanide-sexiphenyl molecules, which confine surface-state electrons to produce quantum corrals in the nanocavities [403]. However, the features we observe here do not show a characteristic voltage dependence to suggest they

are standing wave patterns. Instead, we find evidence that they are trapped NHC monomers.

Figure 11.24: (a) STM image of the Kagome lattice showing four distinct features in the hexagonal nanocavities (100 mV, 100 pA, $12.0 \times 12.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) Line profiles comparing the apparent height and spatial extent of the nanocavity features.

Line profile measurements corresponding to the nanocavity features identified in Figure 11.24a are shown in Figure 11.24b. Differences in spatial extent indicate that bright states appear 0.1 to 0.2 nm larger than dark states. Based on the peak maxima, bright states show a 35 to 40 pm increase in apparent height compared to dark states. An analysis of the large-scale STM image in Figure 11.25a provided a more accurate estimate of the height difference. We considered protrusions with nearly circular shapes (indicated in the inset) and extracted the median apparent height for 193 features using image thresholding methods. As shown in Figure 11.25b, the height distribution is bimodal with a $30 \pm 14 \text{ pm}$ difference between modes. For comparison, the height distribution of the Au metal centres was approximately Gaussian, similar to

the distribution shown in Figure 11.11b. As well, our observations do not suggest that bright and dark states occupy preferential regions on the herringbone reconstruction. Instead, they appear to be randomly distributed. Time-lapse STM measurements also show bistable switching sequences between bright and dark states under mild (100 mV, 20 pA) tunnelling conditions (Movie S2). These results indicate that the origin of the observed contrast is not linked to the underlying herringbone reconstruction. Based on amplitude coefficients extracted by fitting the data, we also find that the ratio of the number of bright to dark states is approximately 3 : 1, indicating that bright states are favoured at 77 K.

Figure 11.25: (a) Large-scale STM image used to obtain statistics on the nanocavity features (100 mV, 60 pA, $40.0 \times 40.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) Median apparent height distribution of 193 bright and dark state nanocavity features. Only nearly circular protrusions were considered in the analysis, as featured in the inset of the STM image.

An examination of disordered regions in the NHC^{Me} monolayer allowed us to identify molecular building blocks capable of forming the nanocavity features. The bright and dark state protrusions identified in Figure 11.26a have a hexagonal structure that becomes more prominent at high tunnelling currents, Figure 11.26b. The molecular

building block associated with these features is identified in [Figure 11.26c](#). Its shape is roughly triangular and resembles half an $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex without the bright signature from the Au adatom. Accordingly, we attribute the feature to an NHC monomer in either a flat-lying or tilted configuration. Instances of such features were only captured in highly confined regions, suggesting that the molecule becomes pinned by steric confinement. In subsequent analysis, we show that the rotation of the NHC trapped within a nanocavity can reproduce the observed hexagonal features.

Figure 11.26: Nanocavity features and their molecular building blocks. (a) Nearly-circular protrusions in bright and dark states (100 mV, 60 pA, $7.0 \times 7.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (b) Scanning at high current over the same region reveals their hexagonal symmetry (100 mV, 3.5 nA, $7.0 \times 7.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (c) Triangular features in a distorted nanocavity (200 mV, 60 pA, $5.0 \times 5.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (d) Flower-shaped features in bright and dark states (100 mV, 100 pA, $7.0 \times 7.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (e) A distorted nanocavity containing a distorted flower-shaped feature (100 mV, 50 pA, $7.0 \times 7.0 \text{ nm}^2$). (f) A distorted nanocavity containing a three-lobed feature (200 mV, 60 pA, $5.0 \times 5.0 \text{ nm}^2$).

Bright and dark flower-shaped cavity features are identified in [Figure 11.26d](#). The

features show a central protrusion surrounded by a circular depression, which is in turn surrounded by six bright intensity lobes. Interestingly, we find that the shape of these features is highly dependent on the local environment, with their geometry determined by the shape of the nanocavity. In hexagonal nanocavities, the features exhibit six-fold rotational symmetry with a precise orientation with respect to the Kagome lattice. Regions where the symmetry of the lattice is interrupted contain distorted features, such as the one shown in [Figure 11.26e](#). In some cases we also observe a distinct three-lobed feature, [Figure 11.26f](#). Based on time-lapse STM data, the feature is likely an NHC monomer, analogous to the one identified in [Figure 11.26c](#). Image sequences taken under mild tunnelling conditions, for example, have revealed reversible transitions between all four cavity modes (Movie S2). That is, on/off switching between bright and dark states and reversible transitions between hexagonal and flower-like features. In cases when $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in the lattice undergo structural rearrangements, we have also observed reversible transitions involving the three-lobed feature. These results indicate that the different features we observe can be formed by the same species, namely a trapped NHC monomer.

In principle, conformational changes in the wingtip groups could explain the difference between the triangular and three-lobed features. One possibility that we considered was a hybridization-induced conformational change, whereby the hybridization of the nitrogen atoms changes from sp^2 to sp^3 . Disrupting the conjugation around the *N*-heterocycle may produce a non-planar structure with pyramidalized nitrogen atoms. In a tetrahedral geometry, the methyl groups protrude from the molecular plane, as shown in [Figure 11.27a](#), which could give rise to a feature with three lobes

in STM. While a change in bond hybridization could be thermally or STM-tip induced [411, 412], NHC bonding may be substantially more complicated. Physical changes, such as tilting, could affect the aromaticity of the heterocycle as well. We also considered a rotational motion of the NHC to explain the structural differences. Figure 11.27b illustrates the rotation of a tilted NHC where each methyl group pivots into and away from the surface. More work would be needed to establish the dynamics of the caged molecule, and whether such motion can give rise to the three-lobed feature observed by STM. In what follows, we examine the nanocavity features by modelling both a hindered rotation and random motion of the monomers.

Figure 11.27: Adsorption scenarios considered to explain the three-lobed feature. (a) A tilted NHC monomer with pyramidalized nitrogen atoms. (b) The rotation of a tilted NHC monomer.

Models for the triangular and three-lobed features, Figure 11.28, were generated by randomly sampling points from two-dimensional Gaussian distributions. Three distributions, corresponding to a central distribution and distributions for two lobes, were sampled to reproduce the shape of each feature. By varying the centre position and variance in x and y for each distribution, the models were constructed to coincide with the experimental data provided in Figure 11.26.

First we considered the hindered rotation of an NHC about its central distribution, \mathcal{O} or \mathcal{O}_1 . If the molecular structure of a flat-lying NHC is superimposed on the models,

the points \mathcal{O} and \mathcal{O}_1 would roughly correspond to the centre of the benzene ring. The patterns generated by superimposing images rotated by 60° closely correspond to the features observed in the nanocavities. As shown, the six-fold rotation of the triangular feature produces a hexagonal protrusion. Similarly, a flower-shaped feature is recovered by the rotation of the three-lobed feature. The approximate size of the features are indicated by line profiles presented below the images. A comparison with [Figure 11.24b](#) shows that the models correspond well with the experimental data. Less clear is the origin of bright and dark states.

Figure 11.28: Models for the molecular building blocks and features formed by their six-fold rotation. The left panel shows a hexagonal protrusion and flower-shaped features are shown in the two right-most panels. Line profiles provided below the images indicate their approximate spatial extent.

One factor that we considered to be important was the rotation centre, since dark states show a smaller size compared to bright states. In [Figure 11.28](#), we considered a rotation of the three-lobed feature about \mathcal{O}_2 , displaced by 190 pm with respect to the central distribution. The rotation centre roughly corresponds to the centre of the N -heterocycle, rather than the benzene ring, when the molecular structure of a flat-lying NHC is superimposed on the model. As shown in the right-most panel, the six-fold rotation about this point gives rise to a flower-shaped feature with dimensions that closely compare with experiment. We also produced distorted flower-shaped

features using symmetry-breaking perturbations and smaller hexagonal protrusions in a similar manner. Accordingly, we find that these data well-reproduce the shape of the nanocavity features.

While the data are well-described by our simple model of a rotating NHC, it remains largely unclear if or why an NHC would preferentially rotate about one of its aromatic rings. In general, the motion of an NHC may be much more complicated, determined by an interplay of molecule-substrate and molecule-molecule interactions. These include steric interactions between the NHC and neighbouring $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, which limit translational and rotational degrees of freedom. Similarly, interactions between the aromatic rings of the NHC and the substrate may be relevant in establishing preferred alignment directions, as is the case for $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes. To examine the impact of these constraints on a random walk process, without an understanding of motion details, we considered an ensemble average over accessible configurations within the nanocavity. These were defined based on a Kagome pattern of available adsorption sites, [Figure 11.29a](#), reflecting the symmetry of the Kagome lattice. Repeated random sampling of the triangular feature generated a hexagonal protrusion. Similarly, the characteristic flower shape was produced by repeated sampling of the three-lobed feature, [Figure 11.29b](#). Its shape and size is similar to both the middle panel in [Figure 11.28](#) and bright flower states observed in the STM data. The agreement indicates that the confined motion of an NHC trapped within a nanocavity can establish an apparent axis of rotation, questioning whether or not NHC motion is purely rotational.

Further study of the effect of confinement on translational and rotational motion would be required to determine whether NHC motion inside a nanocavity can give rise

Figure 11.29: Quasi-random walk of a surface-bound NHC monomer. (a) Adsorption configurations based on a trapped monomer aligned along the $[11\bar{2}]$ directions. Available adsorption sites were limited to a Kagome pattern and available orientations were limited based on steric constraints imposed by the host Kagome lattice. (b) Flower-shaped feature produced by randomly sampling available adsorption configurations.

to dark states as well. This includes an understanding of the host-guest chemistry, comprising in particular NHC-substrate interactions and intermolecular interactions between a trapped NHC and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in the host Kagome lattice. In what follows, we consider different mechanisms that might explain the difference between bright and dark states, including changes in molecular conformation, dipole orientation, and charge state.

We have studied the switching behaviour of bright and dark cavity features at variable bias and tunnelling current to examine the influence of the STM tip. Bistability has been reported in many molecular systems due to the manipulation of adsorbates with the STM tip [411]. The applied bias creates an electric field in the tip-sample gap that can induce molecular motion through interactions with intrinsic or induced dipoles. For example, Weiss *et al.* observed bias-dependent switching of oligo(phenylene-ethynylene)s (OPEs) on Au(111), which they linked to changes in tilt

induced by either attractive or repulsive interactions between the intrinsic dipole moment of the molecule and the electric field applied by the STM tip [413]. Tip-induced effects also include phenomena that depend on the magnitude of the tunnelling current, such as local heating and electron attachment [414]. A fast-scanning STM study over -1.4 V to $+1.4\text{ V}$ in 100 mV increments did not reveal transitions between bright and dark states. The four cavity modes were also resolved in tunnelling conditions ranging from 20 pA to 3.5 nA . These observations likely rule out electronic mechanisms induced by the STM tip, such as charge switching and dipole switching.

A different mechanism for bistability is thermal excitation. Weiss *et al.* related the conductance switching of OPEs to a tilting of the molecule, or a change in its orientation with respect to the STM tip, due to a varying hybridization of the sulphur atom [412]. On Au(111), the energy barrier between sp and sp^3 hybridization states could be as low as 0.1 eV [415]. The authors argue that a change in hybridization, corresponding to a change in the surface-C-S bond angle from approximately 180 to 104° , is therefore energetically accessible at room temperature. This mechanism is supported by the bias-induced switching behaviour of OPEs with dipole moments, which adopt upright or tilted configurations [413]. Further work would be needed to determine if a similar tilting mechanism applies to NHC binding, and whether the process is thermally induced.

Chapter 12

Conclusions and future work

Organic molecules capable of forming strongly bound self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) offer a promising route to surface modification and functionalization. Technological advances including the protection and stabilization of nanoparticles and the development of lab-on-chip sensors have been largely realized by the adsorption of alkanethiols. *N*-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) were recently introduced as alternative anchors in the preparation of SAMs on metal surfaces and may be superior to thiol-based systems. Compared to thiols, these newcomers are more diverse, with highly tunable structural and electronic properties, and are capable of forming strongly bound monolayers with improved stability. Accordingly, we performed an in-depth study of NHC adsorption and self-assembly on gold. In particular, we examined the effect of NHC structure, surface coverage, deposition temperature, and annealing temperature on NHC binding, self-assembly, and mobility for an important class of NHCs, namely alkylated benzimidazolylidenes. Our work provides several new insights into NHC–NHC and NHC-substrate interactions, finding that NHC adsorption and self-assembly on gold is substantially richer than previously thought.

12.1 Conclusions

By means of scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM), we carried out the first in-depth study of the binding and self-assembly behaviour of benzimidazole-based NHCs on Au(111). Our molecular-level study of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ adsorption shows that the molecule can adopt a number of distinct binding modes, which are summarized in [Figure 12.1](#) as a function of surface coverage. At low coverages, $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ shows a preference for step edges and elbow sites of the herringbone reconstruction. STM image sequences show that the molecules found at these adsorption sites, which are the most reactive sites on Au(111), are mostly immobile. STM observations also indicate the presence of upright, surface-bound NHCs, flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, and NHC monomers on terraces at low coverages. These species form a highly mobile 2D gas-like phase before self-assembling into lattices that are stable for imaging. By increasing the coverage slightly, we observed lattices composed of surface-bound NHCs, $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes, and a more exotic lattice possibly involving both surface-bound NHCs and $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes.

Figure 12.1: Structural model showing the different adsorption configurations of $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ on Au(111) as a function of surface coverage.

Further increase in surface coverage led to the formation of a zig-zag lattice formed by upright/tilted NHCs bound to adatoms. An examination of the lattice structure and the deposition of its deuterated analogue, $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}-d_{14}$, suggests that NHC–NHC

interactions play an important role in stabilizing this lattice. The incorporation of Au adatoms into the assembly is found to occur at a critical coverage of approximately 0.4 ML, which is discussed in relation to adsorbate-induced surface stress. At this coverage, the STM data also show evidence for surface-bound NHCs and small arrays of (NHC)₂Au complexes. We found that their relative abundance on the surface is considerably affected by coverage, possibly due to competitive adsorption or on-surface chemical reactions. On saturated surfaces, for example, we observe a single phase consisting of upright, adatom-bound NHCs. A number of observations support adatom involvement, including:

1. the observation of vacancy islands, which form by the removal of Au atoms from the top surface layer,
2. the registry of the zig-zag lattice on Au(111), which suggests NHCs sit above three-fold hollow sites,
3. the small apparent height difference between NHCs at step edges and NHCs in the zig-zag lattice, and
4. agreement with DFT calculations.

Together, these observations provide a consistent picture for NHC attachment to gold adatoms.

In addition to surface coverage, the propensity for NHCs to adopt upright or flat-lying adsorption configurations strongly depends on wingtip structure. When deposited on room-temperature Au(111) surfaces, NHCs with bulky wingtip substituents, including NHC^{*i*Pr} and NHC^{*t*Bu}, form upright SAMs attached via Au adatoms. This preference arises from the minimization of molecule-surface steric

interactions, which can be effectively tuned by changing the wingtip substituents. Remarkably, we found that removing even a single methyl group from $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ changes the preferred adsorption orientation. Our STM observations show that $^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, NHC^{Et} , and NHC^{Me} dimerize to form flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes on Au(111), consistent with DFT-calculated binding energies, Figure 12.2.

Figure 12.2: Effect of wingtip structure on the binding energy of an upright/tilted NHC bound to an adatom (blue) and a flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex (red) on Au(111).

Several new findings on how these complexes bind and self-assemble on Au(111) are presented in this thesis. Clear evidence for Au adatom involvement is provided based on (i) the structure of the observed features, (ii) total energy calculations, (iii) the observation of vacancy islands, and (iv) voltage-dependent imaging experiments. Our findings suggest that the mechanism by which Au atoms are released from the surface to produce $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes is similar to how $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ combines with Au adatoms despite the change in adsorption orientation and number of carbenes per adatom. A notable difference compared to NHCs in upright adsorption geometries is that $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes are highly mobile on Au(111) at 77 K. This finding is consistent with DFT calculations, which show that $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes do not form strong covalent bonds with the surface. To limit surface diffusion, most of our

research efforts focused on NHC films prepared at or near saturation coverage. We report on a number of lattices, including in particular a non-porous chiral Kagome lattice containing trapped NHC monomers, and constructed molecular models for these lattices to gain new insight into the interplay of molecule-molecule and molecule-substrate interactions.

Table 12.1: Adatom density measurements in NHC films. Values are reported for $\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$ (disordered layer), $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ (zig-zag lattice and lattice of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes in parenthesis), $^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$, NHC^{Et} (rhombic and oblique lattices), and NHC^{Me} (Kagome and rectangular lattices). The adatom density of $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes can be multiplied by a factor of 2 to obtain the molecular density (does not account for monomers trapped in the Kagome lattice).

	$\text{NHC}^{t\text{Bu}}$	$\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$	$^{\text{Et}}\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$	NHC^{Et}	NHC^{Me}
Density [adatoms/nm ²]	1.4	1.6 (0.47)	0.55	0.59-0.64	0.55-0.64

Overall, the successful use of NHCs in many potential applications is strongly dependent on the orientation and structure of the SAMs they form. In this thesis, I have provided a comprehensive picture of NHC binding and self-assembly, which features a complicated competition between direct attachment to gold adatoms and the formation of a flat-lying $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complex. Characterization of these monolayers also shows a relationship between NHC structure and packing density, which is summarized in [Table 12.1](#). The general trend for each binding mode shows that the packing density increases as the size of the wingtip groups are reduced. These data, together with our ability to make thermodynamic predictions based on total energy calculations, will hopefully help guide further research and NHC applications where knowledge and control of the SAM properties are important.

12.2 Future work

Areas of future work include low-temperature STM investigations at low coverage to better characterize isolated molecules that would otherwise be mobile on the surface. The simultaneous use of complementary imaging modalities, including differential conductance measurements, inelastic electron tunnelling spectroscopy, and atomic force microscopy, would also greatly benefit the interpretation of the observed contrast. In addition to an enhanced characterization of these systems, it would also be useful to design NHCs with upright adsorption orientations for the future application of NHC research. In what follows, I consider a number of factors to promote and/or stabilize the upright adsorption mode, including (i) the crystal surface, (ii) the structure of the NHC ligand, and (iii) the deposition method.

NHC adsorption and self-assembly may be substantially different depending on the crystal surface. A recent theoretical investigation by Tang *et al.* found that NHC^{Me} adsorbs strongly on Ru(0001) and Pt(111) surfaces in upright configurations [416]. Their results provide a guide for future experimental study, offering a new and intriguing avenue towards the formation of upright, strongly bound SAMs consisting of simple methyl-substituted NHCs.

Another approach in promoting/stabilizing the formation of upright SAMs is by tailoring the structure of the NHC ligand. Structural changes to the ligand modify its interaction with the substrate, which can possibly induce a conformational change. For example, it may be possible to change the preferred adsorption orientation of methyl- and ethyl-substituted NHCs by introducing fluorine atoms or CF_3 groups into the molecular backbone. The addition of alkyl chains on the molecular backbone may also promote upright adsorption orientations due to entropic effects associated

with the minimization of their steric impact. These approaches, based on modifying NHC-substrate or NHC-NHC interactions, may promote NHCs that would otherwise dimerize to form $(\text{NHC})_2\text{Au}$ complexes on Au(111) to form dense upright SAMs.

Finally, NHC film properties strongly depend on the deposition method, which may be tuned to promote organization and possibly the preferred adsorption orientation of the ligand. For example, high-coverage $\text{NHC}^{i\text{Pr}}$ films prepared by flash deposition onto room-temperature Au(111) substrates contain vacancy islands, which interrupt NHC ordering. Although high-temperature annealing removes these defects, it also reduces the surface coverage. Accordingly, the (continuous) deposition of NHCs up to saturation coverage onto heated surfaces may lead to enhanced molecular order by reducing vacancy island formation (i.e. by preventing the nucleation of vacancies and promoting their annihilation at steps). Similar experiments with NHCs bearing methyl or ethyl wingtip substituents could also yield interesting results. We have already shown a dramatic change in NHC binding and self-assembly behaviour by direct deposition onto LN_2 -cooled surfaces. We speculate that increasing the substrate temperature during the deposition process will uncover unique adsorption and self-assembly behaviour due to the influence of thermodynamic and kinetic factors on SAM formation. It may also be interesting to investigate films prepared by solution deposition. This method produces a constant flux of particles into and away from the surface, which may allow the NHCs to organize into a thermodynamically preferred state that is inaccessible with vapour deposition. Consequently, it seems worthwhile to investigate whether such experiments can influence the adsorption orientation of NHCs in SAMs.

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Appendix A

Mechanical design

This appendix provides assembly drawings for a few custom components that we designed using Inventor 3D CAD software. Using a combination of both research and trial-and-error based approaches, we iteratively designed and maintained these components to suit our experimental needs. Overall, each of the most recent design implementations are considered successes and a good fit for our instrumentation needs. Included are the final assembly drawings for the velocity selector, ionization gauge, ion extractor, and the optical encoder.

- Two Swagelok Tube Fittings (2X) Swagelok SS-400-1-4 3/16 SS Male Connector for 1/4" Tube OD
- Ferro-Magnetic Fluid Rotary Feedthrough (1X) Kurt J. Lesker KLDFC032725 2 3/4" CF Mounting Flange, 3/8" Shaft Diameter, Rated to 10,000 RPM
- Custom Zero-Length Reducer Flange (1X) Kurt J. Lesker RF8000X275 8" to 2 3/4" CF Flange
- Three Individually Customized Bearing Mounts (3X) McMaster-Carr 6620K222 Multipurpose 304 SS Machinable Sheet, 1/2" x 3" x 4"
- Two Custom Bearing Support Bars (Long) (2X) McMaster-Carr 89415K29 Multipurpose 304 SS Tight-Tolerance Rectangular Bar, 3/4" x 3/4" x 2"
- Two Custom Bearing Support Bars (Short) (2X) McMaster-Carr 89415K15 Multipurpose 304 SS Tight-Tolerance Rectangular Bar, 1/2" x 1/2" x 1"
- Eight Individually Customized Waterlines (1X) Swagelok 304L-14-S-035-20 304 SS Seamless Tubing, 1/4" OD, 0.180" ID, 20' Length

DETAIL A

- Four Vented Cup Point Set Screws (1X) McMaster-Carr 91979A341 18-8 SS, Inch No. 6-32 UNC, 3/8" Length
- Two Custom Flanged Shaft Collars (2X) McMaster-Carr 9208K12 Multipurpose 304 SS Short Rod, 2 1/2" OD, 3/4" Long, for 3/8" Shaft Diameter

DETAIL B

- Three Nonmagnetic External Retaining Rings (1X) McMaster-Carr 98410A665 Beryllium Copper Alloy, for 3/8" Shaft Diameter, 0.025" Thickness
- Use Heavy Duty Fixed-Tip Retaining Ring Pliers to Install Retaining Rings (1X) McMaster-Carr 5449A76 0.035" Tip Diameter, for 1/8" to 3/8" Shaft Diameter
- Three Shielded High-Precision Radial Ball Bearings (3X) New Hampshire Ball Bearings, Inc. SSR1-1438ZZRA7P58LY328 Lubed With Brycolite 60LEF Vacuum Grease, ABEC 7 Rating, for 3/8" Shaft Diameter, 7/8" OD, 9/32" Thickness
- Nine Custom Weld Caps (1X) McMaster-Carr 89535K85 Multipurpose 304 SS Rod, 1/4" OD, 6" Length
- Four Unthreaded Spacers For No. 10 Screw Size (4X) McMaster-Carr 92320A765 18-8 SS, 5/16" OD, 0.192" ID, 7/16" Length
- Custom Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Heat Shield (1X) McMaster-Carr 8978T63 Machinable Alumina (Aluminum Oxide) Ceramic Sheet, 48% Porosity, Rated to 1650 °C, 1/8" x 6" x 6"

- High-Speed Helical Flexible Shaft Coupling (1X) McMaster-Carr 6208K536 Aluminum Clamp-On Coupling for 3/8" Diameter Shafts, 5° Max. Angular Misalignment, 0.015" Max. Parallel Misalignment, Rated to 10,000 RPM
- Custom Rotary Shaft (1X) McMaster-Carr 5947K36 Chrome-Plated 1045 Carbon Steel, 3/8" OD, -0.001" to 0" Diameter Tolerance, 0.003" Straightness Tolerance per Foot, 24" Length, C60 Rockwell Hardness Rating
- Custom Slotted Cylinder Velocity Selector (Spindle) GPI Prototype & Manufacturing Services PH1 SS, Manufactured Using Direct Metal Laser Sintering, 10 cm OD, 20 cm Length, ±0.2% Part Accuracy
- 90 Internal Helical Channels (2.9° Angular Aperture, 3.0° Pitch Angle), 10 cm OD, 20 cm Length, ±0.2% Part Accuracy
- Sixteen Socket Head Cap Screws (1X) McMaster-Carr 92185A991 316 SS, Inch No. 10-32 UNF - 3/4"

Not Shown: Custom Servo Motor Assembly Designed by Kurt J. Lesker Company

Integrated Servo Motor
 (1X) Animatics SM23165SD
 Integrated Motor, Controller, Amplifier, Encoder, and Communications Bus, NEMA 23 Size, 4,000 Counts per Revolution Encoder Resolution, 10,400 RPM No Load Speed, 0.45 Nm Peak Torque, 1/4" Shaft Diameter

High-Speed Bellows Flexible Shaft Coupling
 (1X) Ruland Manufacturing BC16-6-4-A
 Aluminum Clamp-On Coupling for 3/8" and 1/4" Diameter Shafts, 1.5° Max. Angular Misalignment, 0.004" Max. Parallel Misalignment, Rated to 10,000 RPM

DRAWN	11/04/2017	Queen's University	
CHECKED		TITLE	
QA		Velocity Selector	
MFG		SIZE	DWG NO
APPROVED		C	VelocitySelector
		SCALE	REV
			4

Custom Electrode Shield
(1X) McMaster-Carr 89325K36
316 SS Rod, 1.5/16" OD, 6" Long

Six Socket Head Cap Screws
(1X) McMaster-Carr 92185A109
316 SS, Inch No. 4-40 UNC - 7/16"
Electrical Power Feedthrough
(1X) Kurt J. Lesker FFT043032
1.1/3" CF Flange, 500 V DC Voltage
Rating, 12 A Current Rating (per Pin)
Custom Zero-Length Reducer Flange
(1X) Kurt J. Lesker RF275X133
2.3/4" to 1.1/3" CF Flange

*Sectioning to show internal detail of assembly.

Six Vented Socket Head Cap Screws
(2X) McMaster-Carr 93235A106
18-8 SS, Inch No. 4-40 UNC - 1/4"
Three Socket Head Cap Screws
(1X) McMaster-Carr 92185A105
316 SS, Inch No. 4-40 UNC - 1/4"
Custom Extension Arm
(1X) McMaster-Carr 89495K21
Multipurpose 304 SS Round Tube,
1/2" OD, 0.083" Thickness, 1' Long

Custom Adapter
(1X) McMaster-Carr 8934K22
304 SS Tight-Tolerance Rod,
1.1/4" OD, 6" Long

Six Button Head Hex Drive Screws and
Three Custom 316 SS Two-Hole Washers
(1X) McMaster-Carr 98164A429
316 SS, Inch No. 4-40 UNC - 3/16"
Precision-Mesh Wire Cloth
Tack-Welded to Electrode Shield
(1X) McMaster-Carr 9656T15
316 SS, 20" x 20", 0.46 Open Area

Eight Push-Crimp Connectors
(1X) Kurt J. Lesker FTAPC062
BeCu Connector for a 0.062" OD Wire

Two Socket Head Cap Screws
(1X) McMaster-Carr 92185A105
316 SS, Inch No. 4-40 UNC - 3/16"

Custom Attachment
(1X) McMaster-Carr 8934K37
304 SS Tight-Tolerance Rod,
1.1/8" OD, 6" Long
Kapton Insulated Silver-Plated Copper Wire
(1X) Accu-Glass Products L12697
18 AWG Solid Core Wire, 15' Long

Custom Miniature Dual Filament Ionization Gauge
(1X) Kurt J. Lesker KILC354401YF
Yttria-Coated Iridium Filament, Tantalum Grid,
Tungsten Ion Collector

Not Shown:

Polyether Ether Ketone (PEEK) Shrink Tubing
(1X) Accu-Glass Products 111880
Starting ID 0.125", Recovered ID 0.104", 6" Length
250 °C Max. Operating Temperature, 10⁻⁶~10⁻¹⁰ Torr Max. Vacuum Level

DRAWN	03/11/2016	Queen's University
CHECKED		
QA		
MFG		
APPROVED		
TITLE		
Ion Gauge Assembly		
SIZE	C	DWG NO
SCALE		IGAssembly
REV	4	SHEET 1 OF 1

Detector Subassembly

Source Subassembly

Custom Mount to 4.5" Conflat Viewport
(1X) McMaster-Carr 1610T48
Multipurpose 6061 Aluminum Rod, 5" OD, 1" Long

Custom Laser-Tilt Mount
(1X) McMaster-Carr 9140T271
Multipurpose 6061 Aluminum Rectangular Bar, 2" x 2" x 2"

Two Socket Head Cap Screws
(1X) McMaster-Carr 92185A109
316 SS, Inch No. 4 - 40 UNC - 7/16"

Two Socket Head Cap Screws
(1X) McMaster-Carr 92185A124
316 SS, Inch No. 4 - 40 UNC - 9/16"

Four Thread-Locking Socket Head Cap Screws
(1X) McMaster-Carr 96209A411
316 SS, Inch No. 8 - 32 UNC - 1/4"

DRAWN Ryan Groome	10/10/2014	Queen's University
CHECKED Kevin Robbie		
QA MFG		
APPROVED		
TITLE		Optical Encoder Assembly
SIZE	DWG NO	REVISIONS
C	Optical_Encoder_Assembly	REV
SCALE		SHEET 1 OF 1

- Collimated Laser Diode Module
(1X) Thorlabs CFS180
635 nm, 1 mW, Round Beam, 11 mm OD Housing
- Collimator Adapter
(1X) Thorlabs AD11F
SM1-Threaded Adapter, for 11 mm OD Cylindrical Components
- Absorptive Neutral Density Filter
(1X) Thorlabs NE20A
SM1-Threaded, Optical Density: 2.0
- Kinematic Cage Mount,
(1X) Thorlabs KC1-S
SM1-Threaded with Slip Plate

- Four Cage Assembly Rods
(1X) Thorlabs ER1.5-P4
6 mm OD, 38.1 mm Long
- Thread Adapter
(1X) Thorlabs SMA16FW
External SM1 Threads and Internal SM05 Threads, Knurled Edge
- Ring-Activated SM05 Iris Diaphragm
(1X) Thorlabs SM05D5D
SM05-Threaded

DRAWN	07/10/2014	Queen's University	
CHECKED		TITLE	
Kevin Robbie		Source Subassembly	
QA		SIZE	DWG NO
MFG		C	Source_Subassembly
APPROVED		SCALE	REVISIONS
			1
			SHEET 1 OF 1

- Kinematic Cage Mount, (1X) Thorlabs KCI-5 SM1-Threaded with Slip Plate
- Thread Adapter (1X) Thorlabs SM1AGFW
- External SM1 Threads and Internal SM05 Threads, Knurled Edge
- Four Cage Assembly Rods (1X) Thorlabs ER4-P4 6 mm OD, 101.6 mm Long
- Slotted Lens Tube (1X) Thorlabs SM05L30C SM05-Threaded, 76.2 mm Thread Depth

- Four Retaining Rings (4X) Thorlabs SM05RRR SM05-Threaded
- Premium Bandpass Filter (1X) Thorlabs FLH05633-5 CWL = 633 nm, FWHM = 5 nm
- Unmounted Achromatic Doublet (1X) Thorlabs AC127-075-A Focal Length: 75 mm, ARC: 400 - 700 nm

- Ultra-Compressible O-Ring (1X) McMaster-Carr 2418T136 Buna-N, 5/8" OD, 7/16" ID, 3/32" Thickness
- Photodiode Detector (1X) OSI Opto Electronics QD7-0-SD Sum and Difference Amplifier Module
- Four Unthreaded Spacers (1X) McMaster-Carr 93657A700 Nylon, 0.177" OD, 0.126" ID, 0.079" Thickness
- Two Socket Head Cap Screws (1X) McMaster-Carr 95868A259 Nylon, Inch No. 4-40 UNC - 7/16"
- Two Thread-Locking Socket Head Cap Screws (1X) McMaster-Carr 96209A212 316 SS, Inch No. 4-40 UNC - 3/8"
- Custom Circuitry Mount (1X) McMaster-Carr 9057K313 Multipurpose 6061 Aluminum Tight-Tolerance Precision Ground Rectangular Bar, 3/4" x 2" x 3"
- Ultra-Compressible O-Ring (1X) McMaster-Carr 2418T117 Buna-N, 7/16" OD, 5/16" ID, 3/32" Thickness
- Custom Extension Arm (1X) McMaster-Carr 9062K35 Multipurpose 6061 Aluminum Tight-Tolerance Precision Ground Rod, 7/16" OD
- Collimator Adapter (1X) Thorlabs AD11F SM1-Threaded Adapter, for 11 mm OD Cylindrical Components

DRAWN	07/10/2014	Queen's University	
CHECKED		TITLE	
QA		Photodetector Assembly	
MFG		SIZE	DWG NO
APPROVED		C	Detection_Assembly
		SCALE	REV
			1
			SHEET 1 OF 1

Appendix B

Software design

We used existing thin film deposition software/hardware to develop application software for data acquisition (DAQ) and system control for several new experiments. Building on the work of Tim Brown and others [417, 418], we used multiple computers to communicate with and control equipment using LabVIEW. We also relied on transmission control protocol/internet protocol (TCP/IP) over an ethernet link for data sharing using a client/server design architecture.

The existing instrumentation used a combination of LabVIEW 7.1 system design software, a SQM-242 thin film deposition controller on a PCI card manufactured by Inficon, and a DeviceNet interface for PCI manufactured by National Instruments. DeviceNet, which is based on a trunk-line/drop-line architecture with power and signal wires bundled into a single cable, was the original protocol used to communicate between devices because it is capable of modular expansion while maintaining relatively fast polling speeds for fast equipment control and communication (about 30 ms to 50 ms for this work). The instrumentation suite included pneumatic control valves, digital and analog I/O modules for relays and thermocouples, among others, and a

Bayard-Alpert Pirani capacitance diaphragm gauge from Inficon. We tailored this software to carry out this work and then integrated it with a brand-new system that we designed to suit our laboratory instrumentation communication needs.

To reduce complexity, and since new computers have fewer PCI slots and serial port based instruments are common, we wrote instrument drivers to communicate with and control several devices over USB ports (e.g. connected using a RS-232 to USB adapter), including

1. a Xantrex XHR 100-10 DC Power Supply,
2. a Keithley 2400 SourceMeter,
3. a Keithley 2000 Multimeter,
4. a Keithley 6485/6487 Picoammeter,
5. a National Instruments USB-6211 I/O Device, and
6. a Animatics SM23165D SmartMotor.

We used the Xantrex power supply to control the electrode potential of the ion extractor and connected the Keithley instruments to the ionization gauge detector. We measured the collector current, after transimpedance amplification, using the USB-6211 DAQ device (250 kHz sampling rate) for the phase-sensitive detection experiments. In this case, we used a producer/consumer parallel-loop design architecture to save the data. This method has the benefit of buffered communication; processes that produce and consume data at different rates are decoupled since data, as it is transferred from the DAQ board, is queued in memory and only later dequeued by a second loop that writes it to file. Finally, we drove the velocity selector using the

Animatics SM23165D SmartMotor (10 400 rpm no load speed, 0.28 N m continuous torque) and tuned the acceleration, commutation mode, and the PID controller to improve the performance and the stability of the motion system.

We iteratively designed and maintained our software applications to suit our experimental needs. All of the new systems are robust, have a reduced complexity, and overall our design implementations are a good fit for our communication needs.

Sunday, June 03 2018
2:08:28 AM

STOP RODNEY MONITORING PROGRAM

Loop Execution Time
48 [ms]

Room Temperature
22.6 [Celsius]

Input Water Temperature
13.9 [Celsius]

System Operation

Evaporation Experiment

Error and Notes

Quartz Crystal Microbalances

Open QCM1 Shutter

Open QCM2 Shutter

QCM4 Shutter Is Open

QCM Control

Selector (QCM2): Silver

Set Material: Set Material

Zero Crystal: Zero Crystal

Points to Ave: 10

Tooling: 100.0 %

Source

Electron Beam Evaporator

High Temperature Effusion Cell

Open Shutter

OK

Stepper Motor

Rotation Speed: 0.00 [rev/min]

Rotation Direction: Advance Rod

Rotation Speed: 0.00 [steps/s]

Current Position: 0 [steps]

Enable Stepper Motor

Reset Position

OK

Sunday, June 3, 2018
2:12 AM

STOP

System Operation Evaporation Experiment Error

Run Experiment

OK

ABORT

Progress

Evaporation Experiment

Status

Ready to Run Experiment

Elapsed Time

0 [s]

Estimated Time of Completion

Sunday, June 3, 2018
2:43 AM

Experiment Parameters

Speed

-2420 [rpm]

Data Collection Time

60 [s]

Increment

239 [rpm]

Delay

0 [s]

Maximum Speed

4750 [rpm]

Resonance(s)

0

2850 [rpm]

Enable Servo Motor

OK

Base File Path

RobbieMini2HD:Users:robbiegroupp\Desktop:
EvaporationExperimentPico:
EvaporationExperiment:Experimental_Data:
2018-06-03_013500

Telemetry

Servo Motor

40 [Celsius]

-0 [rpm]

Rotation Speed [rpm]

QCM4

Silver

0.92 [A/s]

Deposition Rate [A/s]

Chamber Pressure (Rodney)

1.996E-7 [Torr]

Pressure [Torr]

Selector

0.00 [A/s]

Deposition Rate [A/s]

Electron Emission Current

0.0002 [mA]

Current [mA]

Collector Current

0.0002 [nA]

Current [nA]

Appendix C

STM software design

LabVIEW-based control software is readily integrated with the Nanonis SPM controller. Here, the application software we developed for bias-/current-dependent imaging and real-time drift compensation is briefly summarized. Overall, the applications were reliable and helped expand our experimental capabilities.

C.1 Bias- and current-dependent imaging

In STM imaging, it is often useful to vary the bias and the tunnelling current to find changes in the observed contrast. Since each image is typically acquired in 10 to 30 minutes, bias- and current-dependent STM studies are best performed with automation. The program in [Figure C.1](#) steps through bias or current in either a linear or logarithmic ramp pattern during imaging. This relatively simple program allowed experiments to be performed overnight without user input.

Figure C.1: User interface for bias- and tunnelling current-dependent imaging.

C.2 Image registration-based drift compensation

We implemented a real-time method for drift compensation based on the TurboReg/StackReg plugin [331], which is an image registration technique used here for *in situ* lateral drift measurements. The program in Figure C.2 calculates a drift vector for consecutive image pairs and uses the result to offset the X and Y scanning piezos. It supports noisy multi-channel STM images and basic processing including plane subtraction and gaussian blurring. For robust and optimal performance, successive drift vectors can be exponentially weighted to reduce the impact of outliers caused by tip changes or noise. Overall, this program reduced the XY drift rate by 2 to 3 orders of magnitude at 77 K.

Figure C.2: User interface for real-time image registration-based drift compensation.